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Inflation : Strategies for Rebooting Progress

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ICAB publications include, inter alia, a quarterly journal titled 'The Bangladesh Accountant', half yearly Journal 'Bangladesh Economica' and ICAB's mouthpiece ICAB Monthly News Bulletin.

In the quarterly journal, articles of ICAB Members, Members from other Accountancy bodies, Academics and Business Leaders from home and abroad are published.

In half yearly journal, articles focus on macro-economy of the country are published.

The monthly news bulletin publishes different ICAB events of the month. This bulletin acts as an information hub for the Members to keep up-to-date about ICAB and its activities in addition to these publications, ICAB also publishes books, monographs, booklets and Students' Study Manuals regularly.

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“The future could be bright for Bangladesh. But success requires urgent action and coordination among various sectors. All the nation’s stakeholders – government and political parties, business, civil society, financial sectors – must urgently seize the opportunity to move Bangladesh forward, as entrepreneurs have seized the opportunity to create jobs and income.”

Md. Shahadat Hossain FCA
Chairman - Editorial Board and
Council Member - ICAB

The first quarter issue of The Bangladesh Accountant is expected to be a blend of reflections regarding issues on business and financial reporting. The ICAB Journal “The Bangladesh Accountant” is the platform where members of the Institute and the writers demonstrate their professional and pragmatic thoughts to promote and innovate matters of accounting, finance and pertinent issues for the economy. It has covered a wide range of contemporary topics. We have endeavored to collect views and opinion of academics and researchers on economic development prospects and recent issues of Bangladesh. Fellow members of the fraternity, especially the most recent qualified members in CAB, their judgment, advice, and inspiring words for “The Bangladesh Accountant” will always be treasures for its progress.

At present, the economy of Bangladesh is rolling its pace of growth in a progressive manner with some favorable economic indicators such as macroeconomic stability, despite inflation hit globally. A well-developed financial sector might play in defining a path of economic development characterized by sustainable, long-run economic growth.

Regardless of macroeconomic challenges, GDP growth is projected to be vigorous. The significant growth drivers are export, manufacturing, and services, driven primarily by domestic consumption. However, private investment, which stagnated in recent years, is expected to pick up with growing confidence on infrastructure development prospects, strong domestic demand, and stronger global markets.

With around two million young people entering the job market every year, Bangladesh must achieve export-led growth by breaking into new markets with new products to create more and better employment opportunities.

It is a well-known fact that economic development and growth will not be achieved if finances are not well

managed. Chartered Accountants render financial services to business owners and the community at large. This role of CA’s is more important now that the world is trying to recover from the shock of the financial meltdown that just rocked the global economy at large.

The future could be bright for Bangladesh. But success requires urgent action and coordination among various sectors. All the nation’s stakeholders – government and political parties, business, civil society, financial sectors – must urgently seize the opportunity to move Bangladesh forward, as entrepreneurs have seized the opportunity to create jobs and income.

We look forward to continued close relations and growing people-to-people ties as Bangladesh takes difficult steps to embark on a path of progress and thereby smart Bangladesh by 2041. To achieve this long-expected dream, development of infrastructure, power, energy, technology, knowledge and skilled manpower are ardent necessary. Regrettably still our education system requires matching with the need of our industry. Coalition between Industry and Academia are highly needed for ensuring sustainable development. With kindest regards to all.

President's Desk

“ This journal gives us invaluable insights of the economy generally trade, commerce, investment, capital market, fiscal policy measures, technical issues of accounting profession, etc. which enrich knowledge of readers, give thought-provoking ideas to key players and provide precious inputs to the policy makers. ”

Mohammed Forkan Uddin FCA
President-ICAB

‘The Bangladesh Accountant’, the journal of the Institute, is a platform of sharing knowledge on concurrent economic and professional issues. The objectives of this Publication is to add value to the development of professional skills as well as to help the various divisions and departments of the government to formulate policies facilitating a thriving economy of the country. This journal not only aims at projecting the technical matters and matters relating to our profession, but also how we play an important role in shaping our country to a developed and smart one.

As I went through the issue, the articles published in the journal mostly focused on macro aspects of concurrent socio-economic issues where our members can play an instrumental role in many different capacities, from performing key management functions to providing essential services as auditors. However, Chartered Accountants play a very supportive role in every organization where they are working in implementing formulated policies with the expected success.

This journal gives us invaluable insights of the economy generally trade, commerce, investment, capital market, fiscal policy measures, technical issues of accounting profession, etc. which enrich knowledge of readers, give thought-provoking ideas to key players and provide precious inputs to the policy makers. No doubt, the articles in this issue will meet readers’ expectations as well.

ICAB has been providing National Budget proposals to the government

regularly not only to improve its revenue collection, but also to create business friendly atmosphere for ease of doing business in Bangladesh. We had exchanged opinions & views regarding VAT, Tax & Customs policies with NBR Chairman. In addition, we have submitted written proposals focusing on salient features and various aspects of the national budget. Not just limiting to various recommendations and suggestions, the Taxation and Corporate Laws committee (TCLC) of ICAB organized a roundtable discussion regarding next National Budget’ aiming to help the people better understand monetary policy, fiscal policy, VAT & Tax revenue policies.

In conclusion, I extend my heartfelt thanks to the Chairman, the Co-chairman, Editorial Board and everyone associated with this publication for bringing out this issue successfully.

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A Study of Inflation in Bangladesh Economy and Strategies Applicable for Mitigation

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Introduction

The macroeconomic climate of Bangladesh in 2024 may be impacted by a wide range of factors, including GDP growth, inflation, the external sector, fiscal and monetary policy, human capital, poverty, the environment, etc. Global growth has declined to 2.9% in 2023 but will increase to 3.1% in 2024, according to the International Monetary Fund (IMF) (2023), while worldwide inflation is expected to remain at 4.3% in 2024. IMF also issues a warning about the dangers of rising interest rates and the war in Ukraine for the world economy. The external sector of Bangladesh, which includes commerce, remittances, and foreign exchange reserves, may be significantly impacted by these global changes. The World Bank estimates that Bangladesh's human capital index (HCI) was 0.5 in 2020, which suggests that a child born in Bangladesh today is likely to be only half as productive as an adult worker. Data on various socioeconomic indices of Bangladesh, such as poverty, life expectancy, population, CO2 emissions, forest area, etc., are also provided by the World Bank.

According to these sources, inflation might be the most significant macroeconomic factor affecting Bangladesh in 2024 because it has utmost impact on people's ability to buy goods and services, the cost of living, the ability of exports to compete and the

stability of the financial system. However, this is not a conclusive article, and depending on the situation and viewpoint, other elements might possibly be equally or become more significant.

Root Causes of Inflation in Bangladesh

The main causes of inflation in Bangladesh are:

- **Demand-pull inflation:** This occurs when the demand for goods and services in an economy outpaces the supply. As a result, prices for these goods and services increase (Money Masterpiece, 2023). An example of demand-pull inflation in Bangladesh in 2023 could be related to the recovery and growth in consumer spending following the COVID-19 pandemic. As the economy recovered, people started

**Demand -Pull
Inflation**

**Cost-Push
Inflation**

**Structural
Inflation**

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- Bangladesh continued to rise. This inflationary trend was clearly cost-push in nature, marked by supply shortages and a lack of dollar availability, leading to significant economic impacts from hoarders and importers facing uncertainties due to deferred LCs and fluctuating dollar rates.
- **Structural inflation:** This is caused by imbalances in the economy that lead to persistent increases in prices. For example, increasing the money supply, liberal debt policy, increase administration cost, and shortage of food can all cause structural inflation (Idrees, G.).

spending more, especially on consumer goods and services. This increased demand, combined with the gradual normalization of economic activities, might have outpaced the ability of businesses to supply these goods and services, leading to higher prices.

contributing to inflation in Bangladesh. The war led to an increase in commodity prices, which were already on an upward trend before the conflict began. Despite a subsequent decrease in global commodity prices, consumer prices in

Here is a chart of the inflation rate in Bangladesh from FY 2017 to FY 2023 based on data from Statista (2022):

- **Cost-push inflation:** This occurs when the costs of production increase, leading to higher prices for goods and services. For example, food price volatility, supply chain disruptions, a depreciating currency, and high oil prices can all contribute to cost-push inflation. In 2023, Bangladesh experienced cost-push inflation due to the aftermath of the Russia-Ukraine war, which started in early 2022. This conflict had a notable impact on global commodity

Between 2017 and 2021, the inflation fluctuated between 5.44% and 5.69%. However, in the year 2022, the inflation rate had crossed the threshold of 6% and reached 6.17%. In 2023, Bangladesh experienced a notable increase in inflation, reaching a peak of 9.49% in November. This was a significant rise from the previous year's rate. The Mastercard Economics Institute has projected that the inflation rate in Bangladesh for 2024 will be around 7.3%, indicating a potential decrease from the 2023 levels (The Business Standard, 2023a). This forecast aligns with a global trend of easing inflation pressures expected in 2024. The Asian Development Bank also provides an optimistic outlook for Bangladesh, forecasting an inflation rate of 6.6% for 2024.

Some possible root causes of inflation in Bangladesh in 2023 were:

- **Food price volatility:** As of 2024, the situation regarding food price

volatility in Bangladesh remains challenging. In 2023, the country experienced significant fluctuations in the prices of essential commodities, including rice, wheat, edible oil, sugar, and vegetables. These fluctuations were influenced by various factors like weather conditions, pests, natural disasters, market manipulation, and global market dynamics. Throughout 2023, there was notable discomfort due to high inflation, which affected the prices of daily necessities. Limited-income families struggled to meet their food expenses, with prices of items like fish, meat, eggs, and milk reaching high levels. Inflationary pressures led to an increase in the prices of several essential commodities, although rice and flour prices showed a marginal decrease. The situation was exacerbated by issues like dollar

shortages and increased import costs, which prevented consumers from benefiting from international market trends where prices of commodities like wheat and sugar fell (The Business Standard, 2023b). The situation in 2024 shows some improvements but still presents challenges. The World Bank reported that 71% of families in Bangladesh are concerned about rising food prices. Food inflation stood at over 12.5% in November, the highest in a decade, affecting low-income groups and threatening to push many back into poverty (Daily Industry, 2024). The government's efforts to curb inflation and stabilize prices have been a key focus, with Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina urging ministries to lower the prices of essentials and ensure uninterrupted supply chains, especially during critical periods like Ramadan.

- **Supply chain disruptions:** The Ukraine-Russian War have disrupted the supply chains of many goods and services, both domestically and internationally. This has led to shortages, delays, and higher costs of production and transportation. These effects have been passed on to consumers through higher prices.

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- Depreciating currency:** The exchange rate of the Bangladeshi taka against the US dollar has depreciated by about 25% since January 2022. This makes imports more expensive and reduces the purchasing power of domestic consumers. Bangladesh relies heavily on imports for many essential goods such as fuel, raw materials, machinery, and consumer goods and rising import costs have fueled inflation. As of January 2024, the exchange rate of the Bangladeshi Taka (BDT) against the US Dollar (USD) has seen notable changes. The highest exchange rate recorded was 110.0581 BDT for 1 USD on January 1, 2024.
- High oil prices:** The oil prices have increased by about 40-50% since

January 2022 due to rising demand and supply constraints. Higher oil prices have increased the cost of production for many sectors of the economy through rising transportation costs.

- Increasing money supply:** In 2023, the Bangladesh Bank implemented several changes in its monetary policy to address economic challenges. These changes aimed to balance the need for economic growth with the need to contain inflationary pressures. During the July-December period of 2023-24, the Bangladesh Bank maintained a contractionary policy stance. This approach was characterized by increasing the policy rate, also known as the repo rate, to 7.75% in an effort to reduce demand and contain

- prices. This rate hike was part of a broader strategy to manage inflation, which had remained over 9% since March of the previous year. The central bank's policy adjustments were made against the backdrop of a persisting foreign exchange crisis and heightened inflation. These challenges necessitated a careful approach to ensure both economic stability and growth. The policy changes included a focus on circulating more hard currency in the economy to meet liquidity needs, and a significant negative growth target in net foreign assets, indicating expectations of the depreciation of the Bangladeshi Taka. It is important to note that the Bangladesh Bank also pursued a cautiously accommodative policy stance from January to June of 2023. The main goals during that period were to contain inflationary and exchange rate pressures, support desired economic growth, and ensure an adequate flow of funds. The central bank's policies during this period reflected an effort to strike a balance between these various economic objectives
- Liberal debt policy:** In 2023, Bangladesh's private sector was tasked with repaying long-term foreign loan installments totaling \$1.62 billion, with more than

\$354 million allocated for interest payments. This amount represented a significant financial obligation amid ongoing dollar scarcity. In comparison to 2022, when repayments of private sector long-term loans were \$2.82 billion, there was a noticeable shift. The 2022 figure showed an increase of 29.6% from 2021, and the new borrowings in 2022 were \$2.82 billion, a decrease of 30.3% from the previous year. This trend underlines the challenges faced by the private sector in managing foreign debt

amidst fluctuating economic conditions and currency valuation issues. The increased cost of repaying these loans, exacerbated by the devaluation of the Bangladeshi Taka, put additional pressure on businesses relying on these funds

- **Increased administration cost:** To deal with the epidemic and its socio-economic consequences, the government has boosted its spending on salaries, pensions, subsidies, social

safety nets, and development projects. These expenditures, however, raise the cost of administration and governance, which can have an impact on the efficiency and efficacy of public service delivery. Increased administrative expenses can potentially cause inflation by boosting aggregate demand and causing fiscal imbalances.

- **Increase in lending rate in banking sector:** The cap on lending has been removed from fixed cap of 9% on all lending from financial institutions in 2023. This has significantly impacted cost of production and added interest costs are later passed on to prices resulting in inflation in all related sectors.

Impact of Inflation on Business

Some possible impacts of inflation on businesses in Bangladesh in 2023 were:

- **Higher revenue and profit:** Inflation may boost a company's income and profit if it can raise its prices faster than its costs. Businesses that produce or sell goods with inelastic demand and necessities such as food, health care, and education may benefit from inflation. Companies with a strong market position or who possess devoted client base may

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have greater pricing power and larger profits (Majumder, S.C., 2016).

- Higher costs and lower competitiveness:** In addition, increased input prices, such as labour, raw materials, energy, and transportation can raise expenses and reduce competitiveness. Companies that manufacture or sell non-essential or luxury products and services, such as tourism, entertainment, and technology, may be impacted negatively by inflation since demand is very elastic. Companies in a highly competitive market or with a small client base may have less pricing power and thus smaller profits (Rabab, S., 2022).
- Higher uncertainty and risk:** Inflation may also increase uncertainty and risk for organizations that must deal with erratic pricing swings, fluctuating currency rates, and shifting

customer tastes. Companies that must make long-term investment choices or prepare for future cash flows may experience additional difficulties as a result of inflation uncertainty (LightCastle, 2022).

- Lower real income and demand:** Inflation can also diminish consumers' and employees' real income and purchasing power, particularly those with fixed or low wages. This has the potential to lower demand for non-essential or luxury goods and services supplied by firms. This can have an impact on the sales and profitability of companies that rely on consumer spending.
- Higher interest rates and borrowing costs:** Inflation can also result in increased interest rates and borrowing costs for firms, when the central bank tightens its monetary policy in order to

limit inflation. Rising interest rates can raise the cost of capital for companies that need to borrow money for investments or operating capital. Increased interest rates can also restrict the availability of finance for firms, particularly small and riskier ones.

- Higher tax burden:** Inflation can also raise the tax burden for businesses since some levies are not inflation-adjusted. Corporate income tax, for example, is based on nominal profits, which may rise owing to inflation even if real profits stay same. Similarly, property taxes are levied on nominal property values, which may rise owing to inflation even if actual property values stay constant. A higher tax burden might affect a company's after-tax income and cash flow.
- Higher wage pressure:** Inflation may also put pressure on wages, as employees may demand greater salaries in order to preserve their actual income and living standards. Increased salaries can raise a company's labor costs and diminish its profit margin. Wage increases can also lead to labor unrest and conflict between companies and employees.
- Lower productivity and efficiency:** Inflation can also reduce corporate productivity and efficiency

since it requires more time and resources to manage inflation-related concerns such as pricing changes, inventory management, cost control, cash flow planning, and hedging measures. Reduced productivity and efficiency can have an impact on the quality and quantity of production as well as the delivery of services by firms.

- **Lower export competitiveness:** Inflation can also reduce a company's export competitiveness by increasing manufacturing costs and causing exchange rate swings. Increased manufacturing costs might lower export items' profit margins and pricing competitiveness. Currency rate variations can have an impact on the predictability and stability of export revenues. Reduced export competitiveness can have an impact on Bangladesh's foreign exchange reserves and balance of payments.
- **Higher input price volatility:** Inflation can also increase the volatility of input costs for firms, since prices for raw materials, energy, transportation, and other intermediate commodities fluctuate more. Increased input price volatility can have an impact on production process planning and budgeting, as well as raise inventory holding costs. Increased volatility in input prices can

potentially cause supply chain disruptions and shortages.

- **Higher consumer price volatility:** Inflation can also raise consumer price volatility for firms by causing price changes in final products and services. Increased consumer price volatility might alter customer demand and preferences, creating uncertainty in sales forecasting. Increased consumer price volatility can also lead to price wars and a loss of brand loyalty.

Impact of Inflation in Accounting and Finance Sector of Bangladesh

Some possible impacts of inflation according to World Bank (2022) on accounting and finance sector of Bangladesh in 2023 were:

- **Higher cost of capital:** Inflation may raise the cost of capital for financial institutions by causing interest rates and borrowing costs to rise. Rising interest rates can lower bank and financial institutions'

profitability and liquidity since they must pay more for loan commitments and working capital needs. Increased borrowing rates can also restrict loan availability and access for borrowing institutions, particularly small or riskier ones.

- **Higher valuation uncertainty:** Inflation may enhance valuation uncertainty for bank and financial institutions by causing price volatility in assets and liabilities. Financial performance reports, such as balance sheets, income statements, cash flow statements, and financial ratios, might be affected by higher variations. Increased value uncertainty can further complicate auditing, taxation, and compliance.
- **Higher exchange rate risk:** Inflation can raise the risk of currency rate swings for business entities, as the value of foreign currencies fluctuates more. Greater fluctuations can have an impact on the profitability and competitiveness of such companies that handle with international transactions such as imports, exports, remittances, and foreign investments. Increased exchange rate risk can also make hedging and managing currency exposure more difficult.

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- **Impact on accounting and finance services:** Inflation can significantly impact the demand for accounting and financial services. As businesses and individuals grapple with inflation-related challenges, there is an increased need for expert advice in areas such as inflation accounting, financial planning, investment management, risk management, tax advice, and compliance. This trend presents opportunities for accounting and finance organizations, potentially leading to higher income and expanded market prospects. Moreover, the complexity associated with financial reporting and management during inflationary periods further drives the demand for

specialized services in these sectors.

- **Higher financial reporting challenges:** Inflation may complicate financial reporting for accounting and finance organizations by requiring them to present extra information and disclosures to stakeholders and authorities. banking and financial Institutions, for example, may be required to report the consequences of inflation on their financial statements, including the impact on income, costs, assets, liabilities, equity, and cash flows. Bank and financial institutions may also be required to reveal the assumptions and estimations used in inflation accounting and valuation.

- **Higher ethical dilemmas:** Accounting and financial businesses may encounter additional conflicts of interest and pressure from customers and stakeholders as a result of inflation. Accounting and finance businesses, for example, may be required to balance the interests of various consumers of financial information, including as shareholders, creditors, managers, workers, customers, suppliers, government, and society. Accounting and finance businesses may also be required to maintain their professional integrity and independence in order to provide impartial and trustworthy accounting and finance services.

How Accounting and Financial Literacy can help to control Inflation in Bangladesh

Accounting and financial literacy can help individuals and businesses make better financial decisions and plan for the future. This knowledge can also help businesses understand their financial statements, track their performance, and evaluate their profitability.

Accounting and financial literacy can help to control inflation in Bangladesh by:

- **Financial Literacy for Informed Decision Making:** Improved financial literacy can empower individuals and businesses to make

informed financial decisions. This includes understanding and applying principles of budgeting, saving, and investing, which can contribute to a more stable economic environment.

- **Role of Fiscal and Monetary Policies:**

Knowledge of fiscal and monetary policies can aid the government and the central bank in implementing strategies that balance spending and revenue. Effective policy-making can help in managing the money supply and interest rates, which are crucial for controlling inflation.

- **Promotion of Financial Inclusion:**

Enhancing financial literacy can lead to greater financial inclusion, especially for underprivileged communities. This, in turn, can facilitate their participation in the economy, potentially leading to improved economic stability.

- **Regulation of the Financial Sector:**

Understanding the financial sector's dynamics can help in better regulation and oversight. This includes monitoring banking operations and ensuring compliance with financial regulations to maintain the stability of the financial system.

- **Public and Private Sector Accountability:**

Improved

financial reporting and transparency in both public and private sectors can lead to better decision-making and investment, thus influencing market behaviors related to inflation.

- **Agricultural Sector**

Diversification: Diversifying and upgrading the agricultural sector can help stabilize food prices and ensure food security, which is critical in managing inflation.

- **Strengthening Social**

Protection Systems: An effective social protection system can mitigate the impact of inflation on vulnerable groups by providing necessary support during economic fluctuations.

- **Human Capital**

Development: Investing in human capital through education, health, and skills development can enhance productivity and economic growth, which can be instrumental in long-term inflation control.

Conclusion

In conclusion, both the economy and the people of Bangladesh are adversely impacted by inflation, which is a complex and diverse problem. Inflation is caused by a rise in the money supply, an increase in production costs, and external factors like fluctuations in the value of the dollar and oil prices

around the world. Financial literacy is essential for reducing the impact of inflation on financial statements, financial ratios, and investment decisions in order to mitigate its effects. To combat inflation in Bangladesh, the government and policymakers must employ a multifaceted strategy. In order to keep inflation under control, it is essential to regulate the money supply. By implementing quantitative easing or setting interest rates, the central bank can control the money supply. The government must also take steps to control production costs. To control production costs, the Government of Bangladesh can adopt a multifaceted approach. This could involve providing subsidies and tax incentives for crucial raw materials to lower direct costs for manufacturers. Concurrently, investment in infrastructure development, particularly in transportation and energy sectors, can enhance efficiency and reduce logistical expenses. Another key strategy is to encourage technological advancements and innovation in the manufacturing sector, which can lead to more efficient production processes and reduced waste. Additionally, implementing regulatory reforms to streamline bureaucratic procedures can significantly reduce administrative burdens on businesses, promoting higher productivity and cost-effectiveness. Businesses that cut costs or invest in infrastructure to lower transportation costs, for

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instance, may be eligible for tax incentives. In Bangladesh, another important measure to combat inflation is to improve people’s financial literacy which is a post-facto scope for improvement. Financial literacy programs can be established by the government, particularly in rural areas where people are less likely to have access to financial education. With this knowledge and skill, people would be able to better manage their money and make better financial decisions. Information on saving, budgeting, investing, and inflation’s causes and effects can all be included in financial literacy programs. Sound macroeconomic strategies can give a favorable climate to organizations to work, set out business to open doors and embrace financial development. In addition, it may enable domestic and foreign investors to make educated investment decisions by providing a stable environment.

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Bangladesh: Inflation in 2023 and Its Trend in Early 2024

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Inflation is a rise in prices, which can be translated as the decline of purchasing power over time. Prices rise, which means that one unit of money buys fewer goods and services. The rate at which purchasing power drops can be reflected in the average price increase of a basket of selected goods and services over some time. This loss of purchasing power impacts the cost of living which ultimately adversely affect the economic growth. The consensus view among economists is that sustained inflation occurs when a nation's money supply growth outpaces economic growth. An increase in the supply of money causes inflation, Inflation is the equivalent of a regressive tax on the consumers. It also erodes the buying power enmasse. Those with tangible assets, like property or stocked commodities, are normally reapers of benefits from some inflation as it raises the real & monetary value of their assets

and stocks. Inflation is one of the major challenges of development phases in a country like Bangladesh. Inflation in January 2024 jumped at 9.86 percent from 9.41 percent in December 2023 at according to data from Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics (BBS). However various initiatives have been taken and are ongoing from the government including tightening latest monetary policy by Bangladesh Bank for January-June 2024. A target of inflation to be achieved at 7.5 percent by June FY24 is in book & action. The expected GDP growth target of 6.5 percent in the policy is on record notwithstanding the ongoing development & price spiral challenges. Annual inflation in the FY 2020-2021 was within acceptable rate of less than 6 % and around 6 % in FY 2021-2022. However, in FY 2022-2023 it rose to over 9%, & was 9.94 % in May 2023.

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Figure-1: Consumer Price Index (CPI) and Inflation Rate (Point to Point), BBS Month: January 2024

CPI Classification	2020-21	2021-22	2022-23	(Base Index 2005-06 =100)			(Base Index 2021-22 =100)			
				2022-23			2023-24			
				Nov'22	Dec'22	Jan'23	Nov'23	Dec'23	Jan'24	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
NATIONAL										
General index	288.44	306.18	109.02	333.07	331.35	333.34	119.10	118.40	119.60	
<i>Inflation</i>	<i>5.56</i>	<i>6.15</i>	<i>9.02</i>	<i>8.85</i>	<i>8.71</i>	<i>8.57</i>	<i>9.49</i>	<i>9.41</i>	<i>9.86</i>	
Food index	313.86	332.86	108.71	360.75	356.86	359.40	120.04	117.48	118.30	
<i>Inflation</i>	<i>5.73</i>	<i>6.05</i>	<i>8.71</i>	<i>8.14</i>	<i>7.91</i>	<i>7.76</i>	<i>10.76</i>	<i>9.58</i>	<i>9.56</i>	
Non-Food index	255.85	271.98	109.39	297.58	298.65	299.93	118.33	119.16	120.66	
<i>Inflation</i>	<i>5.29</i>	<i>6.31</i>	<i>9.39</i>	<i>9.98</i>	<i>9.96</i>	<i>9.84</i>	<i>8.16</i>	<i>8.52</i>	<i>9.42</i>	
RURAL										
General index	286.37	304.76	109.08	331.51	330.00	332.36	119.24	118.55	119.64	
<i>Inflation</i>	<i>5.59</i>	<i>6.42</i>	<i>9.08</i>	<i>8.94</i>	<i>8.86</i>	<i>8.67</i>	<i>9.62</i>	<i>9.49</i>	<i>9.70</i>	
Food index	306.40	326.34	108.79	354.44	350.28	353.23	120.07	117.70	118.42	
<i>Inflation</i>	<i>5.99</i>	<i>6.51</i>	<i>8.79</i>	<i>8.23</i>	<i>8.11</i>	<i>7.92</i>	<i>10.86</i>	<i>9.66</i>	<i>9.41</i>	
Non-Food index	254.51	270.42	109.54	296.61	297.74	299.16	118.46	119.36	120.79	
<i>Inflation</i>	<i>4.85</i>	<i>6.25</i>	<i>9.54</i>	<i>10.31</i>	<i>10.29</i>	<i>10.12</i>	<i>8.00</i>	<i>8.41</i>	<i>9.19</i>	
URBAN										
General index	292.27	308.81	108.87	335.95	333.65	335.15	118.76	118.00	119.37	
<i>Inflation</i>	<i>5.49</i>	<i>5.66</i>	<i>8.87</i>	<i>8.70</i>	<i>8.43</i>	<i>8.39</i>	<i>9.16</i>	<i>9.15</i>	<i>9.99</i>	
Food index	333.08	348.75	108.52	378.58	372.94	374.44	120.04	117.05	118.08	
<i>Inflation</i>	<i>5.15</i>	<i>5.02</i>	<i>8.52</i>	<i>7.95</i>	<i>7.45</i>	<i>7.41</i>	<i>10.58</i>	<i>9.46</i>	<i>9.98</i>	
Non-Food index	257.64	254.07	109.13	298.87	299.86	300.97	117.96	118.59	120.17	
<i>Inflation</i>	<i>5.88</i>	<i>6.38</i>	<i>9.13</i>	<i>9.54</i>	<i>9.51</i>	<i>9.48</i>	<i>8.17</i>	<i>8.39</i>	<i>8.43</i>	

Note : Figures in italics indicate inflation over previous year/month

General Inflation During FY 2023 and January-2024

The Consumer Price Index (CPI) is a measure of the average change over time in the prices paid by consumers for a basket of selected goods and services. Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics publishes the monthly Consumer Price Index (CPI) regularly. Throughout the year 2023 inflation showed an

upward trend and was volatile starting at 8.57% and ended at 9.41 %. It resulted into adverse grievances for consumers especially of low income-groups. (“Inflation climbs to 12-year high” The Daily Star, July 4, 2023).

By the end of 2023, consumer prices in Bangladesh were in a stable trend which did not sustain the beginning month of the new year 2024.

Food Inflation During FY 2023 and January-2024

In January 2024, food inflation slightly declined to 9.56 percent from December 2023 at 9.58 percent. The consumers at large suffer most from food inflation due to squeezed buying power. The period 4 months of August 2023 to October 2023 observed the highest food inflation. The last two months were stable due to various government initiatives like supply of seasonal essential food commodities.

Chart-1: General Inflation

Chart-2 Food Inflation

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Chart-3 Non-Food Inflation

Non-food Inflation During FY 2023 and January-2024

Non-food expenditures in education, healthcare, rents, clothing, transportation, entertainment and labor costs take a major share of income of consumers.

Non-food inflation in January 2024 rose to 9.42% from 8.52 % in December 2023.

Remarkably Demand of Some Essential Commodities Ahead of Ramadan

Demand of some specific import-based essentials such as soybean oil, palm oil, dates, chickpeas, yellow peas, pulses increase remarkably ahead of Ramadan each year amidst persistent inflation level.

The Ministry of Commerce of Bangladesh is responsible for regulating and implementing the policies applicable to domestic and foreign trade. It has a separate cell in the name of Price Monitoring and Forecasting Cell.

“To ensure the price-level of different essential commodities in a convenient range Price Monitoring and Forecasting Cell was established on 24.11.2014 under revenue budget within the Ministry of Commerce. Comparative analysis of different data on essential commodities such as production, demand, amount of import, stock and supply, domestic and international market price etc. is carried out by the Cell. The cell collects information from different organization regarding

production, stock, demand, supply, local and international market price, information on LC openings and settlement thereof pertaining to these essential goods. It further works as a helping hand of the Government to keep the market of essential commodity stable”. Ministry of Commerce-Price Monitoring and Forecasting Cell of The Ministry of Commerce of Bangladesh has a wing named Trading Corporation of Bangladesh (TCB) . Trading Corporation of Bangladesh (TCB) conducts its activities throughout the year by selling essentials commodities at subsidized prices at different places to ensure relief in some extent for the consumers especially from the low-income groups.

Photo: The Daily Star, 21 February 2024

“The global trend of elevated prices has seen some moderation primarily attributed to improved supply conditions and stabilized food and energy prices. However, Bangladesh’s economy has yet to experience an equal adjustment primarily due to domestic price rigidity, market imperfections marked by oligopolistic behaviors in certain commodities, and significant depreciation of the domestic currency, counteracting the potential advantages of reduced global prices.” MPS January-June 2023

Unusual Inflationary Pressure Started Since Russia-Ukraine War

Bangladesh kept its inflation rate below 6% during the COVID-19 pandemic periods. The rise in commodity prices arose since February 2022. In fact, the unusual inflationary pressure begins in Bangladesh along with the world after Russia- Ukraine war since February 2022. Russia and Ukraine are major exporters of several commodities such as wheat, natural gas, palladium, nickel, fertilizers, platinum, crude oil, refined aluminum, seed oil, corn. The war has disrupted trade, including global transport routes, and adding distortion in existing supply chains

Figure-2: Consumer Price Index (CPI) and Inflation Rate (Point to Point), BBS Month: March 2022 (2005-06=100)

CPI Classification	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	2020-21			2021-22		
				Jan'21	Feb'21	Mar'21	Jan'22	Feb'22	Mar'22
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
NATIONAL									
General index	258.65	273.26	288.44	290.03	290.96	291.96	307.02	308.21	310.12
<i>Inflation</i>	5.48	5.65	5.56	5.02	5.32	5.47	5.86	6.17	6.22
Food index	281.33	296.86	313.86	315.81	315.35	317.32	333.51	334.95	337.43
<i>Inflation</i>	5.51	5.56	5.73	5.23	5.42	5.51	5.60	6.22	6.34
Non-food index	229.58	245.00	255.85	256.97	258.18	259.44	273.05	273.93	275.11
<i>Inflation</i>	5.43	5.85	5.29	4.69	5.17	5.39	6.26	6.10	6.04
RURAL									
General index	256.74	271.20	286.37	288.33	288.70	290.68	305.83	307.44	309.62
<i>Inflation</i>	5.15	5.63	5.59	5.00	5.33	5.55	6.07	6.49	6.52
Food index	273.55	289.08	306.40	308.97	308.85	311.14	327.31	329.30	332.01
<i>Inflation</i>	5.27	5.68	5.99	5.46	5.72	5.84	5.94	6.62	6.71
Non-Food index	230.01	242.74	254.51	255.50	256.63	258.12	271.65	272.67	273.99
<i>Inflation</i>	4.93	5.53	4.85	4.15	4.61	5.03	6.32	6.25	6.15
URBAN									
General index	262.17	277.06	292.27	293.16	293.25	294.32	309.21	309.63	311.06
<i>Inflation</i>	6.07	5.68	5.49	5.05	5.30	5.31	5.47	5.59	5.69
Food index	300.30	315.83	332.08	332.50	331.20	332.39	348.62	348.75	350.65
<i>Inflation</i>	6.04	5.17	5.15	4.71	4.76	4.80	4.85	5.30	5.49
Non-Food index	229.00	243.34	257.94	258.94	260.24	261.21	274.92	275.61	276.61
<i>Inflation</i>	6.10	6.26	5.41	5.41	5.92	5.87	6.17	5.91	5.90

Note : Figures in italics indicate inflation over previous year/month

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Controlling Inflation

Price stability or a relatively consistent level of inflation allows businesses to plan for the future to match the expectations. Countries that experience higher rates of growth can absorb higher rates of inflation and for smart Bangladesh the smart control of inflation is very important. Bangladesh's financial regulator Bangladesh Bank shoulders the important responsibility of keeping stable level of inflation through monetary policy. The policy refers to the determinants of a central bank pertaining to the size and growth rate of money supply.

Bangladesh Bank (BB) issue the Monetary Policy Statement (MPS) half yearly. This policy aims to stabilize and uphold the internal and external value of the Taka (BDT) while concurrently fostering investment, employment opportunities, and overall economic growth.

"The inflexible nature of internal price adjustments, coupled with the persistent depreciation of the domestic currency, might impede a decline in domestic inflation despite recent reductions in international market prices. The inflationary strains and significant price surges observed in various essential goods during FY23 and the initial half of FY24 are likely to contribute to sustained inflationary expectations in the latter half of FY24. Elevated land and construction materials

prices have driven up asset prices, further exacerbating inflation risk. While cost-push factors primarily influence inflation in Bangladesh, BB prioritizes measures to curb inflationary pressures. This includes the continuation of tighter monetary policies and strengthened interventions on the supply side, aligning with the objectives outlined in the national budget for FY24. It is anticipated that an improved supply-side scenario, coupled with a stringent monetary policy and support from fiscal measures, will result in a decline in the inflation rate, stabilizing it at an acceptable level by the conclusion of FY24.

BB's strategic policy initiatives to ease external sector pressures and establish a unified exchange rate regime under a crawling peg system aim to mitigate downward pressure on the Bangladesh Taka (BDT). This strategy seeks to minimize the pass-through effects of BDT depreciation and contain inflation throughout FY24. Additionally, the benefits stemming from BB's policy-tightening measures throughout the fiscal year are expected to play a pivotal role in curbing inflationary pressures. Considering these factors collectively, achieving the revised target of 7.50 percent inflation by the end of FY24 appears feasible." MPS January-June 2023

Bangladesh Government should continue the subsidy on fuel and electricity sector to reduce

production costs and transportation costs for sustaining efforts of controlling inflation.

Import of sufficient essential commodities should be ensured and giving importance to all intricacies & complicacies of opening LC, sufficient dollars, timely transportation and distribution need to be taken care of for ensuring smooth operation.

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What you need to know about the purchasing power of money and how it changes

By JASON FERNANDO, Updated January 16, 2024

Inflation: What It Is, How It Can Be Controlled, and Extreme Examples (investopedia.com)

<https://www.thedailystar.net/business/economy/news/inflation-climbs-12-year-high-3360391>

Transforming Bangladesh: Digital Payment Revolution

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Introduction

Bangladesh has undergone a significant transition in recent years towards digital payment methods, revolutionizing the nation's financial transaction practices. Technological advancements, government initiatives, and changing consumer preferences have all contributed to the adoption of digital payment methods such as digital wallets, online payment platforms, and mobile banking. This article examines how Bangladesh's economy is impacted by digital payment systems, highlighting the benefits, challenges, and potential outcomes of this digital revolution.

Background

In Bangladesh, a country with a large population and a growing economy, cash has traditionally been the primary form of transaction. However, in recent years, the government and financial institutions have been actively promoting digital payment systems to improve financial inclusion, increase transparency, and reduce reliance on cash. A significant milestone in this digital payment journey was the introduction of mobile financial services (MFS) in 2011, which provided millions of Bangladeshis with access to formal financial services for the first time.

Mobile Financial Services (MFS) Growth

Since its introduction in 2011, the adoption of mobile financial services (MFS) has grown rapidly in Bangladesh. According to the latest data from the Bangladesh Bank, the country's registered mobile money accounts increased by 16 percent year-on-year, reaching 21.77 crore in October 2023 from 18.75 crore in the previous year. In December 2023, the number of registered clients was 22.04 crore, compared to 22.00 crore in November 2023, indicating a change of 0.17%.

Transaction Volume

The volume of transactions through digital payment systems in Bangladesh has experienced a significant increase. Based on the Bangladesh Bank's latest data for December 2023, the average daily transaction volume was Tk 4018 crore, compared to Tk 3989 crore in November 2023.

Financial Inclusion

Digital payment systems have played a crucial role in promoting financial inclusion in Bangladesh. According to the Global Findex database, while Bangladesh made great strides toward financial inclusion between 2014 and 2017, growth in account ownership has slowed in subsequent years. In 2021, 53% of adults in Bangladesh owned accounts

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with financial institutions or mobile money platforms, compared to 50% in 2017. According to Bangladesh Bank data, in December 2023, the total number of agents was 17.2 lakhs, with a total transaction count of 55.09 crore.

Impact of Digital Payment Systems on GDP

Digital payment systems can contribute to the GDP (Gross Domestic Product) growth of a country in several ways:

Increased Consumption

Digital payments can enhance transaction convenience and efficiency, potentially increasing overall consumption. When individuals find it easier to pay for goods and services, they are more likely to spend, thereby stimulating economic activity.

Financial Inclusion

Digital payment systems can help include more people in the formal financial system. This can lead to greater participation in the economy, as people can save, invest, and access credit more easily, leading to increased economic activity and GDP growth.

Reduced Transaction Costs

When compared to traditional cash transactions, digital payments can lower transaction costs. Businesses and people may be able to save money as a result, which would enable them to increase their spending or investments and support GDP development.

Increased Tax Revenue

Digital payments create a digital trail, which facilitates tax

tracking and collection for governments. This may result in higher tax collections, which might then be utilized to pay for infrastructure and public services, thereby promoting economic expansion.

Efficiency and Productivity

By lowering the time and resources required to conduct a transaction, digital payment systems can increase transaction efficiency. GDP growth may result from higher productivity across the board as a result.

Some Other Benefits of Digital Payment Systems

Efficiency and Convenience

Digital payment systems offer greater efficiency and convenience compared to traditional cash-based transactions. They enable faster and more secure transactions, reducing the need for physical cash handling and paperwork.

Transparency and Accountability

Digital payment systems promote transparency and accountability in financial transactions. Electronic records of transactions can help reduce the risk of fraud and corruption.

Cost Savings

Digital payments can lead to cost savings for both businesses and consumers. For businesses,

electronic payments reduce the need for cash handling and associated costs. For consumers, digital payments can eliminate the need for travel to banks or other financial institutions.

Challenges of Digital Payment Systems in Bangladesh

Infrastructure and Connectivity

The absence of proper infrastructure and connectivity in many areas of Bangladesh is one of the biggest obstacles to the adoption of digital payment systems in that nation.

Inadequate internet availability and restricted smartphone usage prevent the widespread adoption of digital payment services.

Security Concerns

It is increasingly common to see reports of Bkash accounts being hacked on social media. Despite companies' campaigns urging customers not to share their OTP or passwords with callers, such incidents continue to occur frequently. Security is a major concern for digital payment systems. Cybersecurity threats, such as hacking and phishing attacks, can compromise the security of transactions and

undermine consumer trust in digital payment services.

Regulatory Environment

The regulatory environment for digital payment systems in Bangladesh is still evolving. There is a need for clear and consistent regulations to govern digital payment services and protect consumers' interests.

Consumer Awareness and Trust

Despite the benefits of digital payment systems, many consumers in Bangladesh are still unaware of the advantages of using digital payments.

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Building trust and awareness among consumers is crucial for the widespread adoption of digital payment services.

Interoperability

The lack of interoperability between different digital payment systems is a significant challenge in Bangladesh. This means that users of one digital payment platform may not be able to transact with users of another platform, limiting the convenience and utility of digital payments.

Cash Dependence

Bangladesh is still heavily reliant on cash for everyday transactions, which poses a challenge to the adoption of digital payment systems. Encouraging a shift towards digital payments will require efforts to change entrenched behaviors and preferences.

Merchant Acceptance

Limited acceptance of digital payments by merchants is another challenge in Bangladesh. Many small businesses and vendors do not have the infrastructure or knowledge to accept digital payments, hindering the growth of digital transactions.

Connectivity Costs

The cost of internet connectivity and smartphones can be prohibitive for many people in Bangladesh, particularly those in rural areas or with low incomes. This limits their ability to access and use digital payment services.

Example of Successful implementation of digital payment systems

Several countries have successfully implemented digital payment systems,

leading to various positive improvements. Here are a few examples:

Sweden

Sweden's move towards a cashless society has been driven by several factors, including the widespread adoption of electronic banking services and mobile payment solutions. The country's government has also taken steps to discourage cash usage, such as implementing fees for cash transactions. As a result, cash usage in Sweden has declined significantly, with many businesses no longer accepting cash payments. This shift has led to greater efficiency in transactions, reduced costs for businesses, and improved convenience for consumers. of mobile payment solutions and electronic banking services.

Denmark

In Denmark, the use of cash has been declining steadily for years. Most businesses, including public transportation services, now prefer electronic payment methods. The Danish government has also introduced initiatives to promote digital payments, such as offering tax incentives for businesses that do not accept cash.

South Korea

South Korea has one of the highest smartphone penetration rates in the world, which has contributed to the rapid

adoption of mobile payment solutions. Mobile payment apps like Samsung Pay and Toss are widely used, and many businesses accept QR code payments. The South Korean government has also supported the shift towards digital payments by promoting the development of mobile payment infrastructure.

Netherlands

The Netherlands has a well-developed digital payment infrastructure, with electronic payment methods widely accepted. Contactless payments, in particular, are popular, and many businesses and public services prefer electronic payments over cash. The Dutch government has also introduced initiatives to promote digital payments, such as offering tax incentives for businesses that go cashless.

China

China has seen a rapid adoption of digital payment systems, primarily driven by mobile payment platforms like Alipay and WeChat Pay. This shift has transformed the country's economy, leading to increased convenience, efficiency, and financial inclusion.

Future Prospects

The possibilities for digital payment systems in Bangladesh are bright, even in the face of obstacles. The government and financial institutions are addressing infrastructure and regulatory challenges in order to encourage the expansion of digital payment systems use. The country's adoption of digital payments is also anticipated to be fueled by the rising demand for internet connectivity and the growing appeal of smartphones.

Recommendation

Implementing an effective digital payment system requires a comprehensive approach that addresses various aspects of the economy and infrastructure. Here are some recommendations for the Bangladesh government to consider:

Infrastructure Development

Invest in building a robust digital payment infrastructure, including electronic payment terminals, internet and mobile banking services, and secure networks.

Regulatory Framework

Establish clear regulations and guidelines for digital payments, including consumer protection measures, data privacy laws, and interoperability standards.

Financial Inclusion

Promote financial inclusion by ensuring that digital payment services are accessible to all segments of the population, including rural and low-income communities.

Public Awareness

Conduct public awareness campaigns to educate people about the benefits of digital payments and how to use them safely and securely.

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Government Support

Provide incentives for businesses to adopt digital payment systems, such as tax breaks or subsidies for investing in digital infrastructure.

Partnerships

Collaborate with private sector companies, financial institutions, and international organizations to develop and implement digital payment solutions.

Security

Implement strong security measures to protect against fraud and cyber threats, including encryption, authentication, and fraud detection systems.

Interoperability

Ensure that different digital payment systems can interoperate with each other, allowing for seamless transactions between different platforms and providers.

Capacity Building

Provide training and support to businesses and consumers to help them understand and use digital payment systems effectively.

Monitoring and Evaluation

Continuously monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of the digital payment system and make adjustments as needed to improve its performance and impact.

Conclusion

To sum up, digital payment systems have the potential to have a big impact on Bangladesh's economy by lowering costs, increasing financial inclusion, and enhancing efficiency and transparency. To fully reap the rewards of digital payments in the nation, however, infrastructure, security, and consumer awareness issues must be resolved.

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Shape of Future Banking: Perspective for Digital Banking in Bangladesh

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Abstract

Digital banking depicts a virtual process that includes online banking, mobile banking and beyond. It is a complete shift to internet for almost all that is banking. The use of technology to provide smooth end-to-end electronic processing of banking activities or transactions is known as "digitalization of banking" or "digital banking." Digital banking, which may be done from any location, is sometimes referred to as electronic banking, cyber banking, or virtual banking.

Keywords

Introduction, History, Governing Body, Features, Products of Digital Banking, Benefits and Drawbacks, Audit perspectives, Conclusion

Introduction

A digital bank is a bank that operates online and provides its customers the services that were previously available only at a bank branch. Digital banking is part of the broader context for the move to online banking, where banking services are delivered over the internet. The shift from traditional to digital banking has been gradual, remains ongoing, and is constituted by differing degrees of banking service digitization. Digital banking involves high levels of process automation and web-based services and may include APIs (Application Program Interfaces) enabling

cross-institutional service composition to deliver banking products and provide transaction services. It provides the ability for users to access financial data through desktop, mobile and ATM services.

Background of Digital Banking

By the 1990s, the Internet had become widely available and online banking started becoming the norm. The improvement of broadband and e-commerce systems in the early 2000s led to what resembles the modern digital banking world of today. The proliferation of smartphones through the next decade opened the door for transactions on the go beyond ATM machines. Over 60% of consumers now use their smartphones as their preferred interface for digital banking.

According to Statista, the digital banking sector will grow continuously over the next five years. This trend reflects the ongoing development and expansion of digital banking services in the foreseeable future.

The growth of digital banking is primarily driven by the increasing adoption of digital technologies and changing customer preferences, who are increasingly inclined to use digital channels for their financial transactions. Modern digital banks are capitalizing on this trend, offering fast convenient mobile and online

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banking services according to consumers' needs.

Guidelines for Digital Bank by Bangladesh Bank

The operations of a digital bank will be governed by the Banking Company Act, as outlined in the guidelines provided by the Bangladesh Bank. The license of the Digital Bank will be given under the Banking Company Act 1991.

The payment service will be operated under the Bangladesh Payment and Settlement System Regulations, 2014, according to the approved guideline. The board of the Bangladesh Bank has approved the Digital Bank guideline keeping provision for paid-up capital at Tk125 crore. The minimum shareholding of each sponsor will be Tk50 lakh

(maximum 10% or Tk12.5 crore), according to the guideline.

The Bangladesh Bank on Sunday granted digital banking licenses to two out of 52 applicants. The newly licensed banks are Nagad Digital Bank and Kori Digital of ACI. Besides, three other applicants, each backed by different traditional

banks, have been granted permission to establish digital banking windows.

Another three applicants - backed by fintech firms and other companies - may receive license after a six-month monitoring period to assess the performance of the initial two digital banks.

Features of Digital Banking

Products/Services of Digital Banking

Digital banking offers Savings Accounts for easy access to banking services and to preserve our money's purchasing power with interest. The products/services of digital banking are as follows:

- Current Accounts
- Cash Withdrawals and Deposits
- Fund Transfers
- Bill Payments

- Bank Statements
- Loans.

Audit perspective for Digital Banking

Digital Banking has the potential to significantly impact the audit profession in a number of ways. Here are a few examples:

Digital Banking can provide auditors with a secure and immutable record of transactions, which can improve the accuracy and transparency of financial reporting. Auditors

can use digital technology to verify the authenticity of transactions, track the movement of assets, and ensure compliance with regulations.

With the use of digital technology, auditing procedures could be automated to a greater extent than is currently possible. Smart contracts, for example, can be programmed to automatically execute certain audit procedures, such as checking for compliance with regulations or verifying the accuracy of financial data.

By using digital technology to automate certain auditing procedures, auditors could potentially increase their efficiency and reduce costs. This could lead to a more streamlined auditing process that is less time-consuming and add more value to the customer.

As Digital Banking continues to develop, there may be new opportunities for auditors to offer specialized IT auditing services. Auditors with expertise in IT could be in high demand as companies seek to ensure the integrity and accuracy of their technology-based systems. Overall, Digital Banking innovation has the potential to greatly impact the audit profession, leading to improved efficiency, accuracy, and transparency in the auditing process. However, there may also be challenges and risks associated with the adoption of digital technology, such as the need for auditors to develop new skills and expertise in this area, and the potential for errors

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or fraud in digital-based systems.

Benefits of Digital Banking

Digital banking systems are much more flexible and allow banks to add and expand features much faster than traditional systems. It relies on high-level process automation, web-based services and APIs to provide banks and their customers with high levels of cost efficiency, security and flexibility. Modern banking solutions enable a fully digital experience customer, generating real-time data streams and providing key analytics. We can transfer money between accounts using internet banking. We can start domestic and international fund transfers between and within banks.

Drawbacks of Digital Banking

The high proliferation of digital banking also ushers in certain associated risks e.g. Security Risks, Breach of Privacy, Disparity in Services, Cybercrime and Systemic risks. No provision is made for monetary deposits. In the absence of a steady Internet connection, our ability to access Internet banking services may be restricted. Additionally, when bank servers are down, they may have negative impacts. If we don't follow the security guidelines provided by the bank, such as creating secure passwords, not sharing passwords, or failing to log out of our Internet banking account and such others, we could become a victim of online fraud.

Conclusion

Digital banks are extremely popular around the world and have already gathered hundreds of millions of users. Some of the biggest and most well-known digital banks are Revolut and Wise from London, UK, Cash App, Chime, SoFi, and MoneyLion from the United States and many others around the world. Digital innovation is continuously modifying the landscape of the financial system all over the world. Bangladesh Bank (BB) promotes an enabling regulatory environment allowing innovation to make a robust, efficient and secured financial system. Accordingly, BB recognizes the role of digital platforms and usage of artificial intelligence in driving greater efficiency in the delivery of financial products and services and in widening the outreach of the financial system.

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Opinion

Bangladesh-India Multimodal Connectivity: Generating Mutually Rewarding Outcomes

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Backdrop

Over the past years, South Asia has continued to remain one of the most disconnected regions in the world. Political developments and geo-political realities have led to a situation where the traditional connectivities through riverine, rail and road routes, that was there in place historically, got disrupted and discontinued. However, it is encouraging to note that in very recent years several initiatives have been put in motion to reverse the prevailing situation, at least to some extent. In this context, the ongoing initiatives to deepen multimodal connectivity between Bangladesh and India merit special mention since these are likely to have far reaching impact and implications for the two countries as also for the South Asian region. For Bangladesh, these developments are of crucial significance from the perspectives of realising its developmental aspirations in going forward in the twenty first century.

As is said, geography does matter in development as it has crucial significance for geo-economics, and consequently, for economic development of a country. It is Bangladesh's good fortune that the country has a natural advantage to emerge as a regional transport hub thanks to its strategic location as a gateway to the Bay of Bengal (with a large hinterland going

back to southern China), as a transit route between Western and North-Eastern states of India and as a major link in the SASEC (South Asia Subregional Economic Cooperation) transport network which connects Western Asia with the ASEAN and East Asian countries. Indeed, realisation of the opportunities that could originate from this unique geo-strategic location should be seen by Bangladesh as a key advantage. This should also be seen as an important source of earnings in the form of export of transport and connectivity services. Closer bilateral multimodal connectivity with India could be a major driver of Bangladesh's development in this anticipated wider and broader scenario. The key challenge here is to identify appropriate modalities which would help both the countries to realise the potential benefits in a win-win manner.

The Changing Discourse

While closer transport connectivity between and among neighbouring countries is rather common and natural, regrettably, this is not the case in South Asia. History and politics had gone into play and South Asia remained a region with disrupted connectivity and fragmented transport network. There was a time when establishing closer transport connectivity with India was a taboo subject in Bangladesh and met strong opposition from powerful quarters, driven by a number of concerns and

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reasons. These were related to political consideration, security apprehensions and also doubts as to whether Bangladesh would benefit at all from connectivity arrangements with India.

The realities on the ground, however, has since changed. Over the recent past period, the mainstream discourse in Bangladesh has shifted from 'whether to provide connectivity' to 'how best to negotiate any such deal, how to address the attendant concerns of Bangladesh, how best to safeguard the country's interests and how connectivity deals could be negotiated to deliver win-win outcomes for both the countries'.

Several factors inform the aforesaid change in the perspective and the mindset that call for closer examination and analysis.

The potential benefits to Bangladesh that could originate from closer bilateral cooperation, through triangulation of transport connectivity, investment connectivity and trade connectivity, are becoming increasingly evident in recent years. The experience of regional cooperation and integration involving countries of the neighbourhood regions has evidentially revealed the benefits of harnessing deeper integration among geographically contiguous regions and helped to change the opinion in Bangladesh: the ASEAN-wide cooperation; Mekong Delta cooperation; SIJORI growth triangle that includes Singapore, Johor State of Malaysia and Rio state of Indonesia; and others. Regional and sub-regional cooperation, based on seamless connectivity and free movement of factors of production, has brought significant benefits to all the

participating parties in these groupings.

In view of Bangladesh-India bilateral connectivity, the argument that transport facilitation with India is mainly import facilitation, has also proved to be without merit. It needs to be emphasised that it is not the government of Bangladesh that imports from India; it is the country's private sector that does most of the imports. And private sector entrepreneurs do so because they find it cost-effective and profitable to source from India. Import from India allows the consumers in Bangladesh to get agricultural commodities and agro-inputs at competitive prices which help maintain food security and reduce price volatility in the country; these imports allow Bangladesh's entrepreneurs and producers to get intermediate products, raw materials and inputs at competitive prices and with short lead time; a large number of export-oriented industries in Bangladesh source intermediate materials and inputs from India at competitive prices. Indeed, it is the growing competitive edge of the Indian exporters which has led to Bangladesh's import diversion in favour of India.

There is no denying the fact that Bangladesh does have a large and growing bilateral trade deficit with India. While the deficit remains a concern for Bangladesh, this should, however, not be overplayed- in a globalised world, it is not bilateral trade deficit but global

trade deficit that should be the reasons for concern for the policy makers.

However, the above is not to say that Bangladesh should not put more emphasis on reducing the deficit by increasing her exports to India, but to draw attention to the fact that bilateral trade deficit with India, as noted earlier, allows Bangladesh to maintain trade surplus with many other countries such as the USA, UK and majority of the countries in the EU which are the key destinations of Bangladesh's exports, particularly of apparels. For example, Bangladesh has a large trade surplus with the USA, of about USD 7.0 billion, due to USD 8.5 billion worth of RMG exports to the country. These exports use a significant amount of imported inputs and intermediates from India. Thus, trade deficit with India helps Bangladesh to maintain bilateral trade surplus with other countries and helps reduce Bangladesh's global trade deficit. Also to note, about 47.0 per cent of Bangladesh's exports to India constitutes apparels items; a significant part of these exports use imported inputs from India.

The upshot of the above discussion is that one needs to look at the issues of bilateral trade with India in a more holistic and comprehensive manner. Hence, the important and pertinent question to ask is why Bangladesh's export earnings from India has remained so low, and how these

could be increased by taking advantage of the expanding import market of India, through greater competitiveness and by way of export diversification. The last point is important. If Bangladesh is to increase her exports to India, the country will need to have the supply side capacities in products that are imported by India.

Bangladesh's import from India, of about USD 15.0 billion, was about 17.0 per cent of the country's global import (in FY2021-22). As may be recalled, in 2022, India imported about USD 713.0 billion worth of goods, while Bangladesh's export to India was worth about USD 2.1 billion or less than one-third of 1.0 per cent of India's total global import. The pertinent question to ask is why Bangladesh is not being able to take advantage of this growing import market of India. The task at hand is to take concrete actions which would enable Bangladesh to take advantage of the expanding Indian import market. Not that Bangladesh is not making any headway in the right direction: it took Bangladesh 47 years to cross the milestone of USD 1.0 billion export to India, in 2017 as against only five years to cross the landmark of USD 2.0 billion in 2022. There is a growing understanding in Bangladesh that the challenge at hand is to identify and implement appropriate strategies to tap into the import market of India, by building supply-side capacities, through product diversification and by reducing

lead time, raising price competitiveness and reducing cost of doing business with India.

An efficient multimodal transport connectivity could play a critically important role in view of the above. The cost that the traders, producers and consumers are paying because of lack of good transport connectivity, in the form of high prices and erosion of competitive strength, is evidenced by a recent World Bank report which estimates that exporting from Bangladesh to Nepal (by land, via India) was 1.5 times costlier than exporting from Bangladesh to Sao Paulo in Brazil. Indeed, the trend will hold true for trading between any two points in the two countries because of the absence of seamless connectivity.

One often hears of losing the so-called captive market of North-East India in case Bangladesh would provide transit connectivity between Western and North East part of India for movement of goods. As is well-known, historically Bangladesh's exports to North-East states has been very low when compared to not only her global exports, but also in terms of exports to India. A major reason behind this is the low purchasing power of the North East states. As is well-known, India is at present investing heavily in these states. Connectivity through Bangladesh could be a significant win-win for both the countries in this context. An

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economically prosperous North-East will have more capacity to import from Bangladesh than it is being able to do at present. This will also provide Bangladesh an opportunity to reduce bilateral trade deficit through export of (transport) services.

It is to be noted that, in recent years a number of bilateral agreements and protocols are being put in place to address the connectivity deficits involving the two countries. It may be recalled in this connection that a number of bilateral connectivities had been in place that precede the emergence of an independent Bangladesh; however these were disrupted following the India-Pakistan war in 1965. Some of these such as the Akhaura-Agartala rail link are being revived only now. The bilateral Protocol on Inland Waterways Transit and Trade was signed in 1972 (with 8 protocol routes). A number of Agreements to establish new connectivities was signed in recent times. The Coastal Shipping Protocol was signed

more recently in 2015. India has offered Bangladesh free transit for exports to Nepal and Bhutan (September, 2022). To recall, Kathmandu and Thimphu have land transit deals with New Delhi which allows Nepalese and Bhutanese vehicles carrying export-import goods to come to the Bangladesh border points. Bangladesh has allowed India the use of Ashuganj river port for multimodal transport of cargo (through riverine and road routes) to Agartala. Regular transit between Western and North-East parts of India by using the Chattogram and the Mangla ports has started very recently (April, 2023) following the finalisation of the standard operating procedures (SOPs) a few years back. India has allowed Nepal and Bhutan transit facilities to trade with Bangladesh and third countries by using its territory.

The Search for Mutual Benefits

What should concern Bangladesh in view of the above is how to make the aforesaid

Agreements and Protocols, investments, infrastructures and other bilateral initiatives to serve Bangladesh's interests, so that the benefits are not mutually exclusive but complement each other in a way that generates win-win outcomes for both the countries. This is what should concern Bangladesh's policymakers since all these involve intensive negotiations. As is said in the WTO, in this type of discussions countries got not what they deserve but what they negotiate.

In view of the above, issues of cost-sharing and benefit sharing should be important considerations for Bangladesh from the perspective of establishing seamless multimodal connectivity with India. In addition to the various fees and charges, cost sharing needs to address issues of sharing the various expenditures related to the construction, use and maintenance of the multimodal connectivity infrastructures: for example, costs involved in keeping the rivers navigable; maintenance and depreciation cost; payment of road use tolls; costs associated with incremental air pollution, environmental degradation and congestion; sharing of costs to build new transport corridors geared mainly to provide transit facilities to India, to name a few. The principle of proportionality should guide the fixation of these. Some of the corridors will have asymmetric use, to mainly benefit the Indian economy and to serve the interests of Indian

transport operators and businesses. It will be in India's interest to share the associated costs (in accordance with proportional use of the infrastructure). An enlightened and strategic perspective on the part of India will be of advantage to both the countries. It may be noted in this connection that the aforementioned principles are in accordance with the relevant GATT Article as regards providing Transit facilities by one country to another.

The benefit sharing principle stipulates that the gains accrued from connectivity should be shared by the two countries on the basis of agreed proportionality. This should inform the sharing of benefits that would accrue from the savings arising from the difference between the costs of using the traditional routes and the new opportunities of connectivity. This would arise from savings in the form of shorter distance, reduced lower

fuel costs, lower time and other cost cutting elements arising from the use of connectivity through Bangladesh by the Indian users. Bangladesh will need to be cognisant of the fact that the fees, charges, tolls, construction cost sharing etc. to be borne by Indian users should be fixed in a way that makes the new routes commercially attractive to them. Otherwise, they will not be incentivised to use the new connectivities. Transit-related payments to be fixed by Bangladesh, for each route and corridor ought to take the 'economics of connectivity' into consideration. Also, as may be noted, it will be the Bangladeshi transporters, freight-forwarders and other relevant players who will benefit the most from the transshipment business within Bangladesh.

Bangladesh will need to ensure that the facilities, supports and infrastructure to service the transit are in place. The road rail, riverine connectivities and

transport corridors will have to be fit for purpose if the Indian businessmen and transporters are to be encouraged to use the route. The other point to keep in mind is that Bangladeshi traders and business people will also be able to take advantage of the connectivities that will be put in place. There could also be business opportunities in the form of joint ventures with participation of transport operators from both the countries. Thus, both sides have an interest in operationalising the Agreements on an expeditious basis.

The above argument is not mere theoretical conjecture but draws on partial experience. For example, it was envisaged by many at the beginning of the connectivity discussion that the Kolkata-Ashuganj-Agartala connectivity would be a major transit route once the Transit-Connectivity Agreement has been put into operation. However, this did not bring the expected results because the needed infrastructure was not put in place. Greater use of the multimodal connectivity and transshipment facilities at the proposed Ashuganj International River Port (AIRP) would have created business opportunities for truckers and transporters and others stakeholders in Bangladesh involved in transshipment activities, in addition to the income in the form of fees and charges. This was not to be because of lack of readiness of the AIRP.

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The aforementioned specific experience reveals that the two countries will need to make investment in the required infrastructure building, logistics, roads and trade facilitation measures with due urgency. If not, transport operators will be unwilling to take advantage of the connectivity Agreements. The same also holds true for fixation of fees, charges and tolls, as was pointed out above. Transport operators will have to find it economically viable to use any particular route. As was noted, while governments sign Agreements and Protocols, it is primarily the private sector and businesses, conscious about the balance sheet and driven by profit motive, who will choose to take (or not take) the advantage of any specific connectivity option.

From the perspective of operationalising the bilateral connectivity, as also the BBIN (BIN)-MVA, putting in place the required infrastructure at the borders, on both sides, is also critically important. The borders should be crossing points, rather than control and choking points. For this to happen, integrated customs stations (ICS) with harmonisation and standardisation of procedures and protocols, paperless trade, interoperability of systems and closer customs cooperation will be required. There is a need to set up single window facility at the Integrated Customs Stations (ICSS as in the ASEAN) for border crossing and customs

clearance. Mutual recognition agreements (MRAs) involving quality standards (e.g. in case of food items), certification, accreditation and lab-testing, among others, would need to be negotiated to reduce hassle at customs points. Political will and a sense of urgency are needed to make the BBIN-MVA functional (the MVA covers cargo-carrying vehicular movement, bus-passenger service and private transport). To recall, the MVA was signed in 2015 (the SOPs have also been negotiated); however, it could not be operationalised till now. This must be seen as an implementation failure.

Attracting Indian investment to Bangladesh, targeting the Indian market, taking advantage of the duty-free, quota-free preferential market access (to India and other countries), could potentially be a game changer from the perspective of Bangladesh's economic interests. In this backdrop, extending the DF-QF market access to Bangladesh (offered by India since 2011) for a time-bound period, beyond Bangladesh's LDC graduation in 2026, merits serious consideration by Indian policymakers.

Final Observations

As noted earlier, in recent times some positive measures have been put in motion towards seamless multimodal connectivity between

Bangladesh and India. In recent times work has been initiated to build a functional International River Port in Ashuganj; the four-lane Ashuganj-Agartala road is under construction at present. Some infrastructures are being built with the support of the Indian LOCs including the Akhaura-Agartala rail link and a number of others.

Bangladesh is currently also in the process of negotiating a Comprehensive Economic Partnership Agreement (CEPA) with India. Deepening of transport, investment, logistics and people to people connectivities and efficient trade facilitation measures (at the border and behind the border) will play a crucially important role if CEPA is operationalised and made effective. Indian investment in SEZs and the ongoing connectivity initiatives should stimulate the triangulation of transport, investment and trade which is mentioned earlier. This is critically important from the perspective of generating the potential benefits of the proposed CEPA with India. An enlightened and strategic view is required on the part of both the countries if the potential opportunities of deeper bilateral cooperation in the areas of seamless multimodal connectivity are to be realised in a win-win manner.

Appropriateness of Present Government Budgetary and Accounting Classification System for Preparing Smart Public Financial Reports in Bangladesh

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Abstract

This article addresses the various issues to review the fifty-six digit (56) budgetary and accounting classification systems for digitally recording and reporting governmental financial transactions. The Government of Bangladesh (GoB) is bound to prepare two important financial statements called Annual Finance Accounts (AFA) and Annual Appropriation Accounts (AAA), following the fifty-six digits code(s) to fulfill the reporting requirement for the GoB. Moreover, to meet the accountability and transparency obligations of government financial affairs, AFA and AAA are prepared as per Section 4 of the Comptroller and Auditor General (C&AG) Additional Functional Act 1974. This article also analyzes relevant laws and regulations for the Government Budgetary and Accounting Classification System (BACS) [Also known as Code of Accounts/Chart of Accounts (CoA)] to facilitate international comparison and consolidation of government accounts. This is a qualitative study and six Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) and content analysis were conducted to collect data. However, the collected data were analyzed based on their themes. Government Finance Statistics-2014 (GFS-2014) of the International Monetary Fund (IMF) has also been critically analyzed to examine the process of preparing BACS/CoA. GFS Manual (GFSM) instructions were compared

with the supporting laws and regulations of the GoB to identify 'Methodological Gap(s) (If any),' in the practice of governmental accounting and reporting system in Bangladesh. The outcome of the research will be helpful to government accountants in finding out the reporting entities, the nature of the transactions and the sectors of the government where the transactions occurred to ensure the smart Public Financial Management (PFM), accounting and reporting as well.

Keywords

Annual Finance Accounts, BACS, Government Accounting, Reporting Entities, Smart Public Financial Management.

Introduction

Smart public financial reporting is a process of digitally integrating governance indicators, i.e., financial data integrity, accounts reconciliation, timeliness of in-year budget reports and quality of financial statements (Kristensen et al., 2019, Kuddus, 2023). Public Financial Management (PFM) scholars argued that a well-organized and systematic classification of budgets and accounts is an effective tool in preparing, managing and implementing the budget and accounting functions to ensure smart Public Financial Management (Sandeep Saxena, David Gentry, Kris Kauffmann, and Than Lwin, 2014). Cooper and Pattanayek also argued that a practical

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accounting and reporting system must offer precise financial information on government activities on time (Cooper, J. and Pattanayek, S., 2011).

However, the existing Budget and Accounting Classification System (BACS) of Bangladesh has a history of evolution. In 1938 government accounts were classified based on major heads and minor heads (Ministry of Finance, Finance Division, GoB, 2018). Aftermath, four (4) levels and thirteen (13) digits classification system was introduced in 1998 following the recommendation of the Committee of Reforms in Budgeting and Expenditure Control (CORBEC). The CORBEC project was started in 1989 (Timoshenko & Adhikari, 2009, Kuddus et al., 2019). Outcomes of the CORBEC report were accepted by the

GoB in 1993 and commenced a new project named Reform in Budgeting and Expenditure Control (RIBEC) in 1995 (Ministry of Finance, GOB, 1992). The RIBEC project ended in 2002 with some valuable outcomes relating to government financial management. Important outcomes of the RIBEC project were the introduction of a new digital classification chart for budgeting and accounting and the automation of government accounting in the Comptroller General of Accounts (CGA) office (Finance Division, Ministry of Finance (GoB), 2017). The classification system is an ongoing process. So, it takes different shapes and designs with the demand of time and technological advancement. Hence, to minimize the classification system's existing limitations, a task force was formed in 2012 with eleven

members' of expert persons in this field. Considering the recommendations of the task force fifty-six (56) digits classification system was initiated along with nine (9) segments in 2018 (Khan, 2019). As the BACS is a robust tool in public financial management as well as accounting and reporting, very limited research has been done in this field. However, this article's prime aim is to determine the appropriateness of the Budget and Accounting Classification System (BACS) in digitizing government budgets and accounting reporting to ensure Artificial Intelligence (AI) based smart public financial management in Bangladesh. It also explores the documents and legal procedures used for the Budget and Accounting Classification System that can be judged on the appropriateness of the BACS.

Structure of BACS/CoA

The following table shows the structure of the Budgetary and Accounting Classification System (BACS):

Table 1: Summary of the New Budget and Accounting Classification System

Segment Type	Segment Name	Digits	Purpose
Core Posted Segments (Users to enter data compulsory in iBAS++)	Organizational/Institutional	13	Identifies different institutional categories, including local government, public non-financial institutions, public financial institutions, ministries, divisions, departments and other organizational units.
	Operation	9	Identifies operational activities such as special, general, support, transfer to local government/development, ADP/non-ADP programs, and further details for development plans, projects, programs, etc.
	Sources of Fund	8	Identifies the Consolidated Fund, Public Accounts of the Republic, and further information on a consolidated fund similar to the general fund, a specific foreign fund, and foreign grants.
	Economic Nature	7	Determines the economic nature of transactions including products and services, pay and allowances, taxes, and other items.
Additional Posted Segments (Users to enter limited data as required in iBAS++)	Mode of Financing	1	Identifies the type of project finance, such as Direct Project Aid (DPA), Reimbursable Project Aid (RPA) via special accounts and RPA via the GoB are available.
	Location	9	Identifies the location of the transaction, i.e., Union/Thana/District/ Division etc.
Reporting Segments (Pre-defined in iBAS++)	Authorization	1	Identifies parliamentary requirement, charged expenditure (Non-voted) and other (Voted) expenditure
	COFOG	4	Indicates United Nations Classification Of The Function Of Government (COFOG) in ten (10) categories
	Budgetary Sector	4	Indicates Bangladesh government's sector classifications of fourteen (14) sectors to recognize the purpose of the transaction maintaining IMF's categorization of the function of government (COFOG)
Total number of codes		56	

Source: Developed by the researcher from field study and documentary analysis, 2021

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Research Methods and Materials

This is a qualitative study and the study uses primary and secondary data to draw practical conclusions on the problem investigated. For collecting preliminary data, 6 Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) were conducted on the accounts and audit officers working under the Comptroller General of Accounts (CGA) offices and the Comptroller and Auditor General (C&AG) office in Bangladesh. Content Analysis (CA) and Thematic Analysis (TA) were used for analyzing

qualitative data as a robust tool (Nowell et al., 2017, Braun & Clarke, 2006). For thematic analysis, collected data were categorized based on their theme. For content analysis, the European Systems of Accounts (ESA)-2010, National Systems of Accounts (SNA)-2008, Government Finance Statistics (GFS)-2014, Annual Appropriations Accounts (AAA), and Annual Finance Accounts (AFA) were used as the standard materials for the study. Cross tabulations were used for presenting processed data and information in line with the Information Fit Theory as it

is an Information System (IS) research (Hasan Ouda, 2019). Since the main goal of this study is to determine the underlying factors that motivated the government of Bangladesh to dispose of the 13-digit budget and accounting classification system within 20 (twenty) years of its introduction, it also aims to assess the new 56-digit BACS's strengths and weaknesses and identify any obstacles—if any—that users may be encountering when implementing the new system in the areas of budget preparation, budget execution, accounting, and reporting. By collecting and

analyzing firsthand qualitative data, the researcher has tried to address the following questions: How well did BACS categories adhere to the Government Finance Statistics Manual-2014 (GFSM-2014)? Does the iBAS++ system produce GFS reports that meet IMF requirements? Does the BACS budget sector classification align with the UN Classification of Function of Government (COFOG) classification? Would program budgeting be supported in the future by the new BACS?

Analysis of Data and Facts

This section contains two parts. Firstly facts analysis based on content analysis such as government budgetary and accounting classification manual (BACS, Vol. I, Vol. II and Vol. III), Annual Appropriation Accounts (AAA), Annual Finance Accounts (AFA), relevant laws and regulations, published articles and books, etc. and Secondly, analysis of data and information derived

from Key Informant Interviews (KIIs).

Methods of Following BACS/CoA

According to the government Budget and Accounting Classification System (BACS, 2017), the Bangladesh government accounting and reporting system is based on coding. This system uses a modified-cash basis approach and a double-entry accounting system (Finance Division, Ministry of Finance (GoB), 2017). This system has 1, 13,278 organizational, 37,709 operational, 2,046 fund and 1,909 economic codes (Finance Division, Ministry of Finance (GoB), 2017). As the CoA is a critical element of governmental financial accounting and reporting system, preparing a CoA method has needed to be examined. Government offices use fifty-six (56) digits and nine (9) levels of CoA. The rationality of designing and using fifty-six (56) digits and nine (9) levels of CoA for accounting and reporting public money has been critically examined in the following parts:

Posted Segments (Data entry required)						Non-posted Segmented (Data entry not required)		
Core Part (4 segments and 37 digits)				Additional Part (2 segments and 10 digits)		Reporting part (3 segments 9 digits)		
Organizational (13)	Operation (9)	Fund (8)	Economic (7)	Mode of payment (1)	Location (9)	Authorization (1)	COFOG (4)	Budget sector (4)

Source: Developed by the researcher from field study and documentary analysis, 2021

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From the above table, it is seen that there are three parts to the budgetary and accounting classification system. These are core parts, additional parts and reporting parts. In the core parts, there are four levels, e.g., the organizational level contains 13 digits, the operational level has 9 digits, the fund level contains 8 digits, and the economic level contains 7 digits. In the additional part, there are two levels, e.g., mode of payments bearing 1 digit and location levels that bear 9 digits. In addition to these parts, other parts remain called reporting parts. This part contains three levels: authorization has 1 digit, COFOG has 4 digits and the budget sector has 4 digits. The accounting and reporting requirement of BACS/CoA has elaborated in the following manner:

Organizational Segment

In BACS/CoA organizational segment is positional. To illustrate the dimensions of the organizational segment, here is an example of a detailed code and name of the organization,

e.g., 1240209118384 Cikondandi Katakali Government Primary School. The first (1) digit in this segment represents a public sector organization. The next two (2) digits represent the ministry/division. The directorate or department is represented by the subsequent two (2) digits. The last six digits of the position denote the institutional unit, and the next two (2) digits represent subordinate offices/institutions. The first digit of this 13-digit segment has been kept for the public sector. In BACS, the idea of a chart of accounts was creatively integrated. The ability to more easily record the budgets and accounts of a larger variety of governmental organizations outside of the budgetary central government in iBAS++ is the primary advantage of recognizing the category of a public entity. At the beginning of the administrative segment, a new component can identify the type of public entity that has been detailed in the following table (Finance Division, Ministry of Finance (GoB), 2017).

This additional coding element for the category of organization can be used to expand account coverage to include all autonomous bodies, local governments, and State-Owned Enterprises (SOE). This categorization scheme facilitates the application of the International Public Sector Accounting Standard Board (IPSASB) and GFS-compliant reporting in Bangladesh's general government organizations.

Operation Segment

Budget and accounting data can be recorded according to operations allowed by the BACS operation section. Activity, sub-activity, task/scheme/project group, and task/scheme/project are its four aspects. Here is an example of a detailed code and operation name, such as 224013114 productions and textbook distribution, to show the size of the operation section. The first one (1) digit designates the activities that are either 1-operating or 2-development. The subsequent digit denotes sub-activities. 1-general activity, 2-special activities, 3-support activities, and 4-transfers to local governments are all considered sub-activities under operating activity. 1-non-annual and 2-annual development programs are sub-activities under the development activity. The task, schedule, and project group are represented by the next five (5) digits. The next two digits correspond to a particular job, plan, or project (Finance

Table 2: Description of Organizational Segment

Code	Types of Organization
1	Budgetary Central Government
2	Extra-budgetary central government
3	Local government
4&5	Other general government
6	Non-financial public corporations
7	Public financial corporations
8-9	Others

Source: Developed by the researcher from field study and documentary analysis, 2021

Division, Ministry of Finance (GoB), 2017). Descriptions of operation segments are given in the following table:

Fund Segment

The fund section's objective is to identify and manage the sources of funds that will be utilized at payment time. Transactions affecting the public accounts of republics and those involving the consolidated fund are distinguished in this section. There is a difference between transactions using restricted and unrestricted funds in the fund segment within the consolidated fund. There was no fund segment in the previous thirteen (13) digit classification system. Here is an example of a detailed fund code

and name, such as 13029268 Loan-IDA, to show the components of the fund section. The initial one (1) digit is for types such as 1- consolidated fund, 2- public account of the republic and 3- general fund. The next one (1) digit is for a sub-type such as 1- general fund, 2- specific foreign grant and 3- specific foreign loan. The next three (3) digits are to capture data regarding the source of a fund such as GoB, foreign government organizations/international organizations, etc. The next three (3) digits are to capture specific components/agreements related to that funding (Finance Division, Ministry of Finance (GoB), 2017). Descriptions of fund segments are given in the following table:

Table 3: Description of Operation Segment

Code	Types	Code	Details
1	Operating Activities	11	General activities
		12	Special activities
		13	Supporting activities
		14	Transfer to local governments
2	Development Activities	21	Non-annual Development Program
		22	Annual development program

Source: Developed by the researcher from field study and documentary analysis, 2021

Table 4: Description of Fund Segment

Code	Type	Code	Type
1	Consolidated fund	11	General fund
		12	Specific foreign grant
		13	Specific foreign loan
2	Public Accounts of the Republic	20	Public Accounts of the Republic

Source: Developed by the researcher from field study and documentary analysis, 2021

Economic Segment

The economic section aims to support international standards in accounting, reporting, and control. It also gives information on government payments and receipts in a format that is helpful for national account preparation and macroeconomic modeling. To illustrate the dimensions of economic code, here is an example of detailed code and name of the financial segment, e.g., 3255102 printing and binding. The initial one (1) digit is for the type that identifies each of the major elements, such as revenues, recurrent expenditures, assets, etc. A high-level aggregate of each major component, such as employee compensation, products and services, etc., under the expenditure head and tax revenues, non-tax revenues, etc., under the revenue head, is provided by the category with the next one (1) digit. A subcategory that combines each main component's smaller components is represented by the next one (1) digit. The breakdown of each sub-element is shown in the item's subsequent one (1) digit. The next (1) digit corresponds to a sub-item that provides lower-level data for the head of ministries/institutions to plan, monitor, and assess revenue/expenditure. The next two (2) digits are comprehensive and offer data to help decision-makers further break down forms (International Monetary Fund, 2014). Descriptions of economic

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<p>segments are given in the following table:</p> <p>Mode of Payment Segment</p> <p>The section on modes of finance is designed to outline the various funding options for public works initiatives. To identify whether projects are directly financed by the government or get funding from outside sources, this new segment will use a single (1)</p>	<p>digit identifier. The following table provides descriptions of each segment of the payment method:</p> <p>Location Segment</p> <p>The location part allows the overall government spending and receipts statistics to be arranged geographically, for example, by Union Parishad, Upazilla, Districts, and Divisions. It will provide substantial and rational data for cross-regional</p>	<p>government spending comparison. The following table provides descriptions of the location segments:</p> <p>Authorization Segment</p> <p>The rationale of the authorization segment is to distinguish between charged (Non-voted) expenditures and other (Voted) expenditures. This segregation is a constitutional obligation and consequently</p>
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Table 5: Description of Economic Segment

Code	Segments Name
01	Recurrent revenue
02	Capital revenue
03	Recurrent expenditure
04	Capital expenditure
05	Holding gains and losses
06	Volume changes
07	Assets
08	Liabilities
09	Net financial worth

Source: Developed by the researcher from field study and documentary analysis, 2021

Table 6: Description of the Mode of Payment Segment

Code	Mode of Payment
01	RPA through GoB
02	RPA through special accounts
03	Direct Project Aid (DPA)

Source: Developed by the researcher from field study and documentary analysis, 2021

Table 7: Location Segment

Code	Location Code	Descriptions				
02	Division	Barishal	Borguna	Amtoli	Huludia union	Detail code
02	District	10	04	09	344	100409344
02	Upazilla	100409344 indicates that, Barishal Division, Borguna District, Amtoli Upazilla and Hulodia Union				
03	Union					

Source: Developed by the researcher from Field Data and Contents Analysis, 2021

integrated into the new BACS. Descriptions of authorization segments are given in the following table:

COFOG Segment

This segment has been incorporated in the new BACS to produce reports in conformity with the

Classification of Functions of Government (COFOG) as recommended by the statistics division of the United Nations. This will help generate COFOG reports from the iBAS++ system (International Monetary Fund, 2014). Descriptions of COFOG segments are given in the following table:

Budget Sector

In addition to the COFOG, a separate component has been added to the new BACS to categorize anticipated spending by budget sectors. With economic function enlarged to fourteen (14) budget sectors, COFOG is linked to nine (9) of the budget sectors. Descriptions of the budget sector are given in the following table:

Table 8: Description of Authorization Segment

Code	Authorization Segment
01	Charged expenditure
02	Other expenditure

Source: Developed by the researcher from field study and documentary analysis, 2021

Table 9: Description of COFOG Segments

Major head		Minor head		Detail	
Code	Type	Code	Type	Code	Type
01	General govt. services	013	General services	0131	General employee services
02	Defence	021	Military defence	0210	Military defence
03	Public order and security	031	Police services	0310	Police services
04	Economic Affairs	043	Fuel and Energy	0435	Energy
05	Environment protection	051	Waste management	0510	Waste management
06	Housing and community amenities	061	Housing development	0610	Housing development
07	Health	073	Hospital services	0733	Medical and maternity services
08	Recreation culture and religion	082	Cultural services	0820	Cultural services
09	Education	091	Pre-primary and primary education	0912	Primary education
10	Social protection	101	Sickness and disability	1012	Disability

Source: Developed by the researcher from field study and documentary analysis, 2021

Table 10: Description of Budget Segment

Code	Type	Code	Type
01	General administration	0102	Administrative activities
02	Defence activities	0201	Military defence
03	Public order and security	0304	Anti-corruption
04	Industrial and economic activities	0408	Labor and Employment
05	Agriculture	0505	Irrigation
06	Power and Energy	0602	Oil, gas and natural resources
07	Transport and communication	0701	Road transport
08	Local government and rural development	0804	Hill tracts affairs activities
09	Environmental protection	0903	Forestry
10	Housing and citizen amenities	1003	Housing establishment and city development
11	Health	1104	Other health affairs activities
12	Recreation, culture and religion	1208	Religious affairs
13	Education and technology	1308	Information and communication technology
14	Social security	1405	Disaster management and relief

Source: Developed by the researcher from field study and documentary analysis, 2021

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Analysis of Data and Information Derived From Key Informants Interview (KII)

To review the boundaries selected for this research, primary data were collected through Key Informant Interviews (KIIs). Information provided by the broad and diverse participants could be reasonably applicable to establish the bridge between the research problem and the key research objectives. An excerpt is taken from the C&AG Bangladesh official that describes the impact of the Budget and Accounting Classification System (BACS) in recording and reporting government financial transactions:

With the help of the BACS/CoA, all budgeted receipts and expenditures are entered into the Integrated Budget and

Accounting System (iBAS++) software beforehand. An office/officer can only spend a single coin with the prior allocation made in the respective code(s) budget. Moreover, coding is used for identifying the administrative bodies responsible for accounting and reporting functions and operations, i.e. the activities are general or special type activities. From the fifty-six (56) digit code user can quickly determine whether the fund is RPA -GoB or RPA through a special account of a development partner or DPA. In addition, the coding system helps determine whether the items are revenue or expenditure type, assets or liabilities and net worth of Bangladesh, charged (Non-voted) expenditure and other (Voted) expenditure. The coding system has already ensured the accounting and reporting system is centralized,

but services are decentralized. Bookkeeping and the traditional accounting cycle could not be made in the human interface. Rather the whole government accounting and reporting system is computerized. With the invention of code, debit and credit systems in government accounting are now replaced by data science or data analytics systems. BACS has minimized the human interface in accounting services as the software makes financial statements with necessary disclosures (KII 1 and 6, C&AG officials, Dhaka)

The C&AG officials are not alone in these views. Other central and field accounting offices of GoB also supported this statement about the rationality of BACS/CoA. One of the field levels of accounting officers working under the Department of Primary and Mass Education has echoed the same way relating the relevance of coding in line with managing big data regarding government accounting and reporting systems in Bangladesh. The accounting officer describes the necessities of BACS/CoA in the following way:

First, we have to send a demand letter to our superior office describing in detail the codes and sector-based allocation of total budgeted expenditure under the jurisprudence of revenue budget. We think the present government accounting system is an information system because in the time preparing the projected budgeted

amount, we made an analysis of the human resources working in the office, the Post Retirement Leave (PRL) information, recreational demand information, information of teachers and employees working in the whole Upazilla and other overhead expenditures. All allocations are made and get approval against the code(s) duly (KII 2, DPEO, Upazilla accountant, Rajshahi).

The audit and accounts officers working at the CGA office reiterated the relevance of BACS for the governmental accounting and auditing system in Bangladesh. They have asserted that:

All allocations under the budgetary central government are made against the code(s). Various expenditures relating to salary and wages, administrative expenditure, fees, charge and commission, training, petrol, oil and diesel, traveling and transfer, printing and stationery, supply and raw materials, honorarium and special expenditure, maintenance, furniture and fixtures and other fixed assets are allocated to their respective code(s) for accounting and reporting purposes (KII 3 CGA officials, Dhaka).

Upazilla Accounts and Finance Officers (UAFO) working under the jurisdiction of the CGA have also supported BACS/CoA that:

Coding is the cornerstone of government accounting and reporting systems. This is not a new thing, but fifty-six (56)

digits nine (9) levels multi-purpose coding system is the addition of the previous thirteen (13) digits four (4) level code. In 1989 code was in Roman numeric and was divided into major and minor heads. Later the coding system transferred to Arabic numeric, and after 2009, a thirteen-digit coding system was introduced. Finally, in 2014, the coding system moved into fifty-six (56) digits currently in operation. With this coding system, financial statements in AFA (Made up of 14 statements and 25 schedules) and AAA are made automatically in the office from CGA (KII 4, UAFO officials, Rajshahi).

BACS has broad applications for reporting purposes. One of the CGA officials who are working in the accounts and procedures division mentioned that:

Accounts of governmental financial transactions kept by different accounts offices and Divisional Comptroller of Accounts (DCA) offices shall maintain due organizational code(s) and classifications system for reporting purposes. The AFA and the AAA are the two fundamental accounts the government uses to disseminate financial information to the public. All ministries prepare AAA using the same format describing the economic code(s) range and submit it to the CGA for an audit certificate provided by C&AG (see appendix F). The CGA office is responsible for preparing an AFA describing the 14 different

statements. Of which 1-4 statements must be prepared by mentioning the code(s) or receipt and payments (KII 5, CGA officials, Dhaka).

Conclusion

Based on the analysis above, it can be generalized that the Budgetary and Accounting Classification System (BACS) is a process by which government accountants or financial managers can get an answer to the question of 'What', 'Where' and 'How'. In that case, 'What' indicates the types of transaction, i.e. the transactions are revenue types or expenditure, assets or liabilities or net worth and voted or non-voted nature. 'Where' indicates the organizations' whereabouts transactions that occurred, i.e., general government or public corporation, donor agency and also identifies the locations of government entities. 'How' indicates the reporting process of government financial and non-financial information properly through AAA and AFA.

This article has also explored the process of following and compatibility of BACS/CoA for the accounting and reporting system of governmental financial transactions in Bangladesh. Even though there is some debate about classifying different segments of government sectors following the GFSM-2014 and the Ministry of Finance, GoB. This study has identified the mismatch in the classification of revenues,

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expenses and COFOG by the IMF and Ministry of Finance GoB. GFS-2014 classification is consistent and applicable for the public sector as governed by the International Public Sector Accounting Standard Board (IPSASB) and the classification of GoB is pertinent for the general government sector of Bangladesh. However, the study results show a difference in the sector-level classification of GoB and GFS-2014.

GFS-2014 developed fifty-six (56) digits of BACS/CoA for the macroeconomic analytical tool for the general government and public sectors. This classification system identifies governmental economic events and accounts for governmental financial transactions. But for the reporting requirement, GoB is using two accounts namely, AFA and AAA, as per the mandate of the constitution of Bangladesh article 128 and section 4 of the C&AG additional functional Act. 1974. BACS/CoA has ensured a separate system of accounting for the Consolidated Fund (CF) and Public Accounts of the Republic (PAR). It helps identify charged (Non-voted) and other (Voted) expenditures. BACS/CoA has brought revolutionary changes in budget preparation and execution. Finally, it is the most robust tool for public financial reporting and analysis.

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An Empirical Analysis of Capital Market Manipulation in Bangladesh and Its Impact on Investors' Confidence

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Abstract **Purpose**

This study focuses on the complex nature between the market manipulators and their influence on investor's confidence within Bangladesh's capital market. The study goes in depth into the widely applied manipulative techniques, such as wash trading, pump and dump, spoofing, and insider trading, and looks at the repercussions of these tricks on investor trust and perception.

Methodology

This study employed a mixed-method approach. The paper begins with the thorough investigation of the 2010–2011 Bangladesh stock market crash with contribution revealed in the informative report of Khondokar Ibrahim Khaled. After that, the data results collected from surveys and semi-structured interviews will be turned into quantitative data. This quantitative data will be analyzed using multiple regression analysis in SPSS to understand the effects of manipulation market practices on investor's confidence. The empirical study indicates a very strong correlation between revolving around the stock market of stock manipulation acts and investor's confidence, as it has considered many factors involved.

Conclusion

These findings add weight to the necessity of new, advanced

tools in regulating, promoting transparency and investors' education in the area of market manipulations and protecting investors' interests. Such a development will give the roadmap to the policy makers, market players, and stakeholder on how they can improve market and make the market more efficient.

Keywords

wash trading, pump and dump, spoofing, insider trading.

Introduction

Financial markets are critical components of modern economies, facilitating investment, efficiently distributing capital and resources, and encouraging economic progress. Investors' faith in market systems is based on ideas such as fairness, transparency, and trust, all of which are required for these markets to function well. However, the rise in complex trading tactics and technological improvements has given new opportunities for unethical behavior, such as market manipulation.

Market manipulation is defined as deliberate activities taken by individuals or groups with the intention of unfairly influencing the supply, demand, or price of assets, commodities, or financial instruments. The purpose of this manipulation is typically to establish misleading market perceptions that influence the decision-making of other market participants in ways that

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benefit the manipulators. Financial market manipulation not only distorts prices, but it also erodes investor trust, threatening the market's stability and integrity.

The purpose of this study is to conduct an empirical investigation into market manipulation in Bangladesh's capital market and its impact on investor trust. The next chapters will contain a full literature review, research methodology, data analysis, and conclusion. These will contribute to the present body of knowledge and provide important recommendations to policymakers and capital market stakeholders.

Theoretical Framework

As per Bangladesh Securities and Exchange Commission Act

1993, Market manipulation involves any act, omission, or practice that either directly or indirectly brings about this false

or misleading appearance of the price, value, or volume of security or any related security, or which otherwise is intended

Figure 1: Ways of Market Manipulation

Source: Prepared by Author based on primary research

to dupe the investors. Several means of market manipulation may be applied to a market, such as-

- a. Wash trading: Wash-trading involves buying and selling of the same financial instruments in the same hand at the same time, leading to a give-away of trading activity. This, therefore, increases the number of shares traded but often misleads and can lead to the assumption that there is a high level of interest in the market.
- b. Spoofing: Spoofing involves placing large orders intending to later on revoke them before execution. This strategy deceives other market participants that will in turn cause temporary fluctuations in price which the spoofer can profit from. Spoofer uses these movements to his own profit.
- c. Front running/ Insider Trading: Front-running is an activity that a dealer executes orders on-behalf of a client recently made aware of a big incoming order. The front runner attempts to reap the expected benefit of the price effect coming from the order of the client.
- d. Pump and dump: Pumps and dumps schemes build the price of security by unscrupulous actions like

misinformation or exaggeration of the truth, and then unload the overvalued security for profit. It is these practices that give investors the impression that a particular asset is being demanded and hence interested in.

Literature Review

Many academic studies have looked at examples of market manipulation in a variety of contexts. Baker and Wurgler (2007) investigated the effect of simulated price fluctuations and market indicator distortions on investor sentiment and stock prices in the United States. Their findings had a negative effect on stock prices. Siddique and Hossain's (2013) study on Bangladesh's capital market found that it had a negative impact on transaction volume and volatility. The findings point to potential distortions in market signals and a drop in investor confidence. Bhuiyan et al. (2016) discovered a link between market manipulation and stock returns on the Dhaka Stock Exchange, implying that investors could have suffered considerable financial losses.

Al-Tamimi (2005) conducted a study in the UAE to determine major elements influencing individual investors' behavior. The author concentrated on marketability and government ownership, ignoring risk minimization and family perspectives. The Dhaka Stock Exchange in Bangladesh is experiencing persistent manipulation, prompting

regulators to compare it to a gambling casino (Islam Azizul, 2014). This has resulted in increased investor sensitivity and market volatility. Shahjarul Alam (2012) expressed ongoing concerns regarding initial stock sales and potential stock market manipulation. Current methods of assessing stock values do not meet investor expectations.

Kadariya's (2012) study in Nepal emphasized the relevance of both real and intangible factors, such as media and political coverage, fate, and political attitude in influencing investment decisions. In their 2009 study, Comerton-Forde and Putnins investigated the impact of closing price manipulation on equities, demonstrating how it resulted in better returns, wider spreads, and increased trading activity, all of which influenced market quality. Despite the existence of theoretical frameworks, there is a dearth of empirical research on stock market manipulation. Jiang et al. (2005) and Aggarwal and Wu (2004) investigated manipulation, focusing on its financial benefits and impact on market integrity, respectively.

Although market manipulation is frequent in Bangladesh's capital market, there has been little scholarly research on how it affects investor trust. To address an existing knowledge vacuum, this study will look into the relationship between market manipulation and investor trust in the Bangladeshi capital market.

Hypothesis Development

Table 1: Hypothesis Statement

- H₀:** Market manipulation practices do not have any statistically significant effect on investors' confidence.
- H₁:** Wash Trading has a statistically significant effect on investors' confidence.
- H₂:** Spoofing has a statistically significant effect on investors' confidence.
- H₃:** Insider Trading has a statistically significant effect on investors' confidence.
- H₄:** Pump and Dump has statistically significant effect on investors's confidence

Source: Author's Interpretation

Research Methodology

Figure 2: Research Methodology

Source: Author's Interpretation

Data Collection and Sampling Process

The researcher administered a self-conducted survey to 222 investors encompassing various demographic categories such as age, gender, occupation, experience, and income level. The survey encompasses a set of 13 inquiries. The initial six questions center around the demographic information of the investors. The subsequent questions serve to determine the investors' levels of confidence in the Bangladesh capital market, their perceptions and encounters with market manipulation, the influence of

manipulation on their investment confidence, and finally, the last two questions gauge the investors' trust in the regulatory entities responsible for overseeing Bangladesh's capital market. The secondary data sources are obtained from books, journals, articles, past research, newspaper, etc.

The sampling strategy for this study is purposive sampling or judgmental sampling. The study has targeted investors in the Bangladesh capital market who have experience or knowledge of market manipulation practices and their impact on investor confidence.

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Out of our total group of 222 participants, 65% or 144 were identified as male, while 35% or 78 were female respondents. We received responses from individuals belonging to various occupational backgrounds. These occupations were segmented into 10 distinct sectors, encompassing roles such as students, teachers, professionals in various services, bankers, self-employed individuals, doctors, engineers, and retirees, among others.

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The remaining demographic information is visually presented in accompanying figures and tables.

Table 2: Income level of Respondents

Income Level	Below 50,000	50,000-100,000	100,001-150,000	150,001-200,000	Above 200,000	Total
Frequency	6.7%	16.6%	17%	22.4%	37.3%	100%

Figure 3: Age categories of respondents

Source: Author's primary research survey on Investors

Table 3: Size of investment of Respondents

Size of Investment	Below 500,000	500,000 - 10,00,000	10,00,001 - 15,00,000	15,00,001 - 20,00,000	Above 20,00,000	Total
Frequency	9%	18.4%	17%	17%	38.6%	100%

Figure 4: Experience level of the respondents

Source: Author's primary research survey on Investors

Empirical Model

The empirical model can be expressed as:

$$\text{Investor Confidence} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 (\text{Market Manipulation}) + \beta_2 (\text{Control Variables}) + \epsilon$$

Let's denote Investors' Confidence as IC.

$$\text{IC} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{WT} + \beta_2 \text{SP} + \beta_3 \text{FR} + \beta_4 \text{PD} + \beta_5 \text{Age} + \beta_6 \text{Gender} + \beta_7 \text{Experience} + \beta_8 \text{Income} + \beta_9 \text{Occupation} + \beta_{10} \text{Size_of_Investment} + \epsilon$$

Here,

- β_0 is the intercept (the expected mean value of IC when all X=0)
- β_1 to β_{10} are the coefficients of the independent variables, which represent the change in the dependent variable corresponding to a one unit change in the respective independent variables, assuming all other variables are held constant.
- WT, SP, FR, PD represent the perceived frequency of occurrence of Wash Trading, Spoofing, Front Running, and Pump and Dump, respectively. These represent market manipulation practices.
- Age, Gender, Experience, Income, Occupation, Size_of_Investment represent the control variables (investor demographics).

- ϵ is the error term that contains the variability of IC not explained by the independent variables.

Data Analysis and Discussion of Findings

Reasons behind the Crash and its alleged connection to Market Manipulation

The report has successfully identified a cluster of manipulators, including key officials, auditors, issuers, issue-managers, brokers, individual investors, and various other stakeholders.

The Investigation report (2011) conducted by the probe committee highlighted the factors behind the stock market crash.

1. Involvement of stock market regulators and their employees:

The report identified specific individuals within the regulatory body who were implicated in market manipulation practices. There was a noted overlap in responsibilities between the BSEC and entities like the Dhaka Stock Exchange (DSE). Both organizations had surveillance departments tasked with similar roles, but found to have a lack of coordination existed. The report also pointed out inefficiencies in the BSEC's review of listing applications, as it was observed that the DSE and Chittagong Stock Exchange (CSE) conducted this

process more effectively. Additionally, the report raised concerns about the placement of Mutual Funds and Initial Public Offerings (IPOs) at prices below market value, which seemed to function as a method of bribery for influential regulator employees. There were accusations of senior-level employees obtaining placements by using other people's names, making detection challenging. Furthermore, the report acknowledged the insufficient number of skilled employees within the BSEC, including qualified accountants, financial analysts, and researchers, who were required to adequately supervise and monitor the market.

2. Omnibus Account:

According to the investigation report, another significant factor contributing to the stock market crisis was the utilization of Omnibus accounts by ICB and merchant banks. Each branch of a merchant bank operates a single omnibus account, which may encompass a substantial number of BO Accounts, ranging from 3 to 10 thousand. These BO Accounts remain beyond the purview of BSEC's surveillance. Consequently, the details of individual accounts and their transactions are exclusively held by merchant banks. The investigation reveals

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that such accounts were involved in numerous illicit transactions. The report discloses the names of 30 prominent entities, including ICB, linked to numerous suspicious transactions. The investigation suggests that a majority of manipulative activities occurred through these omnibus accounts. Additionally, it is highlighted that an estimated amount of at least Taka 2.5 billion was transacted through concealed or omnibus accounts.

3. Sequential and artificial trading: Certain manipulators orchestrated a simulated atmosphere of

dynamic trading by conducting substantial transactions amongst themselves, consequently inflating share prices. Furthermore, they engaged in sequential trading and manipulated prices by executing numerous buy-sell orders across various accounts and brokerages, ultimately causing an excessive surge in market activity.

4. Questionable dealings involving prominent participants: The investigation findings expose specific individuals and institutional investors who were significant buyers

and sellers during unusual fluctuations in the index across various time intervals. The transactions executed by these investors raised suspicions due to their impact on the market, contributing substantially to both abnormal upward and downward shifts.

5. Bulk placement: Numerous dubious instances of bulk trading in mutual funds were observed. Certain investors were granted substantial placements at various intervals.

Identification of Manipulation through Case Studies

Salvo Chemical Industry Limited

Objectives: The organization possesses significant obligations pertaining to capital expenditures. Consequently, the funds generated from the initial public offering (IPO) will be allocated to support the project's expansion and to settle outstanding loans.

Upon evaluating the financial statements of Salvo Chemical Industry Limited, certain irregularities have been detected.

1. Fixed Assets and Depreciation Expenses:

Particulars	2009 (Taka)	2008 (Taka)	Growth (TK & Percent)		Note no
Fixed assets at WDV	118,644,629	94,142,611	24,502,018	26%	7
Depreciation expenses	7,919,516	8,474,029	-554,513	-7%	7
Fixed assets addition	32,421,534	18,508,593	13,912,941	75%	7

In 2009, the company reported a written down value (WDV) of fixed assets amounting to Tk.118,644,629, reflecting a notable 26% rise compared to the previous fiscal year. Furthermore, the addition of fixed assets during the same period totaled Tk. 32,421,534, marking a substantial 75% increase from the previous fiscal year. These figures illustrate a considerable escalation in both instances. Notably, the percentage of depreciation has shown a decline of 7% in the current financial year. The company's accounting policy stipulates that depreciation must be applied to all assets acquired during the year, commencing from the month of acquisition.

This scenario raises suspicions regarding potential manipulation aimed at boosting the company's profitability by downplaying the charge for depreciation in the present year.

During the year 2009, there was a decline in sales amounting to Tk. 46,728,459, representing a substantial 42% decrease compared to the previous fiscal year. Interestingly, in contrast, container sales, which involve containers used for storing chemicals for sale, witnessed a remarkable increase of Tk. 16,024,600. This figure demonstrates an extraordinary surge of 907% in comparison to the preceding year.

The noteworthy aspect lies in the juxtaposition of these trends. While sales experienced a significant 42% reduction, the container sales surged dramatically by 907% within the same year, prompting questions about the remarkable contrast between the two rates.

In the year 2009, it has come to our attention that sales experienced a decline of Tk. 46,728,459, reflecting a decrease of 42% compared to the previous year's sales.

However, it is noteworthy that accounts receivable have surged by Tk. 41,157,523, representing a substantial increase of 654% in comparison to the prior year's accounts receivable. An additional observation is that the cash flow statement indicates a total cash receipt of Tk. 63,398,016, which exactly matches the company's sales figure. This suggests that all sales transactions were conducted in cash. If this holds true, the question arises as to how there has been such a significant increase in accounts receivable.

Furthermore, all non-operating income was also received in cash. This inconsistency raises concerns regarding the substantial increase in accounts receivable despite a decrease in the sales rate. The apparent manipulation of receivables in the financial statement points to the inaccuracy of the balance sheet.

2. Sales:

Particulars	2009 (Taka)	2008 (Taka)	Growth (TK & Percent)		Note no
Container sales	17,790,400	16,024,600	1,765,800	11%	12
Sales-net VAT	63,398,016	110,126,475	-46,728,459	-42%	24

3. Accounts Receivables:

Particulars	2009 (Taka)	2009 (Taka)	Growth (TK & Percent)	
Sales-net of VAT	63,398,016	110,126,475	-46,728,459	-42%
Accounts receivable	47,452,190	6,294,667	41,157,523	654%
% of accounts receivable of sales	75%	6%		
Cash received from customer (operating income)	63,398,016	126,645,465	63247449	-50%
Cash received from customer (non-operating income)	8,207,556	1,223,636	698392000%	571%

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Descriptive Results

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age	222	1.0	6.0	3.405	1.3811
Gender	222	1.0	2.0	1.351	.4785
Occupation	222	1.0	10.0	5.005	2.7922
Income Level	222	1.0	5.0	3.554	1.2272
Size of Investment	222	1.0	5.0	3.423	1.3624
Experience	222	1.0	4.0	2.532	1.0186
Wash Trading	222	2.0	4.0	3.338	.5019
Spoofing	222	1.0	4.0	2.207	.6034
Insider Trading	222	1.0	4.0	2.991	.6793
Pump and Dump	222	2.0	5.0	3.788	.5256
IC	222	2.0	5.0	3.486	.9161

Source: Author's Calculation

The qualitative data were translated into numerical values for analysis. Upon analyzing the results, we discern that wash trading, insider trading and pump and dump were encountered with notable frequency among the respondents during their investments. On the other hand, spoofing reported to be faced less frequently. Additionally, the average respondents had an investment experience spanning 4 to 7 years.

Investor confidence in the capital market was reported to be influenced on an average significantly due to the practices of market manipulation. Responses varied from moderate to high levels of investor confidence, indicating diversity in perceptions.

ANOVA Table

Table 5: ANOVA Model^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	126.924	10	12.692	45.751	.000 ^b
Residual	58.536	211	.277		
Total	185.459	221			

a. Dependent Variable: IC

b. Predictors: (Constant), experience, SP, Gender, Occupation, WT, IT, PD, Income level, Age, Size of Investment

Source: Author's Calculation

The F-Value of 45.751 is the ratio of explained variability to unexplained variability. The extremely low p-value ($p < .001$) signifies that the model's predictors collectively have a significant impact on IC. The total sum of squares encompasses the overall variability in the dependent variable.

Regression Analysis

Table 6: Regression Analysis

Independent & Control Variables	Coefficients	T value	P value
(Constant)	3.329	8.526	.000***
WT	.467	5.289	.000***
SP	-.222	-2.931	.004***
IT	.250	3.853	.000***
PD	-.332	-4.406	.000***
Age	-.092	-1.903	.058**
Gender	.706	9.022	.000***
Occupation	-.084	-4.399	.000***
Income	.074	1.616	.108*
Size of Investment	-.026	-.474	.636
experience	-.316	-4.428	.000***
R Square	.684		
Adjusted R square	.669		

Source: Author's Calculation

The R square tells us, the independent and control variables in the model collectively explain about 68.4% of the variance observed in the dependent variable. The adjusted R square is 66.9%. This indicates moderately strong fit of the model to the data.

A variable marked with one star signifies significance at a 10% level, a variable with two stars indicates significance at a 5% level, and variables designated with three stars are highly significant, aligning with a 1% significance level.

By using the constant and coefficients, we can formulate our model in the subsequent manner:

$IC = 3.329 + .467 WT - .222 SP + .250 IT - .332 PD + .092Age + .706 Gender - .316 Experience + .074 Income - .084 Occupation - 0.26 Size_of_Investment + e$

Multicollinearity Test

Table 7: Multicollinearity test

Variables	VIF
WT	1.566
SP	1.662
IT	1.546
PD	1.251
Average	1.506

Source: Author's Calculation

The multicollinearity test holds significant importance in quantitative research. Its purpose is to determine if there are any significant correlations among variables. Our average VIF is also within 3 which means that these variables are independent of each other in the model and the dataset doesn't consist of any serious multicollinearity.

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Findings Analysis

The research findings contribute significant insights into the intricate dynamics between market manipulation practices, investor demographics, and their collective impact on investors' confidence within the capital market. The study delved into each aspect comprehensively and unearthed valuable evidence that sheds light on the underlying mechanisms influencing investor confidence.

A thorough examination of the relationship between investor demographics and market manipulation strategies

uncovered a sophisticated understanding. The findings revealed that the combination of these two characteristics had a statistically significant impact on investor confidence. This points to a complex interaction in which manipulation methods interact with demographic characteristics to determine overall confidence levels. The study investigated how manipulation tactics can exacerbate or ameliorate the impact of demographic variables on investor confidence. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected, and all the alternative hypotheses will be accepted-

Table 8: Hypotheses results

Hypotheses	Regression weights	B	t	P value	Results
H ₁	WT → IC	.467	5.289	0.000	Accepted
H ₂	SP → IC	-.222	-2.931	0.004	Accepted
H ₃	IT → IC	.250	3.853	0.000	Accepted
H ₄	PD → IC	-.332	-4.406	0.000	Accepted

Source: Author's Interpretation

Note: p<0.05. WT= Wash Trading; SP= Spoofing; IT= Insider Trading; PD= Pump and Dump; IC= Investor Confidence

Conclusion

A detailed investigation of many factors revealed a strong relationship between market manipulation techniques and investor confidence. We discovered strong evidence on the impact of these strategies on investor perception and confidence by thoroughly evaluating them in the context of Bangladesh's capital market.

This paper goes beyond theoretical research by doing a detailed case study examination of the big stock market fall in Bangladesh from 2010 to 2011. We used Khondokar Ibrahim Khaled's well-structured work to conduct an empirical investigation and confirm the prevalence of market manipulation in the local financial industry.

Overall, this thesis emphasizes the importance of diligent oversight, regulatory initiatives, and investor education in mitigating the negative impacts of market manipulation strategies. The study's findings provide a strategic roadmap for policymakers, market participants, and stakeholders to create a strong and trustworthy investment environment that protects investors' interests while also improving the market's credibility and stability as the Bangladesh capital market grows.

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Determinants of Price-Earnings Ratio: Evidence from DSE Listed Companies

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Abstract **Purpose**

This study is aimed at analyzing and examining the underlying factors affecting price to earnings ratio. It seeks to test the relationship among Age, business size, ROA, institutional ownership, sponsors ownership, foreign ownership, leverage, and their impact on price to earnings ratio.

Methodology

This study employs a quantitative research methodology. This research consists of 111 companies listed under DSE subject to data availability from 2018 to 2022. In order to ascertain the association, correlation matrix, multiple linear regression (OLS), and descriptive statistics have all been carried out. The association has been examined using a multiple linear regression model.

Findings

Empirical evidence reveals that a statistically significant negative relationship exists between leverage and the P/E ratio, and a statistically significant positive relationship exists between sponsor ownership and the P/E ratio.

Practical Implications

P/E ratio combines way more crucial factors of a firm as well as the economy. This study will aid listed companies, fundamental analysts and

decision-makers in examining the factors that contribute to fluctuations in the price-to-earnings ratio. It will also facilitate investor's education.

Value

In Bangladesh, the research done over the P/E ratio explored particular aspects of the capital market or industry, for example, the manufacturing industry. Also, the dimension of ownership structure was not empirically examined before. This study will fill this gap examining holistic and extensive aspects of determinants of the P/E ratio of companies listed under DSE.

Research Limitation

This study has flaws. Only 111 DSE-listed companies subject to data availability are included in this analysis. Therefore, this study fails to represent the large number of DSE-listed companies. This analysis also ignores firm-specific criteria including dividend yield, earnings growth, payout ratio, and ROE. This study ignores macroeconomic considerations like GDP growth and inflation.

Key Words

P/E ratio, DSE, Business size, Leverage, Ownership etc.

Introduction

Price-to-earnings ratio covers two critical factors: (1) the Current market price of the stock and (2) EPS of a particular

period. That is why it is called the relative measure. Because of its simplicity in computation, it is extensively used by investors and practitioners. Price-Earnings Ratio is used as a crucial metric for riskiness and future growth of the market and company to tap the current mood and sentiments of the market. It is a relative measure to show to what extent a company's financial performance is related to its market share value. The P/E ratio is obtained by taking the relative value of the market value of the share at a particular date and earnings per share of a given period. The less the P/E multiple, the more growth opportunities.

The P/E ratio is derived by=
$$\frac{\text{Market price per share}}{\text{Earning per share.}}$$

P/E ratio tells investors about the company's financial performance, investment potential, new product line, and major management changes. The share price and P/E reflect

these significant occurrences. While making recommendations about stock investment decisions, it is assumed that low P/E ratios are not good investments. But it is inconclusive. Empirical evidence found that P/E ratio stocks having low value have better financial performance than stocks with higher ratios (Nicholson,1960). Evidence was also found that P/E ratios having low-value stocks delivered better financial profit than that of P/E ratios stocks with high value (Basu,1977).

The literature related to P/E ratio is rich. A lot of empirical models are used to measure the impact by using a lot of proxies of firm specific variables such as leverage, age, ROA, firm size, payout ratio, stock price, dividend yield, ROE etc. (Dutta et al, 2018; Kumar and Warne, 2009; Kulling and Lundberg, 2007; Kasilingam and Ramasundaram, 2011; Bhargava et al, 2011; Huang et al. ,2007; Emudainohwo,2017). The results were mixed and inconclusive.

Also, the dimension of ownership structure was not empirically examined. In Bangladesh, literature related to P/E ratio is also limited and narrowly designed. This research intends to fill this void and validate the results of previous study with a more extensive approach.

This study tests the relationship of P/E ratio with respect to leverage, Age, size, ROA, and ownership structure over five-year periods. Empirical evidence exhibits a statistically significant negative association with leverage ratio and a statistically significant positive association with sponsor ownership.

Literature Review

P/E ratio has been a handy valuation and predictive tool for researchers, fundamental analysts and investors. Literature related to P/E ratio is extensive and rich. Thus, most of the empirical results of those researches are inconclusive and mixed. Nicholson (1960) examined the financial performance of common stocks with Price-Earnings multiples over 25 and below 12. Compared to the twenty highest multiple stocks, the twenty lowest multiple stocks had appreciated substantially. Evidence revealed that Low P/E equities had greater financial returns than high P/E shares. We concluded that low P/E multiple stocks perform better for investors. Beave and Morse (1978) evaluated the P/E metric and

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earnings growth's effect. They ranked 25 portfolios by P/E ratio. In the portfolio creation period, profits growth negatively affected the P/E ratio, but in the next year, it positively affected it. It was also revealed low profits growth stocks have low P/E metrics. Siegel (1995) studied high-P/E American stock exchange corporations for 21 years. In different market conditions, stocks performed differently. High P/E stocks underperformed during bad times. High P/E stocks outperformed over a long time. Fortune's 100 fastest-growing companies were examined by Beneda (2002). Evidence shows that value stocks return more than growth ones. Bhargava and Malhotra (2006) examined P/E and future share values using European and African S&P indices. Results revealed that P/E had no substantial effect on stock price. Huang et al. (2007) examined P-E measures'

relationships. Expected, residual, and reversed stock returns are examples. Firm specific and macroeconomic characteristics including long-term growth rate, payout ratio, and firm size positively correlated with P/E ratio. Portfolios with low P/E ratios had better reversals than those with high levels. Wan-Ting Wu (2014) examined estimated P/E metrics and earnings growth. They conceptualized using the OJ and anomalous earning growth model. Research discovered a negative correlation between anticipated P/E and earnings growth. It was shown that the forward metric predicts future earnings better than the trailing P/E ratio. Bhargava et al. (2011) used VAR and VECM analysis of BRIC countries to study P/E, DY, and share prices. They examined if BRIC index prices are affected by P/E or dividend yield. Dividend yield hurt Brazil, Russia, and China but helped

India. Kulling and Lundberg (2007) examined Swedish stock market P/E variables. Dividend yield, market value, and leverage were negatively correlated with P/E and market to book, and positively correlated with interest rate. Kumar and Warne (2009) examined how debt-to-equity leverage affects P/E ratios in Indian industries. Over numerous years, leverage positively affected P/E. Shamsuddin and Hiller (2004) examined the Australian stock market's P/E multiple using the ASX 200 index. Payout ratio positively affected and interest rate negatively affected P/E. Additionally, GDP growth, consumer confidence, and an increased Australian dollar exchange rate are positively correlated with price to earnings ratio. Sajeetha et al. (2023) examined the P/E metric of Colombo stock exchange food, beverage, and tobacco companies from 2015 to 2019. ROE and EPS had a minor negative influence on P/E, whereas dividend yield and leverage had a considerable positive effect. Kasilingam and Ramasundaram (2011) examined P/E ratio characteristics in Indian stocks. P/E was primarily affected by predicted return and growth. Except for market capitalization, dividend payout and ROE effect P/E ratio insignificantly. Afza and Tahir (2012) examined the KSE-listed Pakistani chemical industry's P/E measure. The P/E ratio was positively affected by dividend payment and Tobin's Q ratio. In pooled data analysis, payout ratio, price volatility, and growth

were positively correlated, but size was negatively correlated. Emudainohwo (2017) explored non-financial firms that amounted to forty-seven, which are listed in the Nigerian stock exchange over a five-year period. He employed quantile regression and pooled regression models. Evidence was found that payout ratio, share price, and dividend per share were found to have a statistically significant effect over the P/E metric from the view of the 25th, 50th, and 75th percentiles. Dutta et al. (2018) examined DSE manufacturing company P/E metric variables. The P/E metric was affected by net asset value per share, dividend yield, leverage, and size. P/E metric was found to have a significant negative association with Dividend yield and size, and significant positive impact with leverage and NAVPS.

Despite being one of the most crucial factors for stock valuation and predicting future performance, the research

related to P/E ratio in Bangladeshi capital market is understudied and not extensively researched. Fewer studies had been done with a myopic view where ownership structure was not considered. This study intends to fill this gap with an extensive approach and new factors.

Research Question

This research attempts to find answer of the below question:

- To what extent the variables: Age, company size, Leverage, ROA, Institutional ownership, sponsor's ownership, foreign ownership are related with P/E ratio?
- To what extent the association of variables: Age, company size, Leverage, ROA, Institutional ownership, sponsor's ownership, foreign ownership affects P/E ratio positively and negatively?

Conceptual Framework and Hypothesis Development

a. Conceptual Model

This study explores the relationship among P/E ratios with respect to leverage, Age, size, ROA, and ownership structure over five-year periods. The conceptual model is shown below:

Figure 1 : Determinants of P/E ratio

Source: Prepared by Author

**Determinants of Price-Earnings Ratio:
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b. Descriptive Summary of Variables

Here, the P/E ratio is regarded as dependent variable. Also, seven independent variables have been selected for this study, including age, leverage, ROA, firm size, institutional ownership, sponsors ownership, and foreign ownership. Here is the descriptive overview:

Dependent Variable:

Price-Earnings Ratio: Price-earnings ratio can be defined as a relative measure of current stock price and EPS.

This is calculated as follows:

$$P/E \text{ ratio} = (\text{Market share price}) / (\text{earning per share})$$

*Price has been taken as the closing price of the Dividend Declaration Date.

Independent Variables:

Age: Age has been obtained by taking the difference of a listing

year in the Dhaka stock exchange and the respective year taken as a sample.

Age = Listing year in DSE - Sample year

*The natural log (LN) has been used for the Age variable to facilitate better empirical results.

Leverage: Leverage can be defined as the proportion of debt and equity in the capital structure. It measures the long-term solvency of a business.

$$\text{Leverage is calculated by} = (\text{Total debt}) / (\text{Total shareholders' equity})$$

*Both the ending balance of debt and equity has been used.

Return on Assets (ROA): The ROA is used as a determinant to reflect profitability in this study. It is calculated as a relative value of year-end net profit and the value of total assets. It measures

how a company's asset has been utilized to create profit.

$$\text{ROA is calculated by} = (\text{Net Profit}) / (\text{Total Assets})$$

Firm Size: Firm size can be measured in many ways, including market capitalization, total sales, total assets, and total employees. Firm size is a crucial factor because firm size has varying effects on a company's performance. This study uses the natural log (LN) of total assets to get a more robust result.

Firm size is calculated by = $\ln(\text{Total Assets})$

Institutional Ownership: Institutional ownership is measured as how much of a company's issued share is owned by mutual/pension funds, insurance companies, private companies, endowments, and large organizations that invest on behalf of others.

Institutional ownership is calculated by = Year the end % of stocks held by institutions

Sponsors Ownership: Sponsors can be defined as several persons and organizations who direct the company to attain its mission, goals, vision, and objectives.

Sponsors' ownership is calculated by = Year the end % of stocks held by sponsors having an interest in the entity.

Foreign Ownership: Foreign Ownership refers to the people

or entities who have ownership in another country's assets, actual states or have a stake in the business, and generally, they are not the legal citizens of the country and for companies whose headquarters are situated in another territory.

Foreign ownership is calculated by= Year end % of stocks held by individuals/entities of foreign countries.

c. Hypothesis Development

H1: Age has a statistically significant effect on investors' P/E ratio.

H2: Leverage has a statistically significant effect on P/E ratio.

H3: ROA Trading has a statistically significant effect on P/E ratio.

H4: Firm Size has a statistically significant effect on P/E ratio.

H5: Institutional Ownership has a statistically significant effect on investors' P/E ratio.

H6: Sponsors Ownership has a statistically significant effect on P/E ratio.

H7: Foreign Ownership has a statistically significant effect on P/E ratio.

**Determinants of Price-Earnings Ratio:
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Research Methodology

a. Sampling design and data collection:

This study is aimed at exploring key factors influencing the P/E ratio for the listed companies under DSE. This study excludes all the listed banks and non-bank financial institutions (NBFI). Primarily, approximately 300 companies were selected. Due to unavailability of relevant data, 111 companies were finalized for empirical analysis. An overview of sample with respect to industry representation is given below:

Table 1: Industry Wise Sample

Industry	Numbers of Company	Percentage (%)
Cement	6	5.41%
Ceramic	3	2.70%
Engineering	17	15.32%
Food	12	10.81%
Fuel and Power	15	13.51%
Information Technology	6	5.41%
Pharmaceuticals	18	16.22%
Services and Real state	4	3.60%
Textile	21	18.92%
Travel and Leisure	2	1.80%
Telecommunication	2	1.80%
Miscellaneous	5	4.50%
Total	111	100%

Source: Author's Interpretation

b. Research Design

The process of research design has been shown below:

Figure 2: Research Design

Source: Prepared by Author

c. Empirical Model

The empirical model used in the study has been established below:

$$P/E \text{ RATIO}_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1(\ln \text{Age})_{it} + \beta_2(\text{Lev})_{it} + \beta_3(\text{FS})_{it} + \beta_4(\text{ROA})_{it} + \beta_5(\text{IO})_{it} + \beta_6(\text{SO})_{it} + \beta_7(\text{FO})_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

Where,

LEV= Leverage

FS= Firm size

ROA= Return on assets

α =Constant

i= Company

t= Year

IO= Institutional ownership

SO= Sponsors ownership

FO= Foreign ownership

ϵ_{it} = Residual errors

Empirical Analysis

a. Descriptive Statistics

Table provides the mean, maximum, minimum, and std deviation, 1st quartile (Q1), 3rd quartile (Q3), of 111 listed companies under DSE from 2018 to 2022 for each variable. For this study, descriptive statistics are generated by taking into consideration 555 observations summarized below table:

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Observation	Mean	Std Dev	Median	Minimum	Maximum	Percentile 25% (Q1)	Percentile 75%(Q3)
P/E ratio	555	42.098	44.43	24.47	6.90	152.63	13.80	47.61
LN Age	555	2.84	0.68	2.89	0	3.85	2.30	3.49
LEV	555	2.79	20.49	1.055	-0.50	463.36	0.48	2.081
FS	555	22.41	1.70	22.43	17.80	26.79	21.31	23.52
ROA	555	0.048	0.080	0.030	-0.79	0.53	0.010	0.069
IO	555	18.31	10.64	16.86	0	55.34	10.1	25.47
SO	555	43.23	21.93	42.49	0	95	30.03	59
FO	555	1.65	5.55	0	0	44.15	0	0.4

According to the descriptive statistics table above, the P/E ratio ranges from 6.90 to 152.63, with a median of 24.47, mean of 42.098, std dev 44.43, 1st quartile Q1 13.80, and 3rd quartile Q3 47.61. P/E volatility is high. Ln Age ranges from 0 to 3.85, median 2.89, mean 2.84, std deviation 0.68. Its 1st quartile Q1 is 2.30 and its 3rd quartile Q3 is 3.49, making it less volatile. Firm size and ROA also show less variability over the periods. The leverage ranges from -0.50 to 463.36, with a median of 1.055, mean of 2.79, std deviation of 20.49, 1st quartile Q1 at 0.48, and 3rd quartile Q3 at 2.081, indicating more volatility. Institutional ownership spans from 0 to 55.34, with a median of 16.86, mean of 18.31, std deviation of 10.64, 1st quartile Q1 of 10.1, and 3rd quartile Q3 of 25.47, suggesting volatility. Sponsors ownership and foreign ownership have also indicated high variability over the periods.

b. Correlation Matrix

The table of the correlation matrix is given below:

Table 3: Correlation Matrix

Variable	P/E ratio	Ln Age	LEV	FS	ROA	IO	SO	FO
P/E ratio	1.0000							
LN Age	0.2620*	1.0000						
LEV	-0.0114	0.0813	1.0000					
FS	-0.491*	-.212*	-0.0597	1.0000				
ROA	-0.131*	-0.014	-0.1045*	0.153*	1.0000			
IO	-0.296*	-.167*	-0.0690	0.299*	-.182*	1.0000		
SO	-0.0450	-.097*	-0.0192	0.149*	0.339*	-0.3147*	1.0000	
FO	-0.114*	0.177*	-0.0208	0.261*	0.270*	0.0012	-0.0205	1.0000

*Correlation coefficient is significant at 0.05 level. (Two tailed)

Table 3 demonstrates the relationship between the dependent variable, P/E ratio, and the explanatory factors. The matrix indicates a strong positive correlation between the P/E ratio and the natural logarithm of age. This is the sole positive correlation among the other explanatory factors. The association between the P/E ratio and leverage is negative and insignificant. There is a considerable negative association between the P/E ratio and firm size. Currently, it is the most prominent association compared to the other explanatory variables. There is a significant negative association between the P/E ratio and return on assets, institutional ownership, foreign ownership but negative and statistically negligible association between the P/E metric and sponsors' ownership. None of these variables exhibit multicollinearity.

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c. Regression Analysis

Table 4: R Square & Adjusted R Square

R Square	Adjusted R Square
59.77%	48.41%

a. Predictors (Constant), LN Age, LEV, FS, ROA, IO, SO, FO

The model's explanatory components explain 59.77% of the P/E metric's variance. The residual error terms () account for the remaining 40.23% of variation. Thus, factors not accounted for in the empirical model cause 40.23% residual variation. The model accounts for 48.41% of variation, considering sample size and independent variables, according to the adjusted R square.

Table 5: F Test

F	Significance
110.65	0.0000*

a. Predictors (Constant), LN Age, LEV, FS, ROA, IO, SO, FO

b. Dependent Variable: PE

The F-statistic is statistically significant at a 5% significance level. Therefore, it can be inferred that the empirical model holds significance. So, the explanatory variables have a relationship with the P/E ratio.

The multiple linear regression model is utilized to evaluate how explanatory variables impact the P/E ratio of 111 listed businesses over a span of five years. The table displays the regression outcome. Standard deviation is corrected using two-way clustering. Clustering is based on the dimensions of firm and year. The dependent variable-P/E ratio is winsorized top-bottom 10% to reduce outliers effect.

Table 6: Regression Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std Err	t stat	P value
Constant	-113.704	297.3384	-0.38	0.703
Ln Age	-9.092	14.13724	-0.64	0.521
LEV	-0.262	.0208601	-12.57	0.000*
FS	5.752	13.33509	0.43	0.667
ROA	-2.239	76.48843	-0.03	0.977
IO	-0.252	.4166832	-0.60	0.547
SO	1.282	.5930136	2.16	0.033*
FO	1.651	1.021213	1.62	0.109

*Coefficients are significant at 0.05 level. (Two tailed)

Table 6 demonstrates that leverage and sponsor ownership are the two statistically significant drivers that impact the P/E ratio. The leverage coefficient is -0.262, meaning that a one-unit increase in leverage will result in a 0.262 unit decrease in the P/E ratio. The coefficient for sponsors' ownership is 1.282, suggesting that a one-percentage increase in sponsors' ownership will have a notably favorable effect on the P/E ratio. The P/E ratio will rise by 1.282 percent. There is a statistically insignificant negative correlation between the natural logarithm of age, ROA, and institutional ownership. There is a little positive correlation between business size and foreign ownership, but it is not statistically significant. Using excessive debt in a company's capital structure is considered inefficient and risky by the market, which negatively impacts the company's P/E ratio and market value. Moreover, increased ownership by prominent sponsors instills confidence in investors. They believe sponsors will act sensibly in managing firms to generate wealth and avoid making decisions that could harm their wealth and the investors' money. This is why it positively affects the P/E ratio.

Conclusion

This research analyzed the P/E ratio of 111 DSE-listed businesses and how seven fundamental firm-specific factors affect it and explain volatility from 2018 to 2022. From annual data, 555 observations were studied, including In age, leverage, ROA, business size, institutional ownership, sponsored ownership, and foreign ownership. This paper is important since Bangladesh's capital market lacks related literature. The study examines Bangladeshi capital market P/E ratio determinants. This study helps investors make investment decisions by creating a useful forecasting framework. First, this analysis identifies key P/E ratio parameters. Second, this article advises company executives on how to present themselves in the capital market to have a good P/E ratio. P/E

ratio is used by investors and companies for several purposes. Technical analysts don't care, but fundamental analysts need the valuation P/E ratio to decide. This study's significance, relevance, and potential application are clear. Empirical research shows that leverage and sponsor ownership significantly affect P/E ratios. A significant negative correlation exists between leverage and P/E. Sponsor shares positively affect P/E ratio. Foreign ownership, ROA, business size, and age have no statistically significant relationship. The market views heavy debt as inefficient and risky, lowering P/E and market value. More notable sponsors' shares affect investor confidence. This report suggests DSE-listed companies carefully examine adding debt to their capital structures and reducing sponsors' participation.

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Auditing Guidelines for Unclaimed, Unsettled Dividends of Listed Securities

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Interdiction

The Securities Regulator has appointed external auditors to bring issuers into compliance with the Bangladesh Securities and Exchange Commission (Capital Market Stabilization Fund) Rules, 2021 and to verify the status of unclaimed dividend payments to the Fund and this will continue for all listed securities. The Fund formed by the BSEC, for the purpose of investors' protection and increasing the supply of liquidity in the capital market is not getting the expected results, except the claimed settlements, due to which the Commission has decided to appoint auditors. The external auditors will look into why listed companies are not depositing undistributed dividends to the Fund and verify whether the claims of some companies that they have already disbursed the dividends to their shareholders are correct.

In 2021, the Bangladesh Securities and Exchange Commission (BSEC) formed the Capital Market Stabilization Fund (CMSF) in the exercise of the powers conferred under Section 33(1) of the Securities and Exchange Ordinance, 1969, with a view to collecting undistributed, unclaimed, or unsettled dividends – both cash or stock, un-allotted rights shares, or non-refunded public subscription money in favor of the shareholders, stockholders, or investors CMSF is a perpetual fund for functioning as a custodian as well as protecting

investors' right and for liquidity support through investing the fund in the capital market. The companies are not distributing the dividends to the investors because they cannot find shareholders. If this money is brought to the capital market through this Fund, the supply of liquidity will increase. Following the BSEC's initiative for the creation of Fund, the companies moved to provide the undistributed and unclaimed dividends to the shareholders.

The Commission's Order

All the issuer companies of listed securities were given instructions to transfer the cash and stock/bonus dividend, any fund and shares remaining undistributed or unsettled or un-allotted or unclaimed (except cash dividend held as unclaimed against Negotiable Instruments, if any) or non-refunded public subscription money against IPO with the issuer of listed securities for a period of 3 (three) years or more to CMSF as per the Rules.

The Commission's Order for Audit

1. The Commission deems it fit that in the interest of investors and the capital market, certain directives issued to the stock exchange(s), the depository participants, the issuer of listed securities including securities trading at over-the-counter (OTC), Alternative Trading Board

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(ATB), SME Platform or any scheme of a mutual fund (herein after referred to as “the issuer”) and Capital Market Stabilization Fund (herein after referred to as CMSF) with regard to cash or stock dividend or rights shares or public offering subscription money lying unclaimed or undistributed or un-allotted with the issuer of listed securities for long time.

2. For conducting the audit with regard to cash or stock or rights shares or public offering subscription money lying unclaimed or undistributed or un-allotted

with the issuer of listed securities held with issuer company’s bank accounts and suspense BO account(s) or the amounts or securities transferred by them to CMSF.

3. Upon requisition by Auditors, all issuers, Central Depository Bangladesh Limited (CDBL), Stock Exchanges, CMSF and other Depository Participants (Broker Houses) shall allow the Auditor(s) to inspect, verify and collect necessary information, records, ledgers and other relevant documents held with them with regard to cash or stock

1. dividend or right shares or public offering subscription money lying unclaimed or undistributed or un-allotted with the issuer of listed securities or transferred by the issuer to the CMSF for completion of audit as per Terms of Reference and scope of audit.
2. Auditors and CMSF will ensure compliance of the relevant rules, regulations and different notifications and instructions issued by the Commission in this connection.
3. Before finalization of audit report and their findings thereto, a tripartite meeting with concerned department of the Commission will be arranged by the CMSF.
4. Appointed auditors will submit their reports and opinions to the Commission and CMSF in due time as per their Engagement Letters.

The statutory, compliance, or external/internal auditors or any assurance/review services including incentive audit services provided by any auditor to an issuer company ought not to be recommended for the same issuer company.

What will the Auditors Do?

01.1 External Audit Firms may engage to check and verify the status of the amount of the unclaimed dividends as per the Rules 9(1), 9(2), 9(3) & 9(4) of BSEC (CMSF) Rules, 2021.

What will the Auditors Do?

- a. External Audit Firms may engage **to check and verify the status** of the amount of the unclaimed dividends as per the Rules 9(1), 9(2), 9(3) & 9(4) of BSEC (CMSF) Rules, 2021.

Cash dividend

- “Rules 9(1) : If any **cash dividend** remains unpaid or unclaimed or unsettled or un distributed for a period of 3 (three) years from the date of declaration or approval or record date, as the case may be --- shall be transferred by the issuer companies to the Fund.”

Findings/Observations Format for Cash Dividend Data

Year	Number of Shares	Declared %	Declared Dividend	Dividend Paid	TDS	Fractional Dividend	Dividend Unpaid	Transferred to CMSF	Remaining Amount (BDT)
Since Listing									

Stock dividend

- “Rules 9(2) : If any **stock dividend or bonus shares** remains un-allotted or unsettled including corporate benefit in terms of bonus shares thereon for a period of 3 (three) years from the date of declaration or approval or record date, as the case may be -- - - shall be transferred by the issuer companies to the Fund .“

Findings/Observations Format for Stock Dividend Data

Year	Number of Shares	Face Value	Declared %	Declared Dividend	Dividend Paid	Fractional Dividend	Dividend Unpaid	Transferred to CMSF	Remaining share
Since Listing									

Rights share

- ← “Rules 9(3) : If any **rights share** remains un-allotted or unsettled for a period of 3 (three) years from the date of subscription or allotment, as the case may be -- - - shall be transferred by the issuer companies to the Fund .“

Findings/Observations Format for Rights Share Data

Year	Number of Shares	Declared share ratio	Declared share	Allotted to shareholders	Allotted to Underwriter	Unallotted Share	Deposit in CMSF	Remaining Amount/share
From listing								

Public subscription money

- ←“Rules 9(4) : If any **public subscription money** remains non-refunded for a period of 3 (three) years from the date of subscription or refund, as the case may be - - - shall be transferred by the issuer companies to the Fund .“

Findings/observations format for public subscription money

Year	Number of Shares	Amount of IPO money	IPO Money received by company	Allotted to share	Allotted to shareholders amount	Unallotted amount	Deposit in CMSF	Remaining Amount

- b. Examine and review all transactions in **suspense Beneficiary Owner's (BO) account** of the respective issuer company / security maintained for the purpose of bonus shares, right shares or any other purpose.

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- c. Examine and **review share register** as well as suspense BO account maintained by the issuer company / security for paper share (non-demat share) for the purpose of unclaimed / undistributed / unallotted cash / bonus / right / stock dividend along with accrued entitlement with subsequent corporate actions.
- d. Examine, review and **verify all dividend distribution reports** submitted as per Directive No. BSEC/CMRRCD/2021-386/03, dated 14/01/2021 and also reconcile with the line item in balance / notes to the accounts.

Balance of Distribution/ Disbursement details of Cash & Stock Dividend	Cash (BDT)	Stock (Nos.)
Total unpaid/undistributed held in different Bank Accounts BDT as on Date...		
Balance of Unclaimed or undistributed Shares under Different Accounts as on Date		

The status of unpaid/undistributed Cash Dividend as ofas per Books of Account ofis as follows:

Total unpaid/undistributed Dividend held in different Bank Accounts BDT as on Date as per Report	Dividend Payable as per audited financial statements as of	Difference
		-

Total unpaid/undistributed Dividend/stock held in BO ID as per Report	Total unpaid/undistributed Dividend/stock held in BO ID as per Report as per audited financial statements as of	Difference

- e. Examine, review, and report **status of the bank interest accrued** on the unclaimed cash dividends, IPO subscription money, or right share subscription money as well as dividend and interest pending in Foreign Currency (if any).
- f. Examine, review, and report on the amount and **status of unclaimed dividend lying in the foreign currency** where applicable.

Reconcile the paid-up capital

- g. Auditors should examine, review and **reconcile the paid-up capital** with the increase of its capital, time to time, through issuance of stock and rights and **shareholding report (RT-14) as per CDDBL's report**.
- On the course of doing **reconciliation of Paid-up Capital** should consider the **Schedule-X**, [Total paid-up capital - (Minus) RT-14 = Paper Share of the Issuer].

Year	Number of Shares	Face Value	Share Capital	Nature of Dividend	Declared %	Declared Dividend in No. of shares	Declared Dividend in BDT
Since Listing							

- To consider the sponsor/director shareholding position whether compliance in order of minimum shareholding of them individually and collectively.
- h. Examine, review and **reconcile the declared amount of unclaimed dividend** (stock & cash) by the issuer company / security **before implementation of CMSF Rules** as per dividend distribution compliance report and subsequent reports by stock exchanges.

Financial Year	As per the Compliance Report (Before CMSF)				As per report (After CMSF)			
	Stock		Cash		Stock		Cash	
	Declared %	Declared & Approved Dividend	Declared Dividend %	Declared & Approved Dividend Amount	Declared %	Declared Dividend	Declared %	Declared Dividend Amount
Since Listing/ implementation of compliance report								

i. **Examine** all aspects of the issuer company's procedures to determine **the fairness and accuracy of its dividend payments to the investors**; etc.

- Description of Cash/Stock Dividend Distribution Process Flow, Right Issue Process Flow, etc.

j. **Report on the reconciliation of CDBL report**

Central Depository Bangladesh Limited (CDBL) is the sole securities depository of Bangladesh, it has various reports among which the reports required for this type of functional audit are as follows:

- RT - 14: Investors total share holdings at the record date (Electronic Share)
- RT - 32: All settlement/credit at the record date (even fraction and from suspense)
- RT - 41: Non-cash calculation as per record date share holdings (Bonus/Right)
- RT - 42: Cash dividend calculation as per record date share holdings (Cash dividend)
- RT - 74: Cash calculation of fraction stock dividend
- RT - 91: Calculation of total suspense/unpaid (Stock)

Reconciliation with the information from the above reports in this audit can accurately visualize stock and stock dividend information in many cases such as:

Reconciliation of RT-41 [Non-cash calculation as per record date share holdings (Bonus/Right)]

Year	RT - 41	=	RT-32	RT - 91	Total (RT-32 + RT-91)	Difference
In declared year						

Reconciliation of RT-42 [Cash dividend calculation as per record date shareholdings]

Year	RT - 42	=	RT-42	Less TDS	Bank Transfer	Difference
In declared year						

k. **Any other issues**

Any non-compliance with securities laws observed by the external auditors will be included in the audit reports.

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Conclusion

Considering the protection of investors, this initiative of the securities regulator has opened up a path of transparency and accountability in this part of the capital market, as a result of which it is believed that institutional good governance will be strengthened by enforcing laws among listed securities. In this case, an engaging external auditor can play an important role, and these functions will establish the protection of the investors and increase the confidence of the general investors in the stock market, which in turn will result in interest in investment; and investors hopefully will stay for long-terms in our capital market.

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Examination of Relationship between Stock Returns and Foreign Exchange Rates in China Perspectives: A Wavelet Coherence Approach

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Abstract

This study has used wavelet coherence and found out co-movement and time frequency causality between stock exchange and foreign exchange of China. The finding reveals that, the relationship between stock returns and foreign exchange is positive and causality has occurred in a very low frequency area. The co-movement between the two series has only in the period from 1991 to 1998 but in the period from 1999 to 2017 has no co-movement. Therefore, it clearly represents that time causality and co-movement between foreign exchange and stock exchange have existed only on short time basis. This result suggests that investor as well as portfolio managers should invest their investment considering time causality and co-movement of two series and policy maker should take steps to mitigate the risk and return.

Keywords

Co-movement; China; Stock Exchange; Foreign Exchange; Wavelet Coherence

Introduction

Stock market is the backbone of the economy and is impacted by many macroeconomics variables (inflation, money supply, interest rate, GDP, foreign exchange and so on) and non-macroeconomic variables (such as political instability, climate situation, cultural impact, sentimental

impact and so on). Foreign exchange price has a vital effect on stock markets and makes volatility between stock price and foreign exchange price. Therefore, an in depth relationship exists between foreign exchange and stock markets. The previous study found that there has been a positive and negative relationship between share price and foreign exchange price and also have granger causality between them. (Granger, Huangb, & Yang, 2000).

On 1st October 2016, China yuan (CNY) formally achieved memberships of the IMF's Special Drawing Rights (SDRs) basket, escalating the pace of RMB's internationalization. Since CNY is an international reserved currency, it will be used in many countries for various reasons, for which CNY will make volatility. Therefore, we are trying to find out whether CNY has a positive or negative relationship with Shanghai stock price.

Many studies recognized that fluctuations in stock rate have both positive and negative directions with financial markets. The world has observed many events -such as the US financial crisis which also defined world financial crisis in 2007-2008, the European debt crisis 2010 and Asian financial crisis 1997, and those events have a very negative and adverse effect on the financial market. Most developed countries financial markets faced losses drastically during

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financial crisis periods (Zolfaghari & Sahabi, 2017), Which drove to insolvency in many financial institutions after bank lending and liquidity crisis, (Caporale, Hunter, & Menla Ali, 2014). According to theory, export-oriented firms get more benefits than import oriented firms because of currency depreciation, which permit export-oriented firms to export more goods or services and finally raise their stocks prices. On the other hand, import oriented firms may suffer from the declination of stock prices because depreciation of currency declines their stocks prices (Bahmani-Oskooee & Saha, 2016).

However, the dynamic relation between exchange rates and

the stock market has created questions. Measuring exchange-rate and stock-market interconnectivity is increasingly recognized as of vital importance because it concerns portfolio management, the allotment of assets and risks. The recent financial turmoil has led to increased financial market volatility. In particular, foreign exchange purchases in leading currencies have been decreasing and have had a negative impact on returns on stocks (Caporale et al., 2014). Present literature explores extensively the impact of exchange rates on stock returns before and after the global financial crisis and employs different methodologies, raising questions about existing

methods of econometric analysis and the efficacy of current risk management. Moreover, due to the failure of previous studies to obtain clear results on the relation between exchange rates and inventory returns using these econometric models, existing economic time series models are unable to predict time and multi-scale models. They were criticized for being limited to one or two scales (Tsai, 2012) (Zolfaghari & Sahabi, 2017) (Reboredo, Rivera-Castro, & Ugolini, 2017) (Granger et al., 2000): short and long term. These approaches include popular low-figure (OLS) norm, models for co-integration and error correction, VAR and volatility models, such as ARCH and GARCH used in risk management. The Autoregressive Distributed Label Model (ARDL) is one of the most advanced linear timeseries methods used to estimate co-integration and error correction models. One drawback of this model is that stationary and non-stationary variables are combined. As a result, there has been a good understanding of the interactions between the exchange rates and the stock markets among investors, corporate managers, fund managers, policy makers and academics. Moreover, financial disruptions have shown that market shocks can rapidly spread to other markets through a contagious effect mechanism (Zolfaghari & Sahabi, 2017). Thus, the issues created by recurring financial

crises must be resolved urgently and the econometric methods used to calculate uncertainty on the financial markets must be checked. The key downside of such time series models is that they have only one sample predictive power. In addition, the models have not discussed investors' heterogeneity because the financial markets are very complex, with thousands of investors without consistent investment horizons. Instead they have varying investment periods, from a few seconds to a few years. For example, short-term investors, including day traders, are speculating and transactions calculated by transient conditions such as viral effects, market emotions or mental factors. Around the same time, long-term investors like institutional investors invest in stocks as they do, and adopt macroeconomic rules more closely and are more likely to invest than short-term investors. The paper is more based on recent research describing how

the wavelet analysis is applied to stock prices. For instance, Reboredo, Rivera-Castro and Ugolini (2017) analyze the co-movement between stock prices and petroleum and renewables. Our research, by contrast, examines a dynamic connection between exchange rates and stock returns in the BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa). Tsai (2012) analyzed the relationship between stock prices and exchange rates in a dataset that spans a quantitative decline between January 1992 and December 2009, in particular for six Asian economies (Malaysia, Philippines, Singapore, South Korea, Taiwan and Thailand). (Grinsted, Moore, & Jevrejeva, 2004) find out that European equity-based market sharing has generated contagion or key risks. This paper makes a variety of literature contributions. First, by carrying out a wavelet analysis, it advances on existing literature to research complex connections between exchange

rates and stock returns. We chose a wavelet analysis because it is a clear and reliable approach that uses non-stationarity to examine their co-movements in financial time series. In particular, the paper utilizes the wavelet coherence which, in contrast to co-integration and limited to one or two holding periods, provides time-varied correlations between exchange rates and stock returns for different investment horizons. Wavelet consistency has a unique benefit, offering regions that demonstrate the direction and extent of exchange rates and stock returns, and disclose the relation between cause and effect over time and frequency. Finally, our findings provide more perspectives on the foreign equity and monetary markets, and the correlation between exchange rates and share returns, for policymakers, investors and portfolio managers. The research follows the wavelet method for analysing co-movements

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between the exchange rate and share return.

The rest of the paper is organized accordingly. Section 2 examines the current literature; Section 3 describes our methods; Section 4 describes the evidence; Section 5 introduces and addresses our analytical findings and the research implications; and Section 6 introduces our findings.

Literature Review

Theoretical Motivation

This paper adopts two contrasting theoretical models that explain the relation between exchange rates and stock returns, namely good market theory (flow-oriented theory) and portfolio balance theory (stock-oriented theory).

First, Dornbusch and Fischer's (1980) theory of good markets suggests that exchange rates stimulate asset returns, implying that the weakening of the

exchange rate has a beneficial impact on stock prices. In this respect, depreciation of the currency induces export demand from companies. The weak currency, in particular, renders exports more competitive, thus raising demand for foreign exports. Devaluation of the exchange rate often discourages imports as inputs to output are more expensive. In fact, if imports are expensive, they cause sales to fall, leading to a decline in corporate profits and consequently also in stock prices. Depreciation thus stimulates aggregate demand, increasing the balance of trade and real economic growth. Furthermore, empirical literature indicates that the effect of exchange rates on stock returns is positive (Caporale et al. 2014; Ülkü & Demirci 2012).

Secondly, Bearson's (1981) and Frankel's (1983) portfolio balance theory is based on a negative relationship between exchange rates and stock prices.

It argues that exchange rates depend on the demand for financial assets, such as shares and bonds (Bachmani-Oskoe & Saha, 2016)(Chkili & Nguyen, 2014)(Wong, 2017). Besides, the theory notes that exchange rates are dictated by stock market conditions. In the bull market, for example, demand for inventories is increasing, increasing stock prices. It also means high expectations of domestic economic growth, which in effect raises the interest rates and, as a result, foreign investor capital inflows. As a result, stock price rises boost exchange rates, as exchange rates adapt to shifts in demand and supply of domestic and foreign financial assets required for international portfolio diversification. Moreover, the rise in stock prices leads to higher wealth-based companies, thereby increasing their production and sales volumes. As far as stock growth is concerned, growth contributes to aggregate demand that boosts up the real economy.

In the bear market, however, asset prices are falling, causing exchange rates to depreciate. Some empirical studies that tested this hypothesis are discussed here (Caporale et al. 2014; Chkili et al. 2014; Tsai 2012; Wong 2017). 2.2.

Previous Literature on Relationship between Stock Returns and Exchange Rates

Existing literature on dynamic exchange-rate tied with stock returns is comprehensive and

confined primarily to short-term economic or long-term methodologies. Most studies have findings that are mixed. Some research studies found that exchange rates and stock returns are related positively (Bahmani - Oskooe & Saha, 2016; Caporale et al., 2014; Ülkü & Demirci, 2012). Some studies have also shown insignificant relationship between the pair, despite reported negative connections (Caporale et al, 2014; Chkili & Nguyen, 2014; Wong, 2017), (Alagidede, Panagiotidis & Zhang, 2011). Many empirical studies show the positive relationship between exchange rates and stock returns. Bahmani- Oskooe and Saha (2016), particularly for export-oriented firms, found a significant positive correlation between exchange rate and stock return.

They use the nonlinear, self-regressive distributed lag

models (NARDL) from 1992 to 2012, with a number of countries, including Brazil, Canada, Chile, Indonesia, Japan (Alagidede, Panagiotidis and Zhang 2011) Korea, Malaysia and Mexico. Similarly in the United Kingdom the positive relationship between Ülkü and Demirci (2012) depends on managing the impact of stock returns in emerging and advanced countries. From 2003 to 2010, they used daily and monthly info. They say that exchange rates have a big effect on equity returns, along with a robust local stock market, for countries receiving net foreign capital inflows. In the mutual movements, Lin expressed strong relation between stock market and foreign exchange market, strongly expressing during the crisis. Diamandis and Drakos (2011) analyze exchange rates and stock returns and conclude that the relation between these countries is

positive. These two economic series have interacted with US stock returns by co-integration and multivariable Granger causality testing and monthly data between January 1980 and January 2009. The results show that the US stock market reduces the exchange rate / stock price correlation. Using annual data from South Africa from 1979 to 2014 and co-integration calculator, Mitra (2017) reveals a long-term positive relation between exchange rates and stock returns.

Tsai (2012) notes, on the other hand, a negative relationship between exchange rates and stock returns. A number of countries such as Malaysia, the Philippines, Singapore, South Korea, Taiwan and Thailand have been using quantitative regression and monthly data between 1992 and 2009, with stronger linkages at extremes. In a truncated cross-association estimate, Bashir, Yu, Hussain and Zebende (2016) examine the association of exchange rate and stock market for various capital horizons with the causalities of Granger for Latin Americans, namely Argentina, Brazil, Chile, and Mexico. We use monthly data from 1991 to 2015, showing that the exchange rates and stock returns in most selected countries have a negative short-term relationship. In Argentina and Brazil, however, the relationship in both the short and the long term was good. Furthermore, the results show a positive interlink between exchange

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rates and stock returns in all Latin American countries. Finally, Granger causality and statistics from 1992 and 2005 were applied in Alagidede et al. (2011) for five developed countries — Australia, Canada, Japan, Switzerland and the UK — and the results show no long-term link between exchange rates and share price. But Granger's causality in Canada, Switzerland and the United Kingdom defines the relation between the exchange rate and stock prices, and its causality in Japan varies from stock prices to exchange rates. In order to analyze relations among currency exchange rates and stock returns, this variety of results indicates a need to understand the different perceptions of multi-scale frequency bands instead of a two-stage approach because there is little multi-stage and little more. Since the complex relationship between the exchange rate and stock returns

using a wavelet approach has been studied in a broad, multi-scale scale. The above estimate approach gives a fresh and deeper understanding of the subject. To date, however, far too little attention has been paid to multi-scale wavelet analysis, which offers a chance to evaluate series at different frequency levels (Yang, Cai, & Hamori, 2017) rather than just one or both. Wavelet analysis reveals a desirable alternative that simultaneously considers time and frequency domains. The wavelet model is also a very effective calculator, which uses signal processing to analyze the time-frequency aspect of the co-movement between economic sequences. Over time, it offers a deeper understanding of possible interdependencies at various scales (Ferrer, Bolós & Benítez, 2016). It surpasses standard OLS regression, ARDL, Granger or VAR causalities, co-integration and error corrector models that are

currently the most common methods for investigating links between sequences.

Since there has been little multi-scale research that takes a wavelet approach into account the complex relationship between the exchange rate and stock profits. The above estimate approach offers a fresh and deeper understanding of the subject. To date, however, far too little attention has been paid to multi-scale wavelet analysis that gives the potential for analysing series in different frequency scales (Yang, Cai, & Hamori, 2017). The wavelet analysis reveals an appealing alternative that simultaneously takes into account time and frequency domains. In addition, the wavelet model is a very powerful estimator that uses signal processing to examine the time-frequency dimension of co-movement among economic series. It offers a better description of potential interdependencies over time at various scales (Ferrer, Bolós & Benítez, 2016). This outdoors the standard OLS regression, ARDL, Granger or VAR causalities, co-integration and error correction models which today are the most common methods of investigating the relations between these sequences.

Methodology

Wavelet Analysis

The wavelet model is a very powerful estimator that uses signal processing to analyze co-movements between

economic ranges with a single opportunity. It provides an overview of potential interdependence on scales other than one or two (Ferrer et al., 2016). This results in more rigorous results than standard methods, because wavelet analyses generate information on both frequency and time dimensions by using spectral time series as time-dependent bands (Aguiar-Conraria, Azevedo, & Soares, 2008). It allows us to differentiate between a single opportunity cut through multiple scales and clear structures. The wavelet analysis also uses non-stationary and local data (Antonakis, Chang, Cunado & (Ferrer, Bolós, & Benítez, 2016) Gupta, 2017). This is why, due to its versatility, wavelet analysis has become ever more popular in economics and finance (Antonakakis et al., 2017; Ferrer et al. 2016; Yang et al., 2017). A wavelet represents a small "wave packet" that grows and decays in a given period; at the same time, wavelet functions are based on a measure of location, scale parameters, and another wavelet function, ψ in $L^2(\mathbb{R})$, defined as

$$\varphi(r, s(t)) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{|s|}} \varphi\left(\frac{t-\tau}{s}\right), s, \tau \in \mathbb{R}, s \neq 0$$

where s represents the scale parameter, which adjusts for wavelet length; τ stands for the location parameter showing whether the wavelet is centered; s represents a factor of normalization that conserves unit variance of the wavelet; and

ψ denotes a scaling factor that controls the breadth of the wavelet, as scale and frequency have an inverse relationship. As a result, a lower scale suggests a compressed wavelet that detects a higher frequency while a higher scale shows a stretched wavelet that captures a lower frequency. The Morlet wavelet is more commonly used in finance and economy since its amplitude and phase are used (Reboredo et al., 2017). The Morlet wavelet has the following definitions:

$$\varphi(t) = \frac{dy}{4\pi^{1/4}} e^{i\alpha \omega t} e^{-t^2/2}$$

where ω conserves the energy of wavelet as a unit, ω represents frequency without a unit and points as the central frequency. One must obtain $\omega = \omega_0$, which balances the time and frequency localizations. This number is common in the literature on economic applications (Antonakakis et al., 2017; Ferrer et al., 2016; Reboredo et al., 2017). $e^{-(t^2/2)}$ denotes the Gaussian envelope, and $e^{i(\alpha \omega t)}$ stands for a complex analytic wavelet.

Wavelet Coherence

Three different approaches can be used to identify the dependence between two time series in the time and frequency domains: cross-wavelet power, wavelet power spectrum (WPS) and cross-wavelet transformation (Reboredo et al., 2017). The WPS measures the variance of a single wavelet,

which detects and measures the relationship between the two time series; the crosswave power evaluates the covariance of the time series; and the CWT can control the frequency and time dependence between the two time series. Aguiar-Conraria et al. (2008) define wavelet coherence (WTC) as "the ratio of the cross-spectrum to the product of the spectrum of each series, and can be thought of as a local correlation (both in frequency and time) between two series". Wavelet coherence is expressed as the coefficient of the correlation of time-frequency space. We define wavelet coherence as follows:

$$R_w^2(s) = \frac{|S(s^{-1}W_w^{XY}(s))|^2}{S(s^{-1}|W_w^X(s)| \cdot S(s^{-1}|W_w^Y(s)|)^2}$$

where R^2 represents wavelet coherence and S is a smoothing operator. Interestingly, the value of wavelet coherence ranges from 0 to 1. It is a localized time-frequency coefficient of correlation and is a useful technique for the analysis of co-movements over two-time series. Wavelet coherence can be interpreted in the same way as the correlation coefficient, which indicates strong dependence when the value is close to 1 and weak dependence when the value is close to 0. Likewise, the WPS explains the variance between the time series and the covariance, which captures the cross wavelet power between two-time series at each scale or frequency. If the variance of a time series

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becomes large, the wavelet indicates the existence of a large power spectrum. The statistical significance of the coefficient of coherence of the wavelet is estimated using the Monte Carlo simulation, although little is known about its theoretical contribution (Torrence & Compo, 1998).

Phase Difference

The phase difference is the complete duration of the frequency function time series, which gives us knowledge about the delay or synchronization between the two-time series. It also captures positive and negative relations and interactions in the

time-frequency dimension between two-time series. According to Torrance and Webster (1999), the difference between the wavelet coherence process is defined as follows:

$$\phi_{xy}(s) = \arctan \left(\frac{\Im((s^{-1}W_n^{xy}(s)))}{\Re((s^{-1}W_n^{xy}(s)))} \right)$$

where \Im and \Re denote the imaginary and real component parts of the smooth power spectrum respectively. The coherence phase uses arrows, showing the relationship between the two-time series:

(1) When the arrows point to the right (left), the series show in-phase (out-of-phase), and

the correlation coefficient is positive (negative) and (2) when the arrows point down (up) the second (first) variable leads the first (second) variable by a 90° angle. Further, when the phase difference tends toward zero, it suggests that the variables move together at a given time-frequency.

Data

This study has used daily exchange rates based on USD, and stock indices based on Shanghai stock exchange daily returns indices. Data has been collected from Thomson writer's database of University Putra Malaysia. This data includes 27 years of data from 1st January 1991 to 9th October 2017. Because of using daily data, this study finds out different behaviour of different investor in the stock markets and also gets to chance usage of large observation. The long observation is suitable for determination of strong relation between stock exchange and foreign exchange. For exchange we used yuan/us. We calculated exchange rates and stock returns according to the formula:

$$R_t = \log(P_t/P_{t-1}) \times 100 = (\log P_t - \log P_{t-1}) \times 100$$

In here, R_t represents return and P indicates index level at time t and $t-1$.

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 Describes the descriptive statistics of stock returns and exchange return of China economies.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	Stock Return	Exchange Rate
Mean	0.019248	0.001432
Median	0.007438	0.000000
Maximum	31.23236	17.63404
Minimum	-7.776080	-0.900948
Std. Dev.	0.983776	0.218356
Skewness	5.421829	75.46076
Kurtosis	163.3019	6094.613
Jarque-Bera	7506581.	1.08E+10
Probability	0.000000	0.000000
Sum	134.3313	9.993141
Sum Sq. Dev.	6753.417	332.7063
Observations	6979	6979

The mean value of SR and ER indicates that the two series are not in magnitude to each other. Standard deviation, maximum and minimum value indicate that SR is more volatile than ER. Skewness and kurtosis are positive for both series. Moreover, both series failed to reject Jarque-Bera test and indicate that they are not normally distributed. However, for high-frequency data, the maximum time the data faces normality problem.

Unit Root Test

Table 2 describes the **Augmented Dicky Fuller** unit root test of SR and ER. Both series rejected the null hypothesis. Therefore, both series have no unit root and present stationary data series.

Table 2: Augmented Dicky Fuller Test

	At Level	SHANGHAI	YUAN
With Constant	t-Statistic	-80.2315	-83.7223
	Prob.	0.0001	0.0001
		***	***
With Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	-80.2586	-83.7458
	Prob.	0.0001	0.0001
		***	***
Without Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	-38.0172	-83.7248
	Prob.	0.0000	0.0001

Table 3 describes the **Phillips-Perron** unit root test of SR and ER. The both series rejected the null hypothesis. Therefore, both series have no unit root and present stationary data series.

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Table 3: Phillips-Perron Test

	At Level	SHANGHAI	YUAN
With Constant	t-Statistic	-80.6829	-83.7223
	Prob.	0.0001	0.0001
		***	***
With Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	-80.6762	-83.7460
	Prob.	0.0001	0.0001
		***	***
Without Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	-80.7048	-83.7247
	Prob.	0.0001	0.0001

Correlation Test

Table 4 represents the correlation between two series. Both SR and ER have a positive correlation. However, both series have a very small positive correlation. The positive correlation is 0.004369.

Table 4: Correlation Test

	YUAN	SHANGHAI
YUAN	1.000	0.004369
SHANGHAI	0.004369	1.000

Line Graphs of ER and SR

Figure 1 indicate the line graphs of ER and SR. The line graphs represent the structural break of two economic series.

Figure 1: Line graphs of ER and SR

The Residual Value of SR and ER

Figure 2 demonstrates that the lower volatility of both series followed the next low period of volatility and higher volatility followed the next long period of higher volatility. So, clustering of volatility exists both series.

Figure 2: Residual of SR and ER

Empirical results and discussion

We use wavelet analyses to determine the complex relationship between exchange rates and China stock returns, since wavelet analysis is a powerful tool that helps us to quickly identify co-shifts between the choices. It also discusses how the series applies to different frequency bands and how those relationships are changing over time and distance. To analyze the co-moving and leading

relationship between exchange rates and the stock returns of the economy, we use wavelet coherence. The coherence of the wavelets and the progressive difference demonstrate the relationship between the cause and effect of the selected indices.

Wavelet coherence

In this section, we discuss the co-movements and ties between currency and equity returns in CHINA with pairs of wavelet coherence plots. The

horizontal axis is the time element, whereas the vertical axis denotes the frequency variable transformed into days and the colour code measures the co-movement between the indexes. Warmer (red) areas demonstrate that both sets are strongly dependent, whereas cooler (blue) regions demonstrate that they are less dependent. The big black contour of the plots shows the area, as estimated in the Monte Carlo simulation that is statistically significant at 5 percent stage. In addition,

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wavelet coherence shows clearly areas over time and scales in which each index pair is strongly or otherwise dependent, leading to local correlations from 0.4 to 1. The 0.4 local correlation means that there are minor co-movements between the two variables, while the 1 local correlation reveals significant co-movements. The wavelet consistency results, however, must be interpreted with caution (Dewandaru et al., 2016): at the start and end of the cycles, the focus is on time which should be interpreted carefully while in the CWT, the proximity of a specific point is used.

The coherence of wavelets, therefore, appears to discover co-movements in CHINA index pairs, while the dynamic index ties are calculated by observing the lead relationships across different investment horizons. The arrows indicating variations in process indicate the way for interdependence and correlations of cause and effect. Arrows are expected to calculate the difference between phase wavelets in particular (Grinsted et al., 2004). Right and left arrows indicate that the paired series are both phase-in and phase-out. A phase difference of zero means that stock yields and exchange rates shift in the same way, while an out-of-phase wavelet difference indicates that pair sets (i.e. exchange rates and stock yields) travel through different periods and bands to other

directions. In addition, a difference in the phase wavelet phase indicates a positive interaction while the difference in the out-of-phase wavelet phase indicates a negative correlation. Right-up or left-down arrows suggest that stock returns lead as a dependent variable and right-down and left-up arrows indicate that exchange rates lead as an independent variable.

The wavelet coherence plot indicates that the chinses stock and foreign exchange have strong coherence between each other. Both series are strongly dependent at the warmer (red colour) area which exists only lower frequency area (1024) region. Therefore, two series have minor co-movement. The period of co-movement was

from 1991 to 1998, when the world faced the Asian financial crisis. Therefore, the 2008 world economic crisis, the 2010 European debt crisis and 2014 Russian financial crisis had no effects between the stock exchange and foreign exchange of China.

From figure 3, we find out that the comovement between the stock exchange and foreign exchange only occurs in the low-frequency area, which is 1024. The arrows rightward and downward indicate that stock exchange and foreign exchange have positive relationships, and foreign exchange leads the stock exchange. So, this positive relationship between the two variables only supports the flow-oriented theory.

Figure 3: Wavelet Coherence

1991-1994	1995-1998	1999-2002	2003-2006	2007-2010	2011-2014	2015-2017
1000	2000	3000	4000	5000	6000	6500

Fig 3: Wavelet consistency in exchange rates and stock returns. The vertical axis is a frequency component, while the horizontal axis is a time component; the thick black contour is a significant region at a 5 per cent level, and the curved black line is a cone of influence, indicating the regions affected by the edge effects. Right up and down show in-phase, while left up and down are out of phase.

Conclusion

After examination of the relationship between the stock exchange and foreign exchange by wavelet coherence, we find out that a positive relationship exists between the stock exchange and foreign exchange in which foreign exchange leads stock exchange. Moreover, the co-movement influences only short term at the period from 1991 to 1998 when the Asian financial crisis occurred. In the medium and long term, there is no coherence, and the coherence movement is observed only in low-frequency area, which is 1024. Therefore, coherence between two series is very minor.

These findings indicate that investors can invest their capital safely in the long term and medium-term basis but can face a risk in short term basis because, in a short time, the

coherence has occurred between those variables. For example, investors can invest in the Shanghai stock markets in the long term and short term basis for which they don't face any risk for the return of their assets. On the other hand, if they invest for short term, they can lose the return of their assets. Thus, investors and portfolio managers can mitigate their risks. Moreover, financial policymakers can also take proper steps according to our findings so that the financial risk can be decreased.

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Financial Performance of Insurance Companies in Bangladesh: Some Observations

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Abstract

Insurance sector has good contribution in our GDP. The objects of the study are to analyze the financial and operating performance of the insurance sector during the period 2017 to 2022. Sample of four insurance companies is selected based on convenience in data collection. Mainly secondary data are used to arrive at concluding remarks. Major findings and observation are that all the sample companies have satisfactory financial and operating performance leading to target business growth. Practically they need more publicity for creating social awareness in favor of the manifold benefits of insurance activities for the expansion of business advancement in both local and global arena.

Keywords

Financial performance, Financial analysis- vertical & Horizontal analysis, Bench marking, Ratio indicators, Sustainable Business growth and financial statements

Introduction

Insurance is to distribute the loss due to particular risk among various persons. The major function of insurance is to accumulate fund to face the uncertain losses against the risk. Insurance provides certainty, protection, risk sharing, prevention of losses, develops efficiency and economic gains. The Insurance Sector plays an

important role through covering multibillion dollar projects like Bangabandhu Satellite, Padma Bridge, Bangabandhu Tunnel, Ruppur Atomic Energy plant etc. (1) Our National insurance policy 2014 provides 50 major guidelines for the expansion of this sector through the initiative of IDRA. In spite of heavy challenges, there had been increasing trends of insurance precision during 2015 to 2019. Average growth rates were 10% in life and 7.08% in life and Non-life sectors. Per capita gross premium was Tk. 617.81 in 2015. It had also increasing trend which was raised to 799.49 in 2019. We know that world insurance market had 6.6% growth rate in 2019 while it was 3.1% in Bangladesh. (2)

Real global premium growth was 2.9% where life sector contributed 46.30%. In Bangladesh Insurance Sector premium income is dominated by life sector i.e. 70% followed by 30% in non-life Sector. Bangladesh ranks 55th out of 88 economics in 2019 in the activities of life insurance business. We achieved 1.3% of real growth in life insurance premium against 2.2% in global premium growth scenario. (3)

China occupies the longest life insurance market in global context. The emerging market is found in India, China, Brazil and Russia. World insurance market had excellent growth in 2019 providing 5/6 trillion premium in 2019, 46.31% originated from life sector and 53.66% from non-life sector (4).

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In Bangladesh there are life insurance companies and 46 non-life insurance companies. Life insurance sector has a significant role in achieving sustainable development of Bangladesh. It generates good savings investment and employment opportunity strengthening our economic base. Govt. introduced insurance Act 2010 and established Insurance Development & regulatory Authority (IDRA) to facilitate claim payment and pragmatic efforts for the advancement of our economy. (5)

Objectives of the Study

- i. To analyze the financial performance of the

insurance companies during last five years.

- ii. To identify the major determinants of financial performance along with their variations among the sample companies.
- iii. To provide suggestions for developing the same based on environmental opportunity.

Need for the Study

We know that insurance activities and density are the major reflections of overall development of insurance sector. Percentage of total premium income over GDP was .55% in 2017, which rose up to

.57% in 2018 and 2019 respectively. Practically insurance density indicates per capita premium expenditure. This was 8 dollars in 2017 and raised to 9 dollars in 2018 and 2019. There is lack of diversified products in our insurance sector. Agriculture insurance, health insurance, catastrophic insurance and passengers' insurance are not well organized in our economy, out of 167 Million people only 13 million have the insurance facility only. There is shortage of reviewing of feasible products innovative culture digital facility etc. which stand on the way of improvement of this vital sector. This study will be relevant for the policy markets to develop their financial and operating strategies for achieving their Mission and Vision in the context of their CSR (6)

Review of the Related Research Studies

Ahmed & Islam (2017) (7) had a study on "Determinants of Performance of Insurance Companies Evidence from Bangladesh". They found that gross premium and size of the company positively influence the financial performance. While leverage has negative impact on the same. Age has insignificant negative impact. They suggest for controlling premium income, size and leverage factors prudently.

Ahmed, & Sarkar (2019) (8) authored an article on "Measurement of financial Soundness of life insurance Companies in Bangladesh: An

Empirical Study" They found that the sample companies had more liquid assets. Financial health is not up to the mark compared to Z score. They followed CAMEIS ratio and multiple discriminate analysis.

Bhawmik et al (2021) (9) had an article on "Compliance of Management expenses Allowance by life insurance Companies in Bangladesh. They mentioned that in five sample insurance companies there is significant relation between overpaid expense and paid up capital, total assets life fund and premium growth. They suggest for controlling the management expense of the insurance sector.

Ahmed & Alam (2015) 10 prepared an article on "Comparative Financial Performance Measurement of Green Delta and Reliance Insurance Company Ltd. in Bangladesh : An Analytical

Study" They narrated that there is a significant relation with in net income and firm size. Average performance of QDICL was better than the other company.

Ahmed (2016) 11 in a significant study on "Financial efficiency measurement of Non-life insurance Comprise in Bangladesh" highlighted that there is significant difference in financial performance of the sample companies.

Islam et al (2017)12 in their in-depth study on "Role of Corporate governance on financial performance: An Analytical Study on DSE listed Insurance Companies in Bangladesh" Showed that corporate governance contributes a significant impact on financial performance of the insurance companies in Bangladesh.

There is positive correlation between ROE and board composition. They suggest for developing the corporate governance to strengthen their financial performance.

Concept of Financial Analysis

Financial analysis is to assess a firm's financial health and future prospects like potential for earning growth, stock price increase, good dividend payout, repayment of financial obligation in time etc. (13)

Financial performance is mashed narrating the short-term solvency, i.e. liquidity of the business earning capacity, activity ratios, long term solvency i.e. debt equity ratio and equity multiplier along with business growth ratios, market ratios, based on sustainable business growth indicators (14).

Trends in financial performance exhibit whether the performance has been increasing or decreasing. For this purpose, bench marking approach is followed practically comparative financial statement and common size statements are prepared for the purpose of horizontal analysis i.e. trend analysis follows the analysis of financial data over a period of time, year to year percentage of changes in financial statements (15)

Common size statements follow vertical analysis showing the relation among the various

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items of financial statements at a particular point of time. In B/S all items are shown as percentage of total assets while in income statements all expenses are shown as percentage of total sales (16)

Concept of Liquidity

liquidity is the short-term solvency i.e. the capacity to repay the short-term obligations out of current assets. Financial performance comprise organizational effectiveness and profit earning capacity. Financial ratios like ROA, ROE, ROI, EPS, stock price, DPS, Marketing, yield ratios etc. are the major determinants(17).

Financial Key performance Indicators (18) consist of profit volume, gross margin, net profit margin, working capital, liquidity ratio, debt to equity ratio, net cash flow, abandoned loan rate, application approval rate

customer acquisition cost, average conditions for loan, etc.

Non-Financial Performance Indicators

- a. Intellectual capital i.e. talent man power;
- b. Their knowledge, skill, experience, devotion, motivation and cooperation;
- c. Branding, corporate image, patent, trust and confidence; and
- d. Organizational culture.

Major sources of funds creating satisfactory performance are:

Borrowing from bonus capital, reserves and surplus deposits like savings fixed current accounts. Financial statements need to be understandable, relevant reliable consistent, comparable, well statured, finely and systematic in contents,

policies, compliance and governance based on internal control, fulfilling social obligations and stakeholder's satisfaction. (20)

Methodology of the Study

The study follows a sample of four insurance companies viz., Provati Insurance, Pioneer Insurance, Desh general Insurance, Sunflower Insurance, selected on the basis of convenience in data covering the period of 2017 to 2022.

Nature and Sources of Data

The study depends on mainly the secondary data i.e. The publications like annual reports of the selected insurance companies.

Techniques of Analysis

- i. Financial performance indicators are narrated for five years period.
- ii. Operational performance indicators are shown year wise.
- iii. Inter firm comparison is shown based on Bench marking approach.
- iv. Mean values of the different variables and variations thereon, are also high-lighted.
- v. Causes and impact of changes in different variables are also elaborated.

Major Findings and Observation

Table 1: Performance Indicators of PIC during 2017-21

Tk. in Crore

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	Average
Gross premium	48.26	48.54	77.16	92.45	105.62	74.40
R.I. Premium	9.19	10.62	13.30	17.09	24.43	14.93
Net premium	39.06	37.91	63.86	75.36	81.18	59.47
Under writing Profit	5.28	5.32	7.38	8.88	9.12	7.19
Investment	2.98	2.96	3.33	4.58	10.82	4.93
Claims Paid	20.51	19.09	23.46	28.09	24.55	23.14
Net Profit Before Tax	6.90	6.97	9.19	11.80	17.60	10.49
Net Profit After Tax	5.15	5.34	7.06	9.20	14.93	8.34

Source: Annual Report of PIC

Table -1 shows that gross premium had an increasing trends during the period understudy. Mean value of net profit before tax was Tk. 10.49 core and after tax it was 8.34 core during the period. There had been increasing trends in investment and under writing premium also.

Table- 2: Performance Indicators of DGIC during 2018-22

Tk. in Crore

	2022	2021	2020	2019	2018	Average
Gross premium	42.90	34.42	30.42	30.42	20.34	31.78
Net premium	29.33	19.32	20.01	16.79	10.22	19.13
Under writing profit	7.78	8.34	7.70	6.59	4.83	7.05
I. Income	16.8	2.29	1.84	1.84	1.72	3.74
Net profit after tax	4.15	4.66	3.62	3.26	2.40	3.22

Source: Annual Report of DGIC

Table- 2 exhibits that there had been decreasing trends in both gross premium and net premiums during the period. Mean value of profit after tax was 3.22 core during the period showing declining trends. Investment income had also decreasing trends during the period.

Table 3: Operating Indicators of PIC During 2017-2021

Tk. in Crore

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	Average
Total assets	101.97	-93.54	-106.73	114.09	139.31	111.13
Fixed assets	14.32	14.71	14.69	25.45	27.16	19.26
Net asset	50.02	52.25	56.25	62.70	77.63	65.77
Net asset per share	16.84	17.59	18.74	21.11	22.34	19.36
EPS	1.74	1.77	2.38	3.10	4.30	2.66
Equity	5.02	52.24	56.25	62.69	67.63	57.76

Source: Annual Reports

Table 3 indicates that average equity had an increasing trend during the period. Net asset value per share and earning per share had also increasing trends showing the increasing operational efficiency of the company.

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Table 4: Operating Indicators of During 2018-2022 DGIC

	2022	2021	2020	2019	2018	Average
Total Assets	9.90	8.94	7.05	6.93	1.21	7.71
Fixed Assets	1.11	1.17	1.26	1.31	1.21	1.01
Equity	4.54	4.52	2.86	2.78	2.72	3.50
Total Liability	5.35	4.42	4.19	4.14	3.02	4.22
EPS	1.4	1.24	1.51	1.36	1.00	1.23
Total Reserve	1.17	7.78	8.8	7.28	4.60	5.8
Debt equity Ratio	1.18	.98	1.47	1.49	1.11	1.24

Tk. in Crore

Source: Annual Reports

Table 4 reflects that equity volume had declining trends during the period. EPS had also declining trends. Average debt equity ratio was 1.11 during the period. It was worst in 2021 and had an increasing trend during 2018 to 2020.

Table 5: Performance Indicators of PIC during 2018-22

	2022	2021	2020	2019	2018	Average
Gross premium	311.14	286.92	290.5	182.32	163.60	302.40
Net premium	166.37	158.12	158.55	182.32	163.60	165.80
Net claim	32.15	33.33	34.58	56.74	59.87	41.35
Under writing profit	62.66	77.54	65.62	39.28	28.45	54.71
Investment income	13.07	9.35	12.91	9.17	8.65	10.63
Net profit before tax	71.85	84.08	75.04	44.01	33.26	61.65
Net profit after tax	51.54	58.66	53.26	34.419	26.74	65.45

Tk. in Crore

Source: Annual Reports

Table 5 presents that gross premium and net premium earning had decreasing trends during 2020 to 2021 with a little increase in 2022. Profit before tax and after-tax profit had increasing trends up to 2021 with a decline in 2022. Average point after-tax was .65 crore during the period. Net claims had decreasing trends, but the under-writing profit had increasing trends except in 2022.

Table 6: Operational Information of PIC during 2018-22

	2022	2021	2020	2019	2018	Average
Total Assets	595.67	579.81	533.88	469.8	449.60	525.75
Equity	396.99	374.54	348.16	38.54	315.44	348.75
Investment	349.58	312.03	287.20	258.91	270.27	295.60
Current assets	543.57	528.22	481.42	415.42	394.24	472.57
Current liabilities	198.68	205.26	185.71	161.2	134.15	177.00

Tk. in Crore

Source: Annual Reports

Table -6 shows that there had been increasing trends during 2018 to 2022 in total assets, equity investment, current assets. Trends in current liabilities were similar except in 2022. This shows effective operational performance of the company.

Table 7: Financial Indicators of SFIC during 2017-2022

	Tk. in Crore					
	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	Average
Gross premium	104.85	81.71	65.03	59.4	62.24	74.57
Net premium	104.39	81.41	64.82	58.47	62.14	70.25
Reinsurance premium	.46	.3	2	.93	.1	.40
Claims paid	54.84	57.38	35.07	54.95	46.43	49.77
Investment income	7.41	8.02	8.38	7.55	5.7	7.60
Total assets	185.9	166.86	165.29	146.82	134.2	160.0

Source: Annual Reports

Table 7 reveals that average gross premium was Tk. 74.57 crore during the period having declining trends compared to that of 2018. Net premium and claims paid had also in declining trend. Investment income had increasing trends except in 2021 and 2022. Total assets had good increasing trends over the period. This shows sound asset management situation of the company.

Practically we know that 46 non-life insurance companies have stiff competition in insurance sector. There is shortage of professional human resources lack of awareness about the manifold benefits of insurance efforts and diversification of insurance products existence of uninsurable properties of public and private sectors etc. are the major barriers to the advancement of this vital sector.

Concluding Remarks and Policy Implication

Based on overall analysis and interpretation of time series data it could be concluded that financial performance of the sample companies is satisfactory although there are variations among the sample companies. Increasing premium increase net earnings, cost control, good payment of claims, corporate governance activities develop equity growth of all the sample companies. There is need for creating social awareness for the practical benefits of insurance activities. We also need trained human resources to popularize the manifold activities of Insurance Companies for the expansion of business growth in local and global arena.

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The Effects of Customer Relationship Management on Customer Satisfaction: A Study on Insurance Sector in Bangladesh

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to look into the theories around how customer satisfaction in Bangladesh's insurance industry is affected by customer relationship management. Data from 260 respondents who are insurance service recipients in Bangladesh was gathered using a standardized online survey questionnaire. A convenience sampling strategy that is non-probabilistic was employed. SPSS was utilized to examine the information gathered. To account for the variation in responses, demographic, descriptive, correlation, ANOVA, and regression analysis were performed. There is a general correlation between all of the independent factors and the dependent variable. The F-statistics calculated value (19.557), with 14 and 145 degrees of freedom and $p < .05$, was reported by ANOVA. This result is greater than the crucial value, indicating that independent variables appropriately contribute to defining the dependent variable and validating the model's fitness. All three of the supported hypotheses have a favorable and considerable impact on client satisfaction in Bangladesh's insurance industry. In the context of Bangladesh's insurance sector, the R-squared value indicates that 48.0% of the variance in "Customer Satisfaction" can be explained by differences in the independent variables "Service Quality, Employee Behavior, and

Handling Complaints." Regression analysis results show that, in terms of relative strength, service quality is the most important independent variable, followed by employee conduct and complaint handling. The study's findings also offer insurance industry practitioners in Bangladesh a useful resource for understanding how CRM affects customer satisfaction and for enhancing client acquisition and retention tactics.

Key Words

Insurance, Customer Satisfaction, Customer Relationship Management, Service Quality, Handling Complaints, SPSS, Bangladesh.

Introduction

CRM is essential for the growth of any organization. CRM's significance is increasing daily across all business sectors. The firm will not be able to adopt a customer service that meets customer needs due to insufficient customer relationship management. Customer relationship management (CRM) is commonly considered the most efficient marketing solution that integrates human and technological elements and is extensively utilized. Customer relationship management combines technologies, procedures, and personnel to enhance customer service interactions and increase the organization's market share. CRM is utilized to enhance

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customer satisfaction and optimize the company's service delivery [1]. Client relationship management is undeniably advantageous for fostering client loyalty within the firm. CRM is now well established and experimentally validated for organizations. Researchers are motivated to investigate the correlation between customer relationship management, customer loyalty, and satisfaction due to these facts [2]. The researcher is analyzing how the CRM approach and practices affect customer satisfaction and retention in a broad sense. Implementing CRM activities effectively throughout the firm enhanced customer satisfaction. Customers who were content with their previous shopping experiences and after-sales support from the company were more inclined to make repeat purchases through exchange offers and loyalty incentives [3].

CRM, like other management strategies, aims to boost revenues through client retention. CRM success in this scenario is mostly attained by providing customers with enhanced service quality. This study aids scholars and business professionals in understanding which CRM tactics are effective in retaining consumers over an extended period. A thorough literature review was undertaken in customer experience management to fulfill the study's purpose. The study's objective is as follows:

1. To review the CRM effects on customer satisfaction.

Literature Review

A collection of relational strategies used by businesses to attract, hold onto, and strengthen their client connections is referred to as customer relationship management. It has become

apparent that most firms in a variety of sectors can use it as a potential strategy to gain a sustained competitive advantage. Building strong customer relationships is not only necessary given the recent uptick in competition, but it's also essential for differentiation—a critical strategic tool for customer management that emphasizes seeing customers as unique individuals rather than as parties to be packaged. [4] [5]. CRM is used to discover and retain customers. It helps companies make their least profitable customers more profitable. CRM frameworks are advantageous to organizations because they enable them to produce more client data. Customer data is transformed into useful customer information that is utilized for market intelligence [6].

Customer satisfaction is acknowledged as one of the most researched constructs in business literature. Due to its ability to both retain and draw in new clients, this is extremely important in the company's market [7]. "A person's feeling of pleasure or disappointment which occurs as a result of the comparison between product or service performance and expectation" is how Kotler defined satisfaction [8]. Oliver offered an alternative viewpoint, characterizing customer happiness as the "reaction of the consumer to fulfillment." It is an assessment of a feature of a good or service, or it is a determination of whether the

good or service has truly fulfilled the desires of the customer to a satisfactory degree [9].

Understanding the elements that lead to client pleasure is the endeavor of providing service. Customer satisfaction is positively impacted by and significantly correlated with service quality [10]. Hanley lists several strategies for enhancing service quality, such as: satisfying client demands for excellent service and providing a large selection of products; providing premium goods at competitive prices; and addressing customer complaints about products [11].

The relationship between the company and its customers is more likely to improve when employees adhere to the organization's beliefs and habits. One should expect a

reversal pattern of results when an employee act independently. In these circumstances, a consumer can think that the business does not offer the symbolic value benefits that s/he had anticipated, and s/he might form a bad opinion of the business. Put differently, under circumstances similar to the ones mentioned above, an employee is probably going to have a big impact on the perception and attitudes of the company [12]. Positive employee behavior can have the dual benefits of speeding up employee response times to customers and guaranteeing that staff members treat them with courtesy and respect, both of which raise client satisfaction levels [13].

A customer's dissatisfaction with a specific brand they have purchased might be characterized as a complaint.

Consumer complaints may be caused by a variety of circumstances, including disagreements, ignorance, uncertainty, and overblown expectations [14]. The main topics covered in business literature are boosting purchase frequency, promoting brand switching, and attracting new customers. These interventions are more aggressive than defensive, with the exception of defensive marketing research, and there hasn't been much done to promote a company's loyalty through defensive marketing. Examining the interplay between offensive and defensive strategies is their main objective in order to guarantee that market share and benefit are maintained and enhanced. Because of this, the particular objectives were to highlight how crucial it is to infer customer unhappiness and prospective purchasing patterns, as well as to develop a model that would keep customers from switching to other businesses [15].

A conceptual model is created using the prior literature review as a foundation. Within this conceptual framework, three independent variables are identified. They are addressing disagreements, staff behavior, and service quality. The variable that is reliant is customer happiness. This model focuses on the notion that customer satisfaction in Bangladesh's insurance industry is impacted by CRM. This framework posits that a set of hypotheses should be produced.

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H1: Service Quality (SQ) has a significant effect on customer satisfaction in the insurance sector in Bangladesh.

H2: Employee Behavior (EB) has a significant effect on customer satisfaction in the insurance sector in Bangladesh.

H3: Handling Conflicts (HC) has a significant effect on customer satisfaction in the insurance sector in Bangladesh.

Research Methodology

The nature of this research is primarily quantitative. For this study, a descriptive research design was adopted. The perception of the event and experiential marketing among consumers has been ascertained using descriptive study. To get the necessary data, a quantitative survey was also employed as the main method. All people who receive insurance services from

Bangladesh make up the group under study in this study. This population's representative sample consists of city dwellers that previously relied on services from either public or private insurance. A 260-person sample is used. The non-probability convenience sampling methodology has been employed since it is the least costly and time-consuming method available. The survey ran from October 10, 2023, to January 9, 2024, for duration of three months. The survey questionnaire had been distributed via both online and offline means. 302 respondents were sent the survey URL and physical copy by Facebook Messenger, WhatsApp, bank employees, and mail. Twenty-six of the 302 respondents took part in this survey. 260 is the sample size, therefore. To gather information from the respondents for this study, a systematic questionnaire has been created. There were two sections on the questionnaire, A and B, each with a total of 23 questions. In Section A, the frequency distribution of the respondents' demographic profile is based on a nominal scale. The questionnaire was designed with a five-point Likert scale, from "strongly disagree=1" to "strongly agree=5", to assess the constructs of section B. Two software programs have been used to process the collected data: Microsoft Excel and SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) version 25. Microsoft Excel was used to arrange and code the collected data. The software SPSS (v.25) received coded data for analysis.

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework

Data Analysis

Table - 1 to Table -5 contains the detailed information of the respondents' demographic profile, including frequency and percentage.

Table 1: Gender Analysis

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	186	0.72	0.72	0.72
	Female	74	0.28	0.28	100.0
	Total	260	100.0	100.0	

Table 2: Educational Level Analysis

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Higher Secondary	64	0.25	0.25	0.25
	Graduation	136	0.52	0.52	0.77
	Post-Graduation	47	0.18	0.18	0.95
	Others	13	0.05	0.05	100.0
	Total	260	100.0	100.0	

Table 3: Age Analysis

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Below 25 Years	52	0.20	0.20	0.20
	25 - 40 Years	150	0.58	0.58	0.78
	41 - 55 Years	38	0.15	0.15	0.93
	Above 55 Years	20	0.07	0.07	100.0
	Total	260	100.0	100.0	

Table 4: Occupation Analysis

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Student	55	0.21	0.21	0.21
	Job Holder	112	0.43	0.43	0.64
	Businessman	75	0.29	0.29	0.93
	Others	18	0.07	0.07	100.0
	Total	260	100.0	100.0	

Table 5: Monthly Income Analysis

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Below 25000 BDT	77	0.30	0.30	0.30
	25000 BDT - 50000 BDT	93	0.36	0.36	0.66
	51000 BDT - 75000 BDT	66	0.25	0.25	0.91
	Above 75000 BDT	24	0.09	0.09	100.0
	Total	260	100.0	100.0	

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Table 6 reveals that "Customer Satisfaction" has the highest mean value of 3.5058 with a standard deviation of 0.61503 among all the variables included. The variable "Employee Behavior" has the lowest mean value of 3.2819 and a standard deviation of 0.54274 among all the variables entered. The descriptive statistics indicate that all variables have a mean value greater than 3, which is favorable for the analysis.

Table 6: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
Customer Satisfaction	260	3.5058	.61503
Service Quality	260	3.3817	.56714
Employee Behavior	260	3.2819	.54274
Handling Complaints	260	3.3752	.51184

The correlation analysis findings are displayed in Table 6. The study analyzes the correlation coefficient between service quality, employee conduct, complaint handling, and customer satisfaction in the insurance industry in Bangladesh. It also denotes the direction, strength, and relevance of the link between all variables. Table 7 indicates that all the factors have a positive correlation. A substantial correlation exists between Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction. The correlation coefficient is 0.587. The correlation coefficients between Customer Satisfaction and Employee Behavior and between Customer Satisfaction and Handling Complaints are 0.432 and 0.298, respectively.

Table 7: Correlation Analysis

		CS	SQ	EB	HC
Pearson Correlation	CS	1.00	.587	.432	.298
	SQ	.587	1.00	.179	.088
	EB	.432	.179	1.00	.201
	HC	.298	.088	.201	1.00

Table 8 shows that the significance level (p-value) is 0.001. The predictors are significantly better than expected by chance, since the p-value is less than 0.05. There is a correlation between customer satisfaction in the insurance industry of Bangladesh and the impact of customer relationship management. A lot of the variation in the independent variable can be explained by the regression line, which is set by the independent variables. The results can be reported similarly to previous ANOVA tests: $F(14, 245) = 19.557$; $p < .05$, indicating a good fit for the model with 14 and 245 degrees of freedom. The estimated F-statistic value of 17.668 exceeds the critical value, indicating that the independent factors significantly contribute to defining the dependent variable. An overall association exists between the dependent variable (Customer Satisfaction) and all the independent variables (Service Quality, Employee Behavior, and Handling Complaints).

Table 8: ANOVA Analysis

	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	38.374	14	2.741	19.557	.001 ^b
	Residual	62.475	245	.255		
	Total	100.849	259			

a. DV: Customer Satisfaction

b. Predictors: (Constant), Service Quality, Employee Behavior and Handling Complaints

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Table 9 illustrates that the R square value of 0.480 in the model summary indicates the proportion of variance in the dependent variable that can be accounted for by all the independent variables. Only 48.0% of the variation in "Customer Satisfaction (CS)" is attributed to changes in the independent variables "Service Quality (SQ), Employee Behavior (EB), and Handling Complaints (HC)." The R-value of 0.693 represents the multiple correlation coefficients, indicating the combined influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable. There is a moderate positive association between the independent variable (customer satisfaction) and the dependent variables (service quality, employee behavior, and handling complaints). The adjusted R-squared value of 0.453 indicates that the three variables can explain 45.3% of the variance in the motive for individual donations.

Table 9: Model Summary

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Sig.
1	.693 ^a	.480	.453	.001

Table 10 Coefficient compares the relative importance of each coefficient in the regression model. The Standardized Beta Coefficient column displays the impact of each individual variable on the independent variable in the model.

Table 10: Coefficients Analysis

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Hypothesis Result
		B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	.410	.523	-	.795	.502	-
	Service Quality	.275	.098	.271	2.771	.006	H1: Accepted
	Employee Behavior	.229	.073	.237	3.265	.003	H2: Accepted
	Handling Complaints	.213	.062	.284	3.537	.001	H3: Accepted

The significance level is set at .05 and all predictors are statistically significant ($p < .05$). The multiple regression analysis results in Table 10 show that Service Quality (SQ) has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction in the insurance sector of Bangladesh. Service Quality is considered an important predictor ($\beta_1 = 0.271$; t -value = 2.771; $p < .05$) and is accepted for this study. The multiple regression analysis results in Table 10 show that Employee Behavior (EB) has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction in the insurance sector of Bangladesh ($\beta_1 = 0.237$; t -value = 3.265; $p < .05$). Employee Behavior is considered an important predictor and is accepted for this study. Table 10 shows the results of a multiple regression analysis indicating that Handling Complaints (HC) has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction in the insurance sector of Bangladesh ($\beta_1 = 0.284$; t -value = 3.537; $p < .05$). This variable is considered an important predictor and is accepted for this study.

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Findings

The descriptive statistics indicate that all variables have a mean value greater than 3, which is favorable for the analysis. Correlation indicates that all variables are positively connected except one. Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction are closely correlated. An overarching relationship exists between the dependent variable, customer happiness, and all independent factors, including service quality, employee behavior, and addressing complaints. 48.0% of the variance in "Customer Satisfaction (CS)" may be attributed to the fluctuations in the independent variables "Service Quality (SQ), Employee Behavior (EB), and Handling Complaints (HC)". All predictors are statistically significant ($p < .05$) since their p-values are below 0.05. All three hypotheses were found to have a favorable and considerable impact on customer satisfaction in the insurance market of Bangladesh.

Recommendations

The study provides recommendations derived from the findings to help academics and business practitioners gain a deeper knowledge of customer experience management activities that impact customer satisfaction in the insurance sector.

1. Insurance companies were less focused on service quality in the past compared to their current emphasis on it. However, trends have shifted due to intense market competition and a wide array of options available to customers. Therefore, insurance businesses need to improve their service quality to attract customers and thrive in an ever-changing climate.
2. Customer - friendly demeanor was completely lacking at one point. Insurance companies were not very focused on how to

manage customers. Insurance companies have started to shift their focus towards providing excellent customer service. They have initiated the development of a specialized section to effectively handle client interactions. Therefore, insurance companies should prioritize enhancing customer-friendly practices to meet client satisfaction.

3. Most insurance companies are indifferent to their consumers' complaints. They make no effort to address consumer concerns. Customer satisfaction increases when insurance firms address their concerns. Insurance companies should prioritize effectively managing customers' complaints.

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Income Tax Assessment Manually in Digital Bangladesh

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Tax is the main source of revenue collection for government in most parts of the world. Unlike mineral-resource-rich countries, Bangladesh heavily relies upon tax collected from public sources to run the show. As per law, taxpayers are required to submit the income tax return on an annual basis. Post return submission, the tax authority does the “Income Tax Assessment”. Basically, the process of examining the “income tax return and related tax liability” by the Income-Tax department is called “Tax Assessment”. Unfortunately, the process of tax assessment in Bangladesh is still done on a “manual” basis and bureaucracy still exists. Due to this manual process, the suffering of a taxpayer has become a regular picture.

In Bangladesh, this tax assessment process is “manual”. Post-tax return submission, all the subsequent steps are manual. In fact, the tax assessment orders are typed on a computer with classical Microsoft Word and there is no central/area-wise back up “archiving system” within the tax administration of Bangladesh. In an era dominated by digital advancement, the question whether manual tax assessment in Bangladesh represents a necessary oversight or an administrative failure has gained considerable attention nowadays. Therefore, it is not surprising that this manual approach, which examines the financial data of millions of Bangladeshi taxpayers, suffers from inefficiency, bias, and error.

Let us illustrate the “manual tax assessment procedure” and correlate the level of bureaucracy involved with each step:

Income Tax Workflow	Process	Level of Bureaucracy
Taxpayer’s Identification Number (e-TIN) Registration	Online	No
Tax Deducted at Source (TDS) Management	Online	No
Income Tax Return Submission	Online or Manual	Low
Notice from the Income Tax Authority	Manual	Medium
Hearing and Documents Submission	Manual	High
Follow-up with the Income Tax Authority	Manual	High
Typing Tax Assessment Order	Manual	Very High
Appeal Process against the order	Online or Manual	High

The Digital Transformation Landscape in the Bangladesh Tax System

Bangladesh has made substantial strides in adopting digital technology in various sectors, including finance, telecommunications, and governance. Some digital transformation initiatives are seen in the tax system as well, such as the introduction of online taxpayer's identification number (e-TIN) registration, the expansion of online Tax deduction at source (e-TDS) collection all of these have created the foundation of an opportunity of modernizing income tax assessment

processes. However, the step of "income tax assessment" in Bangladesh continues to depend on manual processes, and the reason behind this approach is nothing but bureaucracy.

Opportunities for Improvement

While manual processes of income tax assessment are deeply rooted in Bangladesh's tax administration workflow/experience, there are opportunities for gradual improvement without shifting the gear fully from "manual to automation" through the following methods:

- Bangladesh could adopt a **"hybrid approach"**, combining manual processes with digital tools and platforms. This approach allows the gradual integration of digital technologies while maintaining the familiarity of manual procedures. Rather than a sudden shift, a phased transition to digital tax assessment could be more feasible. This involves prioritizing critical aspects of the tax assessment process for digitalization while maintaining manual processes for the rest.
- Bangladesh can invest in robust data management systems to enhance the efficiency of manual assessments. Streamlining data collection, storage, and retrieval of information can reduce errors and delays.
- Prioritizing the training for skill/capacity development of tax officials is crucial. Equipping them with the skills needed to adapt to digital tools can facilitate a smoother transition. **Recently, we have seen the European Union (EU) fund and arrange a 6-day training session on "Advanced Audit" for National Board of Revenue (NBR) officials.**

A balanced and gradual approach that leverages the strengths of both manual and digital methods may provide a

more realistic path forward. By investing in infrastructure, capacity building, and data management, Bangladesh can make strides toward modernizing its tax assessment processes while ensuring inclusivity and fairness for all taxpayers. It's not just a matter of embracing technology but doing so in a way that aligns with the country's unique circumstances and needs.

Recommendation and Way Forward

While digital transformation offers numerous advantages,

the challenges faced by Bangladesh, including resource constraints, a complex tax environment, and data privacy concerns, make a complete shift to digital assessment a formidable task. However, we can definitely start a pathway/ journey, considering the below aspects:

- i. International Best Practices:** We can provide examples of countries (mainly Asian success stories) that have successfully transitioned to digital tax assessment systems and discuss what

- i.** Bangladesh can learn from their experiences, focusing on their technological infrastructure, policies, and the outcomes achieved.

- ii. Digital Tax Assessment Systems:** we can implement a robust digital assessment system and integrate that into the tax assessment process. We can bridge the status quo with a digital system and make the adoption process easy for the tax authorities.

- iii. Showcase the benefits of Digital Tax Assessment:** We can showcase the advantages of shifting to digital tax assessment and gain benefits, such as increased transparency, efficiency, reduced corruption, and better revenue collection.

To conclude, the answer is complex here. Whether manual tax assessment in Bangladesh represents oversight or administrative failure. We believe both factors are liable.

Re-evaluating the Impact: Bangladesh's New Income Tax Act 2023 and Provident Fund Concerns

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Introduction

In a significant legislative move, the Parliament of Bangladesh enacted the Income Tax Act, 2023 (ITA, 2023) on 22 June 2023, replacing the Income Tax Ordinance, 1984. Among the various provisions introduced, one stands out for its potential adverse effects - the imposition of tax liability on the income of the funds (except SEC approved mutual funds, alternative investment funds, real estate investment trusts and exchange traded funds).

Impact on Provident Funds

The alteration has sent ripples through the employment landscape, particularly impacting Provident Funds, which are crucial for ensuring retirement and separation benefits for employees. These funds are established in compliance with the provisions outlined in the Bangladesh Labor Act, 2006.

Apart from re-fixing the income year from 'January-December' to 'July-June', the provident funds are also obligated to make provisions for tax liability on their income (mainly from financial assets) at a rate of 27.5%, except for the assessment year 2023-2024, where the tax rate is set at 15%.

Discrepancies in Taxation Practices

Section 63 of the ITA, 2023 further complicates matters by

mandating the taxation of income from financial assets on a cash basis. As opposed to that, the funds are required by their governing rules to maintain their books of accounts on an accrual basis, adhering to the International Accounting Standards (IAS) and International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS). This disparity results in a temporary difference between the carrying amount and tax base of the receivable in terms of accrued interest, leading to a sudden 'deferred tax expense' and corresponding 'deferred tax liability' in the income year 2022-2023.

Consequences Illustrated

To illustrate the tangible consequences of these changes, let's consider a recognized provident fund's investment in Bangladesh Saving Certificates (BSP) and Treasury Bonds with a 05-year tenure. Let's also assume an annual investment of Tk. 20 lakh in BSP in 2019 and Tk. 02 crore in treasury bonds in 2020. The Interest rate for BSP is 11.28%, where the TDS rate is 10%. The Interest rate for treasury bonds is 10%, where Bangladesh Bank does not deduct tax at source. Corporate tax rate for the AY 2023-2024 is 15% vide the SRO no. 333-Law/Income Tax-20/2023 dated 06 December 2023. Since there is no mention of the corporate tax rates for the subsequent years, a tax rate of 27.5% is considered thereafter.

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Extracts of the Statement of Profit or Loss and Other Comprehensive Income

	2018-2019	2019-2020	2020-2021	2021-2022	2022-2023
Income from interest from BSP & Treasury bond	2,25,600	22,25,600	22,25,600	22,25,600	22,25,600
Current tax on interest from BSP*	(22,560)	(22,560)	(22,560)	(22,560)	(78,960)
Deferred tax on income from treasury bond**	-	-	-	-	(22,00,000)
Net surplus after tax	2,03,040	22,03,040	22,03,040	22,03,040	(53,360)

* During the period from financial years 2018-2019 to 2021-2022, income from the recognized provident funds was exempted from income tax under para 6 of the 6th Schedule, Part A of the Income Tax Ordinance, 1984 (ITO, 1984). Despite the exemption, a 10% tax deduction at source was implemented on interest from BSP, in accordance with section 52D of the ITO, 1984. This deducted tax served as the final discharge of tax liability of the taxpayers in compliance with section 82C of the Ordinance. As such, a 10% tax provision on accrued interest income was made annually up to FY 2021-2022.

However, on the income during FY 2022-2023, a 15% tax was imposed as per the respective SRO (no. 333 of 2023 as mentioned above) on the realized income (cash basis) in line with section 63 of the ITA, 2023. Section 163 of the ITA, 2023 stipulates the tax deducted at source from BSP interest (u/s 105) as the minimum tax liability. Consequently, the remaining tax liability was recognized as the current tax expense in the Statement of Profit or Loss and Other Comprehensive Income.

** As the income of the recognized provident funds was tax exempted and the Bangladesh Bank does not deduct income tax at source on income from Treasury Bonds, there were no deferred tax implications. However, with the removal of tax exemption for the income during the financial year 2022-2023, the deferred tax expense and corresponding deferred tax liability are manifested in the relevant financial statements. On the temporary difference between the carrying amount of Tk 80,00,000 (20,00,000*4yrs) of income receivable (equivalent to the closing balance of income receivable from treasury bonds)

and the tax base of Tk 0 (zero), a deferred tax liability is recognized at the rate of 27.5%, and an equivalent amount is recorded as deferred tax expense.

Immediate and Long-term Effects

The presented example reveals a substantial reduction in the fund's net surplus after tax from Tk. 22,03,040 over the preceding 03 years to a loss of Tk. 53,360 in 2023. This accounting treatment, triggered by the imposition of income tax on the fund, has far-reaching consequences for individual employees. Immediate effects

may include a diminished provident fund balance, affecting those intending to leave within a few months.

Moreover, employees who are separated from the organization, say in 2021 and 2022, received interest based on accrual accounting of a mere 10% (for interest income from BSP) or no tax implication (for income from treasury bonds). However, under the provisions of the ITA, 2023, when these interest amounts are received in

cash in 2023 or later, they will incur a higher tax impact of 15% or 27.5%. This additional tax burden, reaching up to 27.5%, will have to be borne by existing members of the provident fund (employees), leading to a substantial reduction in their provident fund balances.

As exemplified above, from the year 2018-2019 to 2021-2022, the fund earned Tk. 2,03,040 after tax in the first year and then Tk. 22,03,040 after tax in the subsequent years. The

employees (members of the fund) who left the organization during that period received their balances with the provident fund including interest earned by the fund. However, in the year 2022-2023, the current tax and deferred tax impact on the previously accrued income of the fund were accounted for, which resulted in a detrimental net surplus after tax, totaling Tk. 53,600 for the concerned year. This financial setback will adversely affect individual members' balances in the

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provident fund, comprising both contributions (principal amounts) and accrued interest. Consequently, there is a risk that employees may incur a reduction in proportional interest over the course of the year.

For new employees who have not yet qualified for interest accrual during the year, the impact may be more severe. The negative net surplus after tax could potentially lead to a loss not only in interest but also in the principal amounts invested. This scenario implies that employees, irrespective of their tenure, might witness a decline

in the real value of their investment, especially when considering the impact on purchasing power parity.

Conclusion and Recommendation

In light of these pressing concerns, it is imperative to reconsider the imposition of tax on the income of the funds designated for employees' retirement and separation benefits. Private sector employees, already grappling with the challenges of securing constant and sufficient income post-retirement, face limited investment options that promise

steady and adequate returns. Even the Universal Pension Scheme falls short of delivering a robust return, particularly when factoring in the escalating rates of inflation on essential commodities. Furthermore, the limited investment options for savings certificates as well as slab wise reducing rates of returns thereon also do not ensure adequate earnings for a person retired from a private sector job, especially in such an era of extreme inflations caused for many uncontrollable reasons.

Therefore, carefully evaluating the facts and constraints faced by private sectors' retired employees, we all hope that the competent authorities will decide to withdraw the tax imposition on the employee benefits-oriented funds, particularly being provident funds, gratuity funds, workers profit participation funds etc. The livelihood of these hardworking individuals depends on a fair and considerable approach to their financial well-being, especially the crucial post-employment phase.

“Integrated Reporting (IR)”, Opportunities, Challenges and Strategies to Improve: A Critical Review

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Abstract

This study critically reviews the realm of financial reporting, acknowledging the limitations of traditional methods in capturing the holistic value creation and sustainability aspects of organizations. Integrated Reporting (IR) emerges as a comprehensive solution, bridging the gaps between financial, social, and environmental aspects. This paper explores opportunities presented by IR, such as addressing stakeholder demands, capturing business value beyond numbers, unlocking long-term strategic advantages, and gaining global acknowledgment. Despite its potential, IR faces challenges, including the dilemma of information disclosure, global variances in integration, country-specific external challenges, and internal organizational hurdles. To address these challenges, the study proposes strategies such as seeking country-specific institutional support, partnering with professional bodies, offering continuous guidance, and recognizing the diverse needs of organizations. Furthermore, the study identifies key strategies for potential and existing organizations to implement and improve IR, emphasizing the importance of a gradual shift, stakeholder engagement, and a clear linkage between financial and nonfinancial information. The incorporation of climate-related disclosures and

understanding value creation through the six capitals framework are highlighted as crucial steps. As the International Sustainability Standards Board (ISSB) gains prominence, this paper suggests navigating the transition collaboratively to enhance the overall reporting system.

Key Words

Integrated Reporting, IIRC, Sustainability Reporting, Value creation, Climate-related Disclosures

Introduction

Financial reporting plays a significant role as the primary medium of communication for firm-specific financial information. But traditional financial reporting have been criticized for their limited scope in capturing the broader value creation and sustainability aspects of organizations (Steenkamp, 2018). The market value of intangible assets has increased significantly for the last quarter century and it has emerged as a leading asset class (TOMMO, 2020). Traditional reporting does not provide sufficient information of an organization's future prospects and existing value creation processes like ESG factors (Garcia-Sanchez et al., 2021). Numerous organizations opt to disclose their financial metrics in annual reports, while details concerning social and environmental metrics are typically included in separate

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Figure 1: Integrated Reporting Value Creation Framework

Source: (IIRC, 2021)

reports like ESG/CSR/Sustainability reports (Steenkamp, 2018). However, these different reports are often not connected and create confusion for the investors (Sun et al., 2023). Consequently, integrated reporting (IR) can effectively overcome the shortcomings of both financial reporting and ESG reporting by furnishing data on social and environmental metrics, focusing on future perspectives, and delivering organization’s value-creation capability information (Barth et al., 2017; Garcia-Sanchez et al., 2021; Sun et al., 2023).

“IR as a process founded on integrated thinking that results

in a periodic integrated report by an organization about value creation over time and related communications regarding aspects of value creation” (IIRC, 2013b). Integrated Reporting (IR) attempts to scale up qualitative reporting and ensure accountability including the environmental and social effects of a company (Stubbs & Higgins, 2018). The international integrated reporting framework (IIRF) was first issued in 2013, after that it has received worldwide acceptance as a measure for the qualitative disclosure of companies, and nonprofit firms (Dameri & Ferrando, 2022; De Villiers et al., 2017). Creating value for the organization is the prime

concept of Integrated Reporting (EY, 2013).

The following parts critically examine the opportunities and challenges of Integrated Reporting, followed by some approaches to addressing these challenges and finally, some strategies to improve financial reporting using IR in future.

Opportunities to implement Integrated Reporting (IR)

In response to growing stakeholder demands and a call for greater corporate transparency, organizations are increasingly turning to Integrated Reporting (IR).

Addressing Stakeholder Demands and Enhancing Corporate Transparency

KPMG Survey of Sustainability Reporting 2022 highlighted that more than 75% of the top 250 companies of the world in terms of revenue are now adopted IR standards for their reporting (Leacy, 2022). Acknowledging the growing stakeholders demand, South Africa mandated the use of Integrated Reporting (IR) for all the companies listed in the Johannesburg Securities Exchange (JSE) since March 2010. (Zhou et al., 2017) study on Johannesburg Securities Exchange (JSE) listed companies provided evidence that more aligned Integrated Reporting reduces analyst forecasting error and provides more useful information to the capital market than traditional reporting.

Capturing Business Value Beyond Numbers

Financial scandals like Enron and Parmalat have shaken the traditional financial reporting system and forced the standard setters to think of a better reporting system for both financial and nonfinancial information. While International Integrated Reporting Council (IIRC) provides regular guidelines to utilize sustainability reporting with financial reporting to communicate company's long-term value creation process. As a result, IR frameworks contributes explicitly by increasing reputation and legitimacy of companies in Colombia (Macias & Farfan-Lievano, 2017). Moreover, Companies of various sizes persist in their pursuit of sustainable solutions that increase their profitability, which

can be achieved through IR (James, 2013).

Unlocking Long-term Value: Strategic Advantages of Early Adopters

Early adopters of IR can benefit from the understanding of long-term value creation process and improved decision making (Sun, 2015). (Samy & Deeb, 2019) identified significant positive relationship between IR and firm performance through value creation over long time by investigating the EGX30 indexed companies listed in the Egyptian Stock Exchange. while the benefits of IR can be ranged from enhancing reputation, increased stakeholder engagement to greater customer and employee commitment (Frias-Aceituno et al., 2013). Dellas Spa, an Italian company of leading international producer of diamond tools established in 1973, started implementing Integrated Reporting from 2013. As a result, Dellas documented the benefits of IR ranging from improved stakeholders communication, more committed employees, improved suppliers' relationships, better communication of company's values, etc. (Del Baldo, 2019).

Global Integration and Acknowledgement

Acknowledging the potential benefits of IR, the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB) are now using the IR Frameworks as a part of the

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IFRS Foundation to help in achieving an internationally accepted comprehensive reporting system (Integrated Reporting, 2022). IR disclosures are seen as a communication tool that allows for the explanation of the company's business model, strategy, governance, and operational performance to stakeholders (Lodhia, 2015). Consequently, more than 70 countries and 2,500 plus companies have already adopted IR formally till 2022 (Integrated Reporting, 2022).

Challenges

Navigating the landscape of Integrated Reporting (IR) involves confronting various dilemmas and challenges that organizations encounter in their pursuit of transparency and value creation. In this context, this study explores key considerations, from the dilemma in information disclosure and cost-benefit analysis to global variances in

integration and uncertainties about value creation. Additionally, country-specific external challenges and organization specific internal challenges tied to institutional environments and sustainability development are also considered.

Dilemma in Information Disclosure and Cost-benefit Analysis

Since Integrated Reporting helps management to report a lot of nonfinancial information to meet the desire of the stakeholders, management always face a dilemma of how much information they should report. So, A prevalent challenge that companies often confront is determining the extent of information they should reveal in their annual integrated report (Du Toit et al., 2017). Another crucial challenge is the cost of providing extra information. Because, accounting principle states that the benefits of providing

accounting information should be greater than its costs (Belkaoui, 2004).

Global Variance in Integration and Uncertainty About Value Creation

Apart from South Africa and Brazil, Integrated Reporting are still optional in other countries. After all, the success or failure of Integrated Reporting adaptation highly depends on gaining trust of the preparers (Chaidali & Jones, 2017). Additionally, a deep organizational mindset is necessary to implement and maintain the IIRC framework (Al-Htaybat & von Alberti-Alhtaybat, 2018). In addition to that, the IIRC defined value creation as a process of increase or transform organization's capital through business activities, but this definition is still vague and lacks considerable coherence (Dumay et al., 2017).

Country Specific External Challenges

As country specific institutional environment and the level of sustainability development have significant association with Integrated Reporting adaptation (Kılıç et al., 2021). The diverse country specific reporting practice and institutional development with social and environmental awareness differences can pose some significant challenges for IR implementation. For example, LOTOS Group, one of the leading energy companies of Europe based in Poland,

adopted Integrated Reporting framework as the first company in Poland since 2014, while many major energy companies who have been criticized for their negative environmental impact are still in the phase of adapting IR fully.

Organization Specific Internal Challenges

Since compatibility with the adopters existing annual financial and sustainability reporting is very important for IR adaptation (Gunaratne & Senaratne, 2017; McNally et al., 2017), existing organizational practice may pose some challenges for IR adaptation. Moreover, Realizing the advantages of Integrated Reporting in the UK may require several years, given the country's emphasis on long-term value creation and the evolution of organizational culture, structures, and processes conducive to Integrated Reporting can be a time-consuming process (Robertson & Samy, 2020). So, the adopters may not get

benefits from the framework immediately.

Approaches to Address Challenges

Seeking Country Specific Institutional Support

Many stakeholders do not have adequate knowledge about Integrated Reporting, especially in developing countries. As we can see, lower education rate in developing countries are associated with poor stakeholder knowledge of IR, so governments should mandate firms, especially for the publicly listed, financial and government entities, to prepare Integrated Reports annually (Bananuka et al., 2019). The IIRC can seek different governments and policymakers support to create stakeholders awareness and implement IR effectively.

Partnering with Professional Accounting Bodies and Training Providers

The growing acceptance of the Integrated Reporting (IR)

among the larger companies may also induce other managers to adapt IR as their reporting process. Top officials are now more interested in adopting IR in South Africa because the legitimacy of Integrated Reporting is growing (McNally & Maroun, 2018). In addition, Professional accounting bodies that raise awareness, offer practical guidance and training opportunities can play a crucial role in fostering the adoption of Integrated Reporting (IR) within a country (Gunaratne & Senaratne, 2017). So, to boost the IR adoption, the IIRC should focus on partnering with professional accounting bodies and training providers (Robertson & Samy, 2020).

continuous Guidance and Simplification

Continuous guidance, explanations of the key concepts, and research on practical benefits of IR from the IIRC can increase the understandability among the preparers. Because, providing additional guidance on how fundamental concepts of Integrated Reporting (IR) can be practically applied may diminish the perceived complexity of IR (Robertson & Samy, 2020). Moreover, the IIRC should also highlight that companies may not be able to get full benefits of IR without embracing the framework fully. For effective IR implementation, the IIRC should take into consideration of the eight stages (figure 2) of gradual IR implementation plan for

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potential organizations proposed by (Momot et al., 2021).

One Size does not Fit for All

Though many large organizations of the world already adopted the Integrated Reporting fully but the rate of adaptation in small organizations are still low. One of the main reasons for SMEs non-adaptation is the high cost and administrative burden to prepare the Integrated Reports and suggested the IIRC should consider the development of a lighter version of IR Frameworks for the SMEs (Gerwanski, 2020). Additionally, the IIRC should also consider adding more

corporate leaders to their board to increase their contributions towards a well-accepted Integrated Reporting for all (Chaidali & Jones, 2017).

Strategies for Potential Organizations to Implement Integrated Reporting

After critically analyzing the extensive number of publications by different researchers and institutions on guidelines and strategies for implementing Integrated Reporting, this study identifies strategies proposed by three different publications to be helpful in implementing IR in a modern organization.

(PwC, 2015) propose three fundamental foundations (i.e., Materiality analysis, Value creation, and Impact evaluation) on which modern organizations should consider implementing Integrated Reporting in five consecutive stages (i.e., Engage with stakeholders, Refresh company strategy based on stakeholders value propositions, Align internal process to the strategy, Develop Integrated dashboard, and Prepare Integrated Report). (PwC, 2015) introduce integrated dashboard as an organization-specific tool to monitor stakeholder value propositions with some management information.

Secondly, as a part of gradual shifting towards Integrated Reporting (Clare, 2016) suggested five steps strategy for the potential organizations, namely, Issue a statement of intent for the stakeholders, Identify the principal stakeholders and their material issues, Think about value creation and match with the six capitals identified by the IIRC, Rework with the existing business model to capture the stakeholders value and, Develop Integrates Reports based on integrated thinking. The IIRC included these guidelines in their database.

Considering the investors' concern regarding value creation and preparers concerns of complexity in report preparation (Momot et al., 2021) devised a eight stage guidelines for implementing Integrated Reporting in a contemporary

Figure 2: New Business language

organizations. The stages started with a statutory audit of current financial statements followed by defining the proposed reporting format (i.e., Integrated Report) for stakeholders, choose which financial and nonfinancial indicators to be included in the proposed report, set up a team for report preparation, prepare the Integrated Report, receive feedbacks from the investors, evaluate the investors feedback publicly and professionally, and finally, publish the new Integrated Report for all.

Considering these three guiding sources and other relevant information, this study proposes the following key strategy for

implementing Integrate Reporting in a contemporary organization:

- Integrated reporting should be a gradual process rather than a sudden step.
- Before embracing the full IR framework, it is crucial to set a foundation and gather support from the key stakeholders. To do so, identify the principal shareholders, capture their concerns, and gain their support by developing shared value propositions.
- Value creation lies in the heart of Integrated Reporting. In June 2021

International Integrated Reporting Council merged with the Sustainability Accounting Standards Board (SASB) and for Value Reporting Foundation (VRF) to provide a holistic view of value creation process for every organization (Value Reporting Foundation, 2021). Organization must critically assess their resources and capitals (i.e., financial, manufactured, intellectual, human, social and relationship, and natural) and identify how they are going to create value over time using their capitals and communicate with the stakeholders as per the VRF's guidelines.

- Financial statements of IR proposing organizations should be audited. So that true value creation can be measured by comparing the audited figures with Integrated Report figures in future.
- Reassess internal business strategy and align with the proposed shared value creation strategy to foster integrated thinking within the organization. Integrated thinking is defined by (Value Reporting Foundation, 2021) as a process of examination by an organization of its relationship between different operational and functional unites and the resources that the organization utilizes or influences.

Figure 3: Eight Stages Implementation

Source: (Momot et al., 2021)

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guideline for Integrated Reporting assurance in early 2021. Moreover, apart from the International Standard on Assurance Engagements (ISAE) 3000 (Revised), International Auditing and Assurance Standards Board (IAASB) will soon publish additional guidance for extended internal reporting like IR (Dancey, 2021). So, based on these guidelines, reasonable assurance on Integrated Reports can certainly improve both financial and nonfinancial information quality.

Clear Linkage Between Financial and Nonfinancial Information Using Balance Scorecard Strategy

Acknowledging the growing stakeholders demand for nonfinancial information on governance and sustainability, many organizations, such as Aegon N.V., moved towards producing integrated reports instead of annual reports with less detailed financial information (Income Statement and Balance Sheet only). While (Eccles et al., 2014) emphasized in creating proper linkage among these limited financial information with nonfinancial information to capture and communicate organizational value generation process and satisfy stakeholders demands. However, (Dumay et al., 2017) stated that integrated thinking and value creation are not clearly defined so far. So, (Massingham et al., 2018) suggested a new model (figure 3) using learning and growth perspective of Balance Scorecard (BSC) which was first

- An experienced and prudent team should be formed to work with implementing IR frameworks.
- Prepare the draft report and update the contents through systematic review by the investors and professionals.
- Publish the report and monitor the progress of the organization to capture organizational success or failure over IR adaptation.

Strategies for Existing Organizations to Improve Financial Reporting Using IR

Patience in Transition

A gradual shift instead of a radical one is always a prudent strategy. Following the findings of (Lee & Yeo, 2016) that the overall benefits of Integrated

Reporting exceed the costs of its preparation, (Clare, 2016; Momot et al., 2021; PwC, 2015) suggested that contemporary organizations should consider gradual shifting strategies from their existing reporting to Integrated Reporting instead of instant shifting strategies.

Assurance on Integrated Reports

Unlike limited assurance, reasonable assurance improves stakeholders’ protection by reducing the likelihood of financial frauds and misconducts. Though a few companies, such as ABN AMRO N.V., Petronas Chemicals Group, etc., already started to produce limited assurance Integrated Reports, now it is time to move towards the reasonable assurance (Dancey, 2021). Considering the urgency, the IIRC and the International Federation of Accountants (IFAC) jointly published a

Figure 4: Mapping Learning and Growth of BSC to IR

Source: (Massingham et al., 2018)

introduced by Kaplan and Norton in 1992, to measure value creation and integrated thinking explicitly. This model is

Intended to utilize the IR Framework to put integrated thinking into practice. Contemporary organizations may use the newly developed model of BSC by (Massingham et al., 2018) as new strategy to improve reporting.

Incorporating Climate-related Financial Disclosures

Increasing amount of carbon emissions leading to greater greenhouse impact is a major

concern now. Even the investors are now raising questions about the financial reporting on climate impact. Which is relateable to the findings of (Chen et al., 2022) that climate related disclosures improves the firm performance. A taskforce developed by the Financial Stability Board (FSB) recommended some climate-related financial disclosures, specifically for four thematic areas (Governance, Strategy, risk management, and metrics and targets) (Financial Stability Board, 2017). Incorporating these climate-related disclosures into the Integrated Reports could be another

strategy to improve financial reporting.

Unveiling Value Generation Using Six Capitals

Value creation lies in the heart of Integrated Reporting. (IIRC, 2013a) explicitly defines six categories of capitals (i.e., financial, manufactured, intellectual, human, social and relationship, and natural) to help and generate organizational value. Moreover, in June 2021, International Integrated Reporting Council (IIRC) announced the merger with the Sustainability Accounting Standards Board (SASB) and

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<p>formed the Value Reporting Foundation (VRF) to provide better understanding on value creation process for every organization (Value Reporting Foundation, 2021). Without explicitly using the six capitals to generate organizational value like figure 1, firms may not fulfill the stakeholder’s expectation regarding value generating information.</p>	<p>Navigating Transition with the ISSB and Fostering Integrated Thinking</p> <p>Following the Covid-19 pandemic, sustainability reporting emerged significantly (KPMG, 2020). The International Sustainability Standards Board (ISSB) was established by the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS)</p>	<p>Foundation in 2021. Moreover, in November 2021 at the UN climate change conference (COP26), the IFRS Foundation announced that they will issue two exposure drafts (IFRS S1 and S2) for sustainability and climate related disclosures (IFRS Foundations, 2022b). Meanwhile, the IFRS Foundation and the Value Reporting Foundation (VRF) complete</p>
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Figure 5: Strategies for improving financial reporting using IR

Source: Author's own creation

their consolidation in 2022 (IFRS Foundations, 2022a). Since the ISSB will lead the development of sustainability standards and IR is still a voluntary resource, a new concern arises whether the IR will cease to exist (De Villiers & Dimes, 2023). However, IR can still play significant roles within the IFRS Foundation in standard development by connecting financial and nonfinancial information, fostering integrated thinking, and understanding sustainability risks and opportunities using the six capitals (Van Wyk & Els, 2023). So, navigating this transition with the ISSB and fostering integrated thinking using VRF's guidelines, IR can still improve the overall reporting system.

Conclusion

Integrated Reporting (IR) offers a transformative approach, addressing the limitations of traditional financial reporting by integrating tangible and intangible assets. However, challenges including dilemmas in information disclosure, global variances in integration, country-specific external challenges, and internal organizational hurdles. Despite challenges, the future of financial reporting lies in the synergies between IR, climate-related financial disclosure, and sustainability reporting. Even with more focus on sustainability and the establishment of the ISSB, IR continues to play a vital role in connecting financial and

nonfinancial information, fostering integrated thinking, incorporating climate-related disclosures, and understanding sustainability risks and opportunities. As organizations navigate this transition, IR remains a valuable tool for capturing and communicating long-term value creation in a rapidly evolving global landscape.

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A Review of Korean Investment in Bangladesh Export Processing Zones

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Abstract

This paper tries to analyze the current situation of Korean investment in Bangladesh's EPZ. The author also makes an effort to understand the factors and limitations that affect investors' decisions to invest in Bangladesh. Using a standardized questionnaire, data were gathered from a sample of 30 international businesses operating factories in Bangladesh's EPZs. There were quantitative and qualitative approaches applied. By employing a standardized questionnaire to interview the respondents, primary data were gathered. Data analysis employs statistical techniques and finds a few key indications and challenges, and it offers modest strategies for attracting more investment into EPZs. The findings of this study will aid developed-world businesses in the evaluation of their investment plans in Bangladesh.

Keywords

Export Processing Zones (EPZ), Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), Indicators, Obstacles, Strategies, Bangladesh

Introduction

Bangladesh acts as a conduit between Southeast Asia's developing markets and the prosperous ASEAN markets (Biswas & Rahman, 2023). Bangladesh's economy has had a remarkable transformation over the last two decades,

ranking 32nd globally in terms of purchasing power parity (PPP) (Frayes, 2022). Bangladesh has made steady development progress with aspirational targets for investment and economic growth, particularly foreign direct investment (FDI). Bangladesh's Export Processing Zones (EPZ) play a critical role in attracting foreign direct investment (FDI), which raises the country's overall export volume and foreign exchange earnings. The country aims to reach upper middle status by 2021 with an average GDP growth rate of 7.4%, investment-to-GDP ratios of 34% and 50%, \$6.7 billion in average FDI inflow each year, and \$54 billion in exports (The World Bank, 2021). According to Hasan and Ali's (2019) analysis of the role of export-oriented zones (EPZs) on Bangladesh's economy, these zones effectively facilitate foreign direct investment (FDI), exports, and investment, hence drawing in foreign capital. The Covid-19 pandemic has presented business issues for Bangladesh and the rest of the world. To help its esteemed existing and future investors operate their enterprises in EPZ without any hurdles both during and after the pandemic, the government has still adopted a fundamental policy.

South Korea is an important economic ally of Bangladesh and a major force in the building, electronics, and RMG sectors. Bangladesh gained a lot in 1979 from the Korean Daewoo

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Corporation’s worker training initiatives. One of the largest investors in EPZ is the multinational company Youngone, which is headquartered in Korea. Das et al. (2018) studied the factors affecting FDI inflows in Bangladesh and they found that FDI inflow in Bangladesh has a positive correlation with the GDP, inflation, infrastructure, labor cost productivity, trade openness, and trade performance and a negative correlation with tax while political stability has a non-significant negative relationship with FDI inflow. High growth rates, prudent macroeconomic management, demographic dividends, liberal investment policies, strategic

location, flexible and inexpensive labor markets, preferential market access, and services that support an environment that is business-friendly, open, transparent, hassle-free, and expedites investment for foreign investors in EPZs are just a few of the many powerful factors that make Bangladesh a potential destination for EPZ investments (Baby & Sharma, 2017; Park & Jung, 2020).

All of these preliminary talks point out how important it is to understand what influences investors’ decisions to make investments in various nations. Thus, in this study, we aim to evaluate the reasons for the disparity in the amount of

investment received by certain nations from Korean enterprises, given the ambiguity of past findings in this important area of economic development and employment generation through Korean investment in EPZs.

However, due to inadequate knowledge of the country’s investment climate, several sectors in Bangladesh struggle to draw Korean investors while having enormous economic potential. We aim to explore the indications as well as restrictions that may persuade Korean investors to invest in our country due to the ambiguity of prior research addressing the determinants and barriers in Korean investment, particularly in the EPZ in Bangladesh. Additionally, an effort is made to offer a few ideas for boosting Korean investment in Bangladesh. As a result, the current study is both nationally relevant in terms of Bangladesh’s economic development and practical importance. The study would add to the body of knowledge on Korean FDI inflow, particularly in Bangladesh’s EPZs.

Objectives of the Research

Outlining the current state of Korean investment in Bangladesh’s EPZ is the main objective of this study. To assist in achieving the primary aim, the following list of specific objectives is provided:

- To analyze the current situation of Korean investment in Bangladesh's EPZ.
- To explore the factors influencing Korean investment in Bangladesh's EPZ.
- To identify what barriers Korean investors in EPZ encounter.
- To evaluate several strategies to increase Korean investments in EPZ.

Literature Review

FDI in Bangladesh

Due to their favorable characteristics, both developed and developing countries have been able to draw sizable sums of FDI. These factors can essentially be divided into three host nation factors that influence FDI attraction. The

first of these is the policy environment for FDI, which consists of laws for entry and operation involving economic, political, and social mobility, norms of treatment for foreign businesses, the nation's trade and tax policies, an international agreement on FDI, etc. Market size, growth, structure, accessibility to international markets, raw materials, labor availability, physical infrastructure, low resource costs, cost of transport and communications, etc. are the second set of economic determinants. The third set of factors is business facilitation, which includes investment promotion, investment incentives, hassle costs associated with corruption and administration, social amenities, etc. TA et al. (2021) looked at the factors influencing investors' propensities to make FDI in Vietnam's Quang Ninh province. They discovered that the greatest influence on investors'

FDI intents is the appeal to FDI strategies, followed by facilities, public services, and human resources, all of which have a considerable impact, and then the level of living, which also has a major impact. Park and Jung (2020) investigated the factors that affect FDI going abroad to developing countries. They found that although presidential visits only have strong and statistically significant effects on FDI in countries outside of Asia, interstate factors like South Korea's international investment treaties and its official development assistance to host countries have favorable effects on FDI in these nations.

Export Processing Zones (EPZ)

In the nineteenth century, the free trade zones of nations like Singapore, Hong Kong, and Gibraltar served as the inspiration for the EPZ concept. Some of the free trade zones at the time permitted imports and exports to be "customs free," allowing the manufacture and reexportation of a variety of goods. Bangladeshi EPZ has grown to be a desirable site for investment both in Asia and internationally thanks to its geo-regional location, the cheapest and most easily trainable labor force, and moderate production costs. Following the success of the first zone, the Chittagong Export Processing Zone (CEPZ), which transformed Bangladesh into a "New Horizon for Investment," eight EPZs are currently operating in

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Bangladesh. Additionally, CEPZ was acknowledged as the fourth-best and third-best competitive zone in the years 2010-2011 (Hossan, 2022). In order to make Bangladesh a hub for export and investment, the government also plans to establish 100 economic zones. 20000 acres of further land were being bought as of January 2017 (Businessnews24bd.com), while 15528 acres had already been secured. Additionally, it is anticipated that the EPZ would use its potential for production, export, investment facilitation, and most importantly employment generation to assist in realizing the government's goal for 2021 and 2041 as well as SDG targets.

One of the major foreign investors in Bangladesh's RMG business is unquestionably Korea. Bangladesh is the operating market for around 220 Korean businesses. Over 1,60,000 Bangladeshi workers now have employment options thanks to these Korean industries. Other Korean businesses have also expressed a strong desire to participate in Bangladesh's Special Economic Zones. In order to attract more South Korean investors, the Bangladeshi government is also providing them with hundreds of acres of land in Mirsarai, Chittagong, or Moheshkhali, Cox's Bazar. The government of Bangladesh is currently creating 100 Special Economic Zones throughout the nation. More South Korean investment in Bangladesh is welcomed by

Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina as the nation works to attain its major goal of becoming a developed nation. The government of Bangladesh is striving to increase trade and business with countries in the region. Bangladesh now has easy access from Chattogram to the Southeast Asian nations, including Thailand, Vietnam, and Laos. Ahn Seong-doo, a former South Korean ambassador to Bangladesh, predicted that Bangladesh would become a significant producer of electronic goods because it is moving ahead with the creation of special economic zones and EPZs. South Korea benefited from its investments in Bangladesh's EPZs as well. The same amenities are available to Korean business owners as to domestic ones.

Bangladesh has a direct impact on the growth of export-oriented sectors by luring more Korean capital into EPZs. Four areas need to be strengthened in Bangladesh in order to draw long-term Korean investment: land acquisition, public procurement, infrastructure, and citizen security and accountability (Mahuba & Jongwanich, 2019). There is limited literature on the current situation of Korean investment in EPZs as well as the problems, despite the fact that the impact of EPZs on the national economy has been noted in a number of studies. This study examines how these economic enclaves affect economic growth in an effort to close this gap.

Research Methods

The thirty Korean businesses operating in Bangladesh's various Export Processing Zones are the subject of this study. Using an easy sampling technique, the sample businesses of the relevant proportion were chosen from the population. This method was chosen because it can swiftly produce a designated sample with little financial outlay (Biswas, 2018; Biswas & Rahman, 2018; 2019; 2021, 2023; Biswas & Alam, 2022; Biswas, Alam, & Akhter, 2022). 180 executives from the thirty Korean sample companies were chosen for in-depth interviews, five from each (a manager and four functional managers) spanning the areas of production, marketing, finance, and human resources. In addition to them, 120 sample respondents were chosen for interview from among business executives, high-ranking BEPZA officials, the BIDA Ministry of Commerce, and several chambers of commerce and industry. Primary and secondary data are the foundation of the investigation. In-person interviews, phone interviews, and field research methods were used to gather primary data. The secondary information was gathered from publications of the relevant businesses, annual reports work by BEPZA, BIDA, and the Ministry of Commerce, as well as from research journals, newspapers, and seminar papers.

Table 1: The Categories of Sample Respondents

Respondents	Number of Respondents
Business leaders	15
A high official from BEZPA	15
A high official of BID	15
Ministry of Commerce	15
Members of the Korean Bangladesh Chamber of Commerce and Industry	15
Members of the Chittagong Chamber of Commerce and Industry	15
Members of Chittagong Metropolitan Chamber of Commerce and Industry	15
Members of Dhaka Chamber of Commerce and Industry	15
High officials of Korean industries in EPZs	180
Total Respondents	300

Source: Authors' Contribution, 2024

Figure 1: The Categories of Sample Respondents

Source: Authors' Contribution, 2024

Characteristics of the Sample Respondents

In this analysis, first-line managers made up 26.7% of the survey respondents, mid-level managers 30.7%, top-level managers 6.7%, and other organizational positions made up 36.0%. 25.3% of respondents had experience of more than one year, 56.0% had experience of more than five years, 14.7% had experience of more than ten years, and 4.0% had experience of more than fifteen years. 53.3% of all respondents, or the majority of respondents, have a graduate or master's degree, while 32.0% have an undergraduate degree. 13.3% of respondents had diplomas, and 1.3% of the respondents had a higher degree respectively.

Survey Instrument

The respondents are given the survey tool (questionnaire) to complete in order to gather data. The authors created a questionnaire with 25 items to collect information. On a Likert scale with a range of 1 to 5, the respondents are asked to rank each item from a series of statements (for example level of corruption, undisputed transfer of land ownership, absence of local extortion, labor policies and practices, wage rate, skilled labor force, political interference etc.) that represent possible feelings about the factors driving the Korean FDI.

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Reliability of the Scale

To examine the items of measurements for study variables, one of the most popular internal constancy metrics is Cronbach's Alpha (Hair et al., 2006; Nandy & Biswas, 2022; Biswas & Rahman, 2015, 2017; Biswas Alam, & Akhter, 2022). In this study, the degree of internal dependability of foreign direct investment is assessed using Cronbach's Alpha. According to Cronbach (1951), the dependability score is 62, which denotes reasonably strong.

Table 2: Reliability of the Scale

Scale	Cronbach's Alpha	N of items
Foreign Direct Investment	0.62	25

Source: Authors' Contribution, 2024

Findings and Discussions

The current state of Korean investment in EPZs has been attempted to learn. The current state of Korean investment in Bangladesh's EPZ is depicted in the following table:

Table 3: Present Scenario of Korean Investments in EPZs

Particulars	CEPZ	DEAZ	COEPZ	UEPZ	IEPZ	AEPZ	MEPZ	KEPZ	Total
Investment US\$ (million)	310.75	127.35	43.18	0	32.03	23.58	0	8	544.9
% of investment	57.03	23.37	7.92	0	5.88	4.32	0	1.47	100
No. of projects	43	20	3	0	2	2	0	4	74
% of no of projects	58.11	27.03	4.05	0	2.7	2.7	0	5.41	100
No. of employment	63541	10910	4153	0	2009	855	0	2802	84270
% of employment	75.40	12.95	4.93	0	2.38	1.01	0	2.33	100

Source: BEPZA (October-December, 2021)

According to the above data, 74 industries are currently active in various Bangladeshi EPZs. 43 (58.11%) of the industries are present in the CEPZ. CEPZ is where investments are growing at the fastest rate. Regarding industry and investment in DEPZ, the second spot is still held. With investments totaling US\$23.37 (27.03%) million, there are 20 (27.37%) operational industries. The data also showed that 4 (5.41%) industries in KEPZ received \$8 (1.47%) in investment, followed by 3 (4.05%) industries in COEPZ, which received 43.18 (7.52%), 2 (2.7%) industries in IEPZ, which received 32.03 (5.78%), and 2 (2.7%) industries in AEPZ, which received 23.58 (4.32%). However, it is impossible to find any Korean investments in the remaining two EPZs, namely UEPZ and MEPZ, as Korean investors are unwilling to put their money into those areas due to a lack of infrastructure facilities. It is also mentioned that the CEPZ has the most employees, 63541 (75.40%), followed by DEPZ with 10910 (12.95%), COEPZ with 4153 (4.93%), IEPZ with 2009 (2.38%), AEPZ with 85 (5.1%), and KEPZ with 2802 (2.33%).

Figure 2: Present Senerio of Korean Investment in Bangladesh

Source: BEPZA (October-December, 2021)

According to the aforementioned data, Korean investors are more likely to put their money into CEPZ and DEAZ. The indicators that influence the Korean investment in EPZs of Bangladesh have been presented in the following table 4:

Table 4: Identification of Indicators Influencing FDI in EPZs of Bangladesh

Sl.No	Factors	No of Respondents	% of Respondents	Ranking the % Of respondent
1	Availability of raw materials	35	7.5	8
2	Infrastructure facilities	31	9	6
3	Bureaucratic complexities	36	12	3
4	Corruption	30	6	10
5	Employment turnover	38	10	5
6	Skilled labor force	32	11	4
7	Political environment	44	15	1
8	Labor safety	35	8.5	7
9	Regulation on Workers Welfare Association	34	8	9
10	Undisputed transfer of land ownership	35	13	2

Source: Field Investigation, 2024

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Figure 3: Factors influencing FDI

Obstacles Faced by Korean Investors in EPZs

Bangladesh is a desirable location for investment, but the main barrier to increasing Korean investment in Bangladesh's EPZ is a lack of adequate infrastructure, particularly physical infrastructure within the zone like water, electricity, factory & service buildings, warehousing, transporting, telecommunication, police stations, and fire stations. Because of inadequate residential housing, urban facilities, academic institutions, telecommunications

infrastructure, hospitals, and hotel facilities, BEPZA was unable to draw in a sizable number of businesses despite lowering its tariffs. Additionally, export-oriented sectors outside of EPZ benefit from roughly the same incentives, but they are unable to perform to their full potential due to inadequate infrastructure corruption thrives in the pervasive atmosphere of bureaucratic and regulatory control, which is why the attitude of bureaucratic red tape slows the approval of foreign projects and supports it. According to Omar Shadat, president of the Bangladesh German Chamber of Commerce and Industry, government

agencies should exhibit a bureaucratic demeanor for domestic and international businessmen. The investors and policymakers in Korea are aware of this challenge. Many Korean investors also expressed dissatisfaction with what they saw to be subpar services at Dhaka's Hazrat Shah Jalal International Airport. While, for EPZs to draw in foreign investors, commercial accessibility is crucial. Additionally, bad governance Less Korean investors are considering investing in EPZs. As a result, the connection of labor unions with political parties, especially those associated with the

government, also interferes with effective national governance. Due to a lack of one-stop services, investors in Bangladesh face difficulties and complications when making investments. Furthermore, rolling parties and local political leaders frequently interfered inappropriately and threatened to do so, which hindered the amicable investment in EPZ. Most of the speakers at a seminar recently held by Reporters Network Bangladesh (TRNB) claimed that Bangladesh's lax protection of intellectual property rights has deterred foreign businesses from investing there. Microsoft had expressed interest in investing in Bangladesh, according to the honorable Tele Minister Mustafa Jabbar, but they decided against it since Bangladesh did not have any explicit data security regulations. Additionally, the authority of KEPZ is having significant problems transferring land and resolving land disputes, which ultimately caused most of the prospective investments to be redirected from overseas to Bangladesh. A global corporation with headquarters in Korea, Samsung, expressed interest in establishing a factory in KEPZ and investing \$5 billion to produce mobile phones, according to the Korean ambassador to Bangladesh. However, due to land disputes in the KEPZ, Samsung's prospective investment was switched from Bangladesh to Vietnam.

Strategies for Attracting Investment

In an effort to increase Korean investment in Bangladesh, various measures are presented. The suggestions below might be useful in luring Korean investment to EPZ.

Facilities with a developed infrastructure

There must be solutions to every kind of restriction on transportation and communication. To match the demands and expectations of international investors, port and internet infrastructures must be strengthened. Partnerships between the public and commercial sectors should be promoted in this regard.

Removal of Local Interferences

To reduce frequent interferences with the management of EPZ, the government should adopt particular rules, regulations, and awareness among the local community.

Liberalizing Policies

To adjust to the fast-shifting international investment climate, Bangladesh's government needs to liberalize various policies and adopt security laws and regulations.

Political Stability

Conflicts between members of opposing political parties' student and youth wings, as well as factions within the same

party, often affect businesses by threatening to use violence to keep employees away and by obstructing transportation, which lowers productivity and raises costs.

Enhance Labor Laws and Procedures

Bangladesh has labor laws that outline the terms of employment, working hours, minimum salary, leave policy, worker health and safety, and compensation for accidents. In contrast, EPZs are an exemption to the national labor legislation because they forbid union membership.

Study's Contributions

According to the findings of this study, Bangladesh's economic development has been significantly impacted by Korean investment in the EPZ. Additionally, in contrast to other studies, the findings indicate various factors and barriers that may affect FDI in the nation's EPZ. This analysis will therefore aid government and business organization policymakers in reducing EPZ issues and enhancing the efficiency of Korean investment in Bangladesh. The study's results also imply that the authority of the EPZ is required to concentrate on creating an environment that is welcoming to foreign investors and has highly protected rules of regulation and compliance. This will cause other investors, including those from South Korea, and make EPZ a magnet

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for foreign investment. Additionally, the current research suggests certain tactics that could be useful in luring Korean investment to EPZ. Thus, in developing their policies, officials, investors, and exporters may find the research in this paper useful.

Conclusions

In Bangladesh, EPZs are important in luring both domestic and foreign investment. Indicators that are crucial for expanding Korean investment in Bangladeshi EPZs have been found in this study. The EPZ administration needs to concentrate on creating an environment where foreign investors can invest safely and legally. There are specific Acts like the Workers' Rights Act, the Foreign Private Investment Act, the BEPZA Act, and regulations on credit facilities, tax, foreign currency, and customs processes that have been put in place to encourage and produce investment in Bangladesh's EPZs. The process for establishing and running industrial activity in the zone has been more or less made simpler by these Acts and guidelines.

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Leadership in Transformation: Past, Present, and Future

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Leadership is a timeless concept that has evolved over centuries, adapting to the changing landscapes of society, human interaction and technology. From ancient civilizations to modern corporate world, the essence of leadership remains the same: the ability to create a vision, communicate, inspire, and guide others towards that vision. However, the methods and characteristics of effective leadership have transformed over time, matching the shifting dynamics of human relationships and organizational structures.

The Leadership of the Past

In ancient times, leadership was often synonymous with authority and power. Kings, queens, and military commanders ruled through dominance and control, enforcing obedience through fear or force. Leadership was hierarchical, with decisions made at the top and directives cascading down the ranks. Leaders were well-regarded for their strength, bravery, and ability to command and control.

However, there were also examples of more enlightened leadership throughout history. Philosophers, scholars, and spiritual leaders such as Socrates and Buddha inspired followers through wisdom, compassion, and moral authority. Their leadership was characterized by humility,

empathy, and a deep understanding of human nature.

The Leadership of the Present

Leadership has evolved into a more complex and complicated phenomenon in the modern era. As organizations have grown diverse and interconnected, the role of leaders has become increasingly demanding. Today's leaders must navigate a volatile, uncertain, complex, and ambiguous (VUCA) world, where changes are constant and challenges are multifaceted.

Effective leaders in the present day possess a wide range of skills and qualities. They are visionaries who can articulate a compelling future for their organizations and inspire others to join them on the journey. They are strategic thinkers who can anticipate risks and opportunities in a rapidly changing environment. They are empathetic communicators who can build trust, foster collaboration, and empower their teams to excel.

Moreover, contemporary leadership is characterized by a shift towards more participative and inclusive models. Command-and-control approaches are giving way to Servant Leadership, where leaders serve the needs of their followers rather than vice versa. Leaders are expected to listen, engage, and empower those around them rather than simply giving directives.

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The Leadership of the Future

Looking ahead, the future of leadership is likely to be shaped by technological advancements, social changes, and evolving organizational structures. Artificial intelligence, automation, and digitalization are already reshaping the nature of work and the skills required of leaders. In the future, leaders may need to navigate increasingly virtual and decentralized teams, harnessing the power of technology to collaborate across borders and time zones.

Moreover, the purpose and meaning of leadership are likely to evolve in response to broader

societal shifts. As individuals seek more fulfillment and meaning in their work, leaders may need to focus not only on driving profits or achieving targets but also on creating a sense of purpose and belonging within their organizations. Leaders who can inspire and align their teams around a shared sense of mission and values will be best positioned to thrive in the future.

In conclusion, while the fundamental concept of leadership remains timeless, its expression and practice continue to evolve in response to changing circumstances. From the hierarchical structures of ancient empires to the participative models of the

present day, leadership has adapted to reflect the needs and aspirations of society. Looking ahead, future leaders will need to embrace technology, diversity, and purpose while remaining grounded in timeless principles of vision, empathy, and integrity.

In old age, leaders used to be behind, hitting others to go ahead; in the modern day, leaders are at the front, calling others to come forward, and as we advance, leaders have to be with the team, not behind or ahead. As the world continues to change, so must our understanding and practice of leadership.

Ensuring Transparency and Reliability in Financial Reporting: Can Auditors Alone Ensure This?

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Transparent and reliable financial reporting is a cornerstone for establishing trust among stakeholders, empowering informed decision-making, and safeguarding the overall integrity of financial markets. It aligns with principles of good governance and responsible corporate behavior. Transparent and reliable financial reporting refers to the practice of providing clear, accurate, and easily understandable information about a company's financial performance and position (Lepadatu & Pirnau, 2009). Key aspects and principles of transparent and reliable financial reporting encompass various elements including adherence to accounting standards (IFRS), clear presentation, comprehensive disclosures, consistency over time, timeliness, clarity in communication, responsiveness to shareholder needs, and responsiveness to change (Barth & Schipper, 2008). There is a common misconception and expectation gap that auditors are solely responsible for ensuring transparent and reliable financial reporting. While auditors play a critical role in providing an external check on financial statements, they are not the sole factor responsible for ensuring these qualities. Transparency and reliability in financial reporting are multi-faceted and involve the collective efforts of various stakeholders. The involvement of different stakeholders in ensuring transparent and

reliable financial reporting can be comprehended by examining their roles within the financial reporting supply chain. While auditors are integral to the process, the responsibility extends across the entire supply chain.

Financial reporting supply chain refers to the end-to-end process involved in collecting, processing, reviewing, and communicating financial information of a company. According to the International Federation of Accountants (IFAC), the financial reporting supply chain refers to the people and processes involved in the preparation, approval, audit, analysis, and use of financial reports. The financial reporting supply chain involves multiple stakeholders, each playing a crucial role in the generation, verification, and communication of financial information. Key parties and their contributions to the financial reporting supply chain include:

Board of Directors

The board is responsible for overseeing the financial reporting process, ensuring that management follows proper accounting practices, and safeguarding the interests of shareholders (Talerico, 2023). The Board of Directors plays a crucial role in ensuring transparent and reliable financial reporting within an organization. Here are key aspects of their role in this context:

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question and seek clarification on financial matters to ensure a thorough understanding of the financial health of the company.

(v) Communication with stakeholders: The Board communicates transparently with stakeholders, providing clear and comprehensive information about the organization's financial performance, risks, and strategies. Interactive engagement with shareholders to address concerns and questions related to financial reporting fosters trust and confidence in the company.

Oversight and Governance

The Board is responsible for developing and approving financial reporting policies and procedures that align with relevant accounting standards and regulatory requirements (Talerico, 2023). If the Board can ensure the existence of a robust governance structure, it will promote ethical behavior, accountability, and transparency in financial reporting.

Selection and Oversight of Management

The Board appoints senior executives, including the CEO and CFO, who are responsible for the preparation and presentation of financial statements. Regular and effective evaluation of the performance of executives including their handling of financial reporting matters can promote ethical behavior,

accountability, and transparency in financial reporting.

Risk Oversight

The Board can assess and oversee the identification and management of financial reporting risks to ensure that accurate and reliable information is provided to stakeholders (ACCA Global, 2017). Effective overseeing of the establishment and effectiveness of internal controls to safeguard assets and maintain the integrity of financial reporting.

Financial Statements Approval

The Board reviews and approves financial statements before they are released to the public, ensuring that they fairly represent the financial position and performance of the organization (ACCA Global, 2017). Directors should actively

Compliance and Legal Obligations

The Board ensures that the organization complies with applicable accounting standards, laws, and regulations governing financial reporting. They promote and uphold ethical conduct in financial reporting, discouraging practices that could compromise accuracy or transparency.

Audit Committee Oversight

The Board establishes an audit committee, comprising independent directors, to oversee the external audit process and the work of internal auditors (ACCA Global, 2017). They ensure the independence and objectivity of external auditors to enhance the credibility of financial statements. Management's adeptness in choosing a

capable audit committee and safeguarding the independence of external auditors can foster robust corporate governance and integrity of financial oversight.

Management

Management is responsible for preparing the financial statements in accordance with accounting standards and regulations (Warren, Reeve, & Duchac, 2015). They establish and maintain effective internal controls to ensure the accuracy and reliability of financial information. Here are key

aspects of the Management role in the context of transparent and reliable financial reporting:

Adherence to Accounting Standards

Management's deep understanding of relevant accounting standards (i.e. IFRS) and applying these consistently in financial reporting is foundational to transparent financial reporting. It influences the entire process, from accurate interpretation and application of standards to effective communication with

stakeholders, fostering trust and confidence in the reliability of the financial information provided.

Internal Controls

Management is responsible for establishing and maintaining effective internal controls (Prasain, 2023). Effective controls help to ensure the accuracy and reliability of financial information by safeguarding assets, preventing fraud, and promoting adherence to policies and procedures.

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Financial Reporting Policies

Management is responsible for developing and implementing financial reporting policies and procedures that align with industry standards and regulatory requirements. These policies guide the preparation and presentation of financial statements. Effective development and implementation of financial reporting policies and procedures contribute to transparency, accuracy, and reliability in financial reporting. It establishes a strong foundation for organizational governance, compliance, and stakeholder confidence.

Accurate Record-keeping

Management maintains accurate and complete financial records. Management with high integrity and proficiency can ensure the accuracy and completeness of financial

records in accordance with applicable accounting principles.

Financial Statements Preparation

Management is directly responsible for the preparation and fair presentation of financial statements (Prasain, 2023). This includes providing appropriate disclosures and ensuring that the financial statements represent the true financial position and performance of the organization. Management with high integrity and proficiency fosters accuracy, transparency, and reliability of the presented financial information.

Timely Reporting

Management is accountable for ensuring that financial reports are prepared and released in a timely manner, meeting regulatory deadlines, and providing stakeholders with

current and relevant information. Highly skilled and experienced management supports to efficient financial reporting system that fosters timely reporting.

Communication with Auditors

Management collaborates with external auditors during the audit process, providing them with the necessary information, explanations, and access to relevant personnel to facilitate the audit. Management can contribute significantly to the external audit process by fostering an environment that promotes open communication, delivery of accurate and timely information, and cooperation in testing procedures which in turn reinforces the external auditors' assessment of transparency and credibility of financial reporting.

Risk Assessment and Management

Management assesses and manages risks associated with financial reporting. This involves identifying potential risks, implementing controls to mitigate those risks, and regularly reviewing and updating risk management processes (Talerico, 2023). Proper risk assessment and management ensures strong internal controls, regulatory compliances, accurate data practices, and proactive monitoring which contribute to transparent and reliable financial reporting.

Finance and Accounting Department

Finance and accounting teams are central to the entire financial reporting process. They ensure adherence to accounting standards, perform data analysis and contribute to the preparation of financial statements. Here are key aspects of the Finance and Accounts Department's role in the context of transparent and reliable financial reporting:

Transaction Recording

The Finance and Accounts Department is responsible for accurately recording all financial transactions in the accounting system. Skilled and experienced teams ensure that entries comply with accounting standards and principles.

Financial Statement Preparation

The Finance and Accounts Department compiles and prepares financial statements, including the income statement, balance sheet, and cash flow statement, adhering to accounting standards and organizational policies (Farahat & Co., 2023). Their proficiency in accounting principles, regulatory knowledge, and analytical abilities ensures accurate, precise, timely, and adaptable financial reporting. An efficient team ensures the timely closing of financial books at the end of accounting periods. As well, it ensures that all necessary disclosures, including contingent liabilities and related-party transactions,

Ethical Conduct

Management sets the tone for ethical conduct within the organization. Ethical conduct ensures transparency and accuracy in financial reporting by upholding honesty, presenting information objectively, complying with standards, providing timely disclosure, avoiding conflicts of interest, promoting responsible governance, and protecting whistleblowers.

Training and Development

Management can ensure that financial reporting personnel possess the necessary skills and knowledge through training and development programs. This helps maintain a high level of competence in financial reporting activities.

Continuous Improvement

Management continuously monitors and evaluates the effectiveness of financial reporting processes. Regular assessments help to identify areas for improvement and promote ongoing enhancements in reporting accuracy and transparency.

Communication with Stakeholders

Management communicates with stakeholders, addressing inquiries and providing additional information when necessary. Transparent communication can enhance understanding of the financial statements.

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are appropriately presented in financial statements to enhance transparency.

Compliance with Accounting Standards

The Finance and Accounts Department ensures compliance with relevant accounting standards to maintain consistency and comparability in financial reporting. Their proficiency in accounting principles, regulatory knowledge, and analytical abilities ensures that financial reporting best meets and complies with accounting standards.

Internal Controls

The Finance and Accounts Department establishes and monitors internal controls to safeguard assets, prevent errors and fraud, and ensure the accuracy of financial data (Farahat & Co., 2023). Their

expertise ensures that controls are well-designed, effectively implemented, and continuously adapted to changing circumstances.

Audit Support

During external audits, the Finance and Accounts Department works closely with auditors, providing necessary documentation, explanations, and support to facilitate the audit process. If they are open to free communication, delivery of accurate and timely information, and cooperation in testing procedures external auditors' assessment of transparency and credibility of financial reporting becomes easy.

Technology Integration

The Finance and Accounts Department can leverage financial software and systems for data management and

reporting contributing to efficiency and accuracy in financial reporting processes. It not only streamlines routine tasks but also provides the tools necessary for data analysis, compliance, and strategic decision-making.

Internal Auditors

Internal audit functions provide an independent and objective assessment of internal controls and financial reporting processes. They contribute to risk management and ensure that the Financial Reporting Supply Chain operates effectively. Here are key aspects of the internal audit role in the context of transparent and reliable financial reporting:

Internal Control Evaluation

Internal auditors evaluate the design and effectiveness of internal controls related to financial reporting to ensure they mitigate risks and promote accuracy (Lyle, 2008). Their primary objective is to ensure that these controls effectively mitigate risks and promote accuracy in financial reporting.

Compliance Verification

Internal auditors verify that whether financial reporting processes comply with applicable accounting standards, laws, and regulations. This causes Management to be proactive in promoting adherence to established guidelines.

Risk Identification and Management

Internal auditors identify and assess risks associated with financial reporting. Their work not only supports the accuracy of financial statements but also helps in building a robust control environment.

Verification of Financial Transactions

Internal auditors perform tests on financial transactions to verify the accuracy of recorded amounts and ensure compliance with accounting principles (Rahmatika, 2014).

Fraud Detection

Internal auditors conduct investigative audits to detect and prevent fraudulent activities that could impact the accuracy of financial reporting.

Communication with Management

Internal auditors communicate findings and recommendations to management, highlighting areas for improvement in financial reporting processes. Effective communication between internal auditors and management is crucial for ensuring that identified issues are understood, acknowledged, and addressed in a timely manner. It fosters a collaborative approach to improving financial reporting processes and contributes to the overall governance and risk management framework of the organization.

Review of Financial Statements

Internal auditors may conduct post-close reviews of financial statements to validate their accuracy and identify any material misstatements that need correction (Rahmatika, 2014).

Follow-up and monitoring implementation

Internal auditors engage in continuous monitoring of financial reporting activities to identify changes in risk and ensure that control measures remain effective. They also monitor the implementation of recommendations and actions suggested in audit reports to ensure corrective measures are effectively implemented.

Collaboration with External Auditors

Internal auditors collaborate with external auditors, providing them with information and supporting documentation to facilitate their audit process. This collaborative approach between internal and external auditors strengthens the audit process, promotes transparency, and enhances the overall reliability of financial reporting.

External Auditors

External auditors provide an independent assessment of the company's financial statements. They review the entire Financial Reporting Supply Chain to ensure compliance with accounting standards and the

accuracy of financial information. Their opinion adds credibility to financial reports, contributing to transparency and reliability. Here are key aspects of the role of external auditors in ensuring transparency and accuracy in financial reporting:

Independent Verification

External auditors, who are independent of the organization and its management provide an unbiased and objective review of the financial statements (Woods, 2011). They provide stakeholders with assurance that the information presented in the financial statements is accurate and trustworthy in all material aspects.

Examination of Financial Statements

External auditors examine financial records, transactions, and supporting documentation to verify the accuracy of the financial statements. By systematically examining financial records, transactions, and supporting documentation, external auditors aim to provide stakeholders with reasonable assurance that the financial statements are free from material misstatements and accurately reflect the financial position of the organization.

Testing Internal Controls

External auditors evaluate the design and effectiveness of internal controls related to financial reporting, ensuring they are adequate and

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functioning as intended (Warren, Reeve, & Duchac, 2015). By thoroughly evaluating internal controls related to financial reporting, external auditors contribute to the overall assurance that financial statements are free from material misstatements and provide a true and fair view of the organization's financial position.

Risk Assessment

Auditors assess the risk of material misstatement in the financial statements, considering factors such as industry risks, internal controls, and the nature of financial transactions. The purpose of assessing the risk of material misstatement is to enable auditors to conduct a targeted and effective audit, identify potential areas of concern, and

evaluate the overall reliability and trustworthiness of financial statements.

Fraud Detection

External auditors are alert to indicators of fraud and conduct their examinations with a focus on detecting fraudulent activities that may impact financial reporting. The identification of fraud promotes transparency in financial reporting. It ensures that material misstatements or deceptive practices are disclosed.

Audit Opinion

External auditors provide an audit opinion stating whether the financial statements are presented fairly, in all material respects, in accordance with the applicable financial reporting

framework (Lepadatu & Pirnau, 2009). Audit opinion provides stakeholders with assurance regarding the reliability of the financial information presented by the entity.

Communication with Management and Board

Auditors communicate their findings, including any identified issues or areas for improvement, to both management and the board of directors. This communication of audit findings to both management and the board of directors plays a pivotal role in promoting accountability, informed decision-making, risk mitigation, and continuous improvement in the organization's financial reporting processes.

Regulatory Bodies

Regulatory bodies set the framework for financial reporting standards (e.g. IASB, BSEC). They play a crucial role in establishing rules that companies must follow, contributing to consistency and comparability across the industry. Regulatory bodies also oversee compliance, ensuring that financial reporting is transparent and reliable. Here are key aspects of the role of regulatory bodies in transparent and reliable financial reporting:

Setting Accounting Standards

Regulatory bodies develop and update accounting standards (Warren, Reeve, & Duchac, 2015). These standards provide a framework for preparing

financial statements and ensure consistency and comparability.

Regulatory Oversight

Regulatory bodies oversee compliance with accounting standards and regulations by monitoring the financial reporting activities of public companies and other entities.

Rule Making and Guidance

Regulatory bodies issue specific rules, regulations, and guidance documents that organizations must follow in their financial reporting. These rules often address issues like disclosure requirements, recognition criteria, and measurement principles.

Auditor Oversight

Regulatory bodies may oversee auditing firms, registering them, and conducting regular inspections to ensure they meet professional standards and conduct audits effectively.

Enforcement Actions

Regulatory bodies have the authority to impose penalties and sanctions on organizations that fail to comply with accounting standards or engage in fraudulent financial reporting.

Corporate Governance

Regulatory bodies may establish corporate governance standards that include requirements for the composition and functioning of boards of directors, audit

committees, and other governance structures.

Educational Initiatives

Regulatory bodies may undertake educational initiatives to increase awareness among companies, auditors, and other stakeholders about changes in accounting standards and reporting requirements.

Investor Protection

Regulatory bodies aim to protect the interests of investors by ensuring that financial information is accurate, reliable, and transparent, fostering investor confidence in financial markets.

Stakeholder Engagement

Regulatory bodies may seek input from various stakeholders, including the business community, investors, and auditors when developing or updating accounting standards to ensure a balanced and informed approach.

Technology Providers

Technology providers contribute to the Financial Reporting Supply Chain through the development of tools and systems that enhance the efficiency and accuracy of financial reporting processes. Technological advancements, such as accounting software and data analytics tools, can support accuracy and transparency. Here are key aspects of their roles:

Financial Software Solutions

Technology providers offer advanced accounting software that automates financial processes, reduces errors, and ensures adherence to accounting standards, contributing to reliable financial reporting.

Data Management System

Technology providers offer robust data management systems that help organizations store, organize, and retrieve financial data securely, ensuring the integrity and accuracy of financial information.

Automated Reporting Tools

Technology solutions enable the automation of financial reporting, reducing manual errors and ensuring that reports are generated consistently and on time (Iris Carbon, 2023).

Data Analytics and Business Intelligence

Advanced analytics and business intelligence tools help organizations to analyze large datasets, identify trends, and extract valuable insights, contributing to more informed and accurate financial decision-making (Faster Capital, 2023).

Regulatory Compliance Tools

Technology solutions assist organizations in monitoring and ensuring compliance with evolving financial reporting standards and regulations,

Ensuring Transparency and Reliability in Financial Reporting: Can Auditors Alone Ensure This?

reducing the risk of non-compliance.

Audit Technology

Technology providers offer tools that automate audit processes, making audits more efficient, reducing the risk of human error, and enhancing the accuracy of financial statements.

Collaboration and Communication Platforms

Technology facilitates communication and collaboration among different departments involved in financial reporting, ensuring that relevant information is shared accurately and efficiently.

User Training and Support

Technology providers offer training and support platforms to ensure that users understand and utilize their tools effectively, contributing to the accurate use of financial reporting technologies.

Media and Public

The media and the public act as watchdogs, scrutinizing financial reports for irregularities or significant events. Their awareness and scrutiny contribute to the overall accountability and transparency of financial reporting. Here are key aspects of their roles:

Investigative Journalism

Media organizations engage in

investigative journalism to uncover financial irregularities, fraud, or unethical practices within companies, contributing to the detection of potential issues and a more transparent and accountable corporate landscape.

Information Dissemination

Media outlets promote transparent financial reporting by disseminating information, scrutinizing corporate practices, and encouraging accountability within the business community (Pena-Martel, Perez-Aleman, & Santana-Martin, 2018).

Whistleblower Reporting

Media reports can encourage whistleblowers to come forward with information about financial wrongdoing, leading to investigations and corrective actions.

Monitoring Corporate Governance and Reporting Quality

Media outlets monitor and report on corporate governance practices, bringing attention to issues such as board composition, executive compensation, internal controls, and financial reporting system.

Demand for Transparency

The public, including customers and investors, can express their expectations for transparency in financial reporting. This demand encourages companies to adhere to high reporting standards.

Advocacy Groups

Public advocacy groups can play a role in advocating for regulatory changes, improved disclosure requirements, and corporate responsibility, contributing to a more transparent reporting environment.

Public Pressure

Public scrutiny and pressure can influence companies to improve their financial reporting practices and corporate governance to maintain a positive public image (Pena-Martel, Perez-Aleman, & Santana-Martin, 2018).

Boycotts and Consumer Actions

Public dissatisfaction with financial practices can lead to consumer boycotts or actions that impact a company's reputation and bottom line, encouraging companies to address concerns and move to more transparent reporting.

Each party in the financial reporting supply chain has a specific role to play in transparent and reliable financial reporting. While auditors are instrumental in ensuring transparency and reliability in financial reporting, a comprehensive and collaborative approach involving various parties is necessary. The collaboration and effective functioning of stakeholders at various stages of the Financial Reporting Supply Chain are essential for

transparent and reliable financial reporting. According to IFAC, all links in the financial reporting supply chain need to be of high quality and closely connected to supply transparent and reliable financial reporting. The collaboration and synergy among these parties contribute collectively to the goal of transparent and reliable financial reporting.

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Recognition of ICAB membership by ICAEW

Membership Scheme of The Institute of Chartered Accountants of England and Wales (ICAEW) allows the members of ICAB to apply for ICAEW membership based on their experiences.

Eligibility criteria of this membership scheme are a series of questions which assess ICAB Member's experience, achievements, skills and expertise. Each application must be supported by an eligible sponsor. Applicants need to complete an Examination of Experience.

Details of ICAEW Membership Scheme is available at <http://www.icaew.com/membership/becoming-a-member/members-of-other-bodies/campaigns/pathways-to-membership>.

ICAB signed its first Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with the Institute of Chartered Accountants in England and Wales (ICAEW) in 2009. Since then, ICAB has been working with ICAEW as the learning and professional development partner, and also recognized as an approved tuition provider of ICAEW.

As per MoU, ICAB Members can be the members of ICAEW after successful completion of 04 papers out of 15. These members have the opportunity to apply for UK Practising Certificate (PC) subject to meeting the standard ICAEW PC requirement.

Recognition of ICAB Membership by CIPFA, UK

Members of the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Bangladesh (ICAB) are eligible to apply for membership of the Chartered Institute of Public Finance and Accountancy (CIPFA), a globally recognised membership body for the public sector.

An MoU between ICAB and CIPFA, UK was signed on 28 January 2017. Under this MoU, an ICAB member can also become a members of CIPFA subject to fulfillment of certain criteria.

An ICAB Member with good standing having five or more years post-qualification public sector experience are eligible for Full Membership of CIPFA as Chartered Public Finance Accountant (CIPFA) and the members having fewer than five years post-qualification public sector experience are eligible as Affiliate member of CIPFA (CIPFA Affiliat).

ICAB members having CIPFA Affiliate membership, or having no working experience in public sector can gain CIPFA status with the successful completion of exams of only two papers i.e. Public Sector Financial Reporting and Strategic Public Finance.

Membership Pathways Agreement (MPA) with CPA Australia

The Institute of Chartered Accountants of Bangladesh (ICAB) has recently signed a Membership Pathways Agreement (MPA) with CPA Australia, one of the largest accounting bodies around the world. Through this agreement, ICAB members can be the members of CPA Australia just after passing 04 papers (i.e. 1. Ethics and Governance, 2. Financial Reporting, 3. Global Strategy & Leadership and 4. Strategic Management Accounting) out of their 12 papers. This MPA has been in effect since 20 July 2018.

Membership through Chartered Accountants Australia & New Zealand (CA ANZ) International Pathway Program (IPP)

The Institute of Chartered Accountants of Bangladesh (ICAB) signed an MoU with the Chartered Accountants Australia & New Zealand (CA ANZ). Under this, ICAB members living in Australia or New Zealand having five years post qualification experience at anywhere will be eligible to be member of CA ANZ after successful completion of CA ANZ International Pathway Program (IPP).

There will be no requirement of passing CA ANZ general route examinations by eligible ICAB members as their International Pathway Program (IPP) workshop through case studies would examine the contemporary Australasian business, accounting and finance environment relevant for members of ICAB. On the other hand, CA ANZ members can also be members of ICAB subject to having Bangladeshi citizenship and other requirements as prescribed by ICAB Bye-laws.

Membership of the International Valuation Standards Council (IVSC)

Efforts are underway for ICAB to Become a member of the International Valuation Standards Council (IVSC). This would create an opportunity for the members of ICAB to involve in the valuation process of local and foreign investment in Bangladesh.

This would allow Chartered Accountants to put up their highly essential services and play positive roles in attracting foreign investment. With regard to this, ICAB has already conducted a Members Conference. More so, a virtual meeting with the CEO of IVSC was held on 8 June 2021 where the IVSC proposed ICAB to become member of IVSC on pro-rata basis.

Other Memberships

ICAB is an active member of International Federation of Accountants (IFAC), Confederation of Asian and Pacific Accountants (CAPA) and South Asian Federation of Accountants (SAFA). ICAB is also an associate member of Chartered Accountants Worldwide (CAW).